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Agri-food and Tourism
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EcoAgriTourism, in the light of its multidisciplinary character, is a wide-open journal which brings together the opinions of specialists from both academic and economic environment, fostering fruitful collaborations.

The journal's structure covers all aspects of the fields approached, the focus being on original and current researches with applications in agriculture, food industry and rural tourism. Collaborators may feel free to undertake biological and technical aspects as well as aspects with social, cultural and environmental impact. Information of general interest is also welcome for the agriecology-food-tourism axis.

Prof. Romulus Gruia Ph. D.

The Journal of EcoAgroTurism aims at approaching analyses, methodologies, options and references within the journal's framework.

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EDITORIAL

*On behalf of the Organizing Committee of the **BIOATLAS International Conference**, it is our great pleasure and privilege to invite you to join us in Brasov, Romania, between May 27 and 28, 2016.*

“BIOATLAS 2016” Conference provides a forum for food and tourism related professionals, professors, lecturers and PhD students to exchange information on education, research, applications and developments the Food and Tourism and publish the most recent results. The topics include aspects related to Biodiversity and Agriculture technologies, new tendencies in Tourism development, IT&C in Agriculture, Food and Tourism Industry, etc. Contributions from various countries will allow a broadened perspective for all attending.

*After the very successful meetings in **2006, 2008, 2010, 2012 and 2014**, **BIOATLAS 2016** offers us the opportunity to combine the beauty and hospitality of **Brasov** city with some of the outstanding works done on the important topics of food science and tourism, and to make easy contacts and relations among researchers from all around the world.*

Brasov is probably the most beautiful city from Romania and one of the most important cities of Transylvania region, surrounded by the Southern Carpathians. Our city provides a mix of wonderful mountain scenery in the nearby Poiana Brasov, and medieval history with German influences in the old town.

We work closely with the Scientific Committee to provide an unforgettable scientific experience as well as to offer a social program filled with opportunities to share the beauty of Transylvania with colleagues and friends from all around the world in a very familiar and warm atmosphere.

We look forward to meet together in the spring of 2016 for a great Conference in Brasov!

*Romulus Gruia, Liviu Gaceu
Chairs of the Organizing Committee*

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ANALYSIS OF PHENOLIC COMPOUNDS EXTRACTED FROM THREE TYPES OF BERRIES

A. FRUM¹, E. LENGYEL¹, C. GEORGESCU¹, F. GLIGOR²,
O. TITA¹

Abstract: The study was conducted using blueberries, raspberries and red currant. Several phenolic compounds like gallic acid, (+)- catechin, syringic acid, cinnamic acid, resveratrol, chlorogenic acid, caffeic acid, ferulic acid, rutin and quercetin were analyzed using an HPLC method optimized for the determination and quantification of these compounds. The greatest amount of the total phenolic compounds analyzed was found in blueberries, followed by red currant and the lowest quantity was found in raspberries. The greatest amount of gallic acid was determined from blueberries alongside with cinnamic acid, resveratrol, chlorogenic acid, caffeic acid, ferulic acid, rutin and from red currant syringic acid and (+)- catechin. Raspberries were the greatest source of quercetin.

Keywords: phenolic compounds, berries, HPLC

1. Introduction

Blueberries (*Vaccinium myrtillus* L.) are a great source of anthocyanins [1] and other phenolic compounds as well as carotenoids, vitamins and nutrients [2]. The composition of red currants (*Ribes rubrum* L.) is valuable for flavonoids, anthocyanins and ascorbic acid [3].

Raspberries (*Rubus idaeus* L.) are rich in vitamins (A, B1, B2, C, E and PP) as well as anthocyanins, ellagitannins, and mineral elements like iron and potassium [4].

These berries are popular all over the world and they are consumed as fresh fruit or in a processed manner [2,3,4]. Phenolic compounds are found in plants as secondary metabolites, representing the plants way of adapting to several environmental factors. They are known to have a great importance in human health due to their biological activity and that's why they have been used from ancient times as remedies [5,6].

For example, they have antioxidant properties; they reduce the risk of cardio-vascular diseases, cancer, neurodegenerative diseases and diabetes [7].

2. Material and Methods

Sample preparation: The berries were harvested from Romania, Transylvania region. They were

frozen and stored at -20°C. Before the analysis they were defrosted, dried at 40°C and grounded on a domestic mill.

The extraction was performed by adding 10 mL of solvent (CH₃OH : H₂O : HCl 0.12M = 70:29:1 (V/V/V)) to 500 mg of berries. Covered and put it in an ultrasound bath at 40°C for 30 minutes. Cooled, filtered through a 45 µm filter and analyzed.

Phenolic profile: The quantitative and qualitative analysis of phenolic compounds was carried out on a Agilent Technologies 1200 series HPLC system, equipped with degasser, quaternary pump, diode array detector, autosampler and column compartment, both thermostated. The used column was Zorbax Eclipse Plus C18 (250 mm x 4,6 mm i.d. x 5µm), at controlled temperature of 25°C. The elution was performed using mobile phase A (H₂O), mobile phase B (CH₃OH) and mobile phase C (H₂O: CH₃COOH = 96:4). The gradient program was used as follows: 0 min: 15% B and 85% C, 15 min: 75% A and 25% B, 20 min: 15% A and 85% B, 40 min: 40% A and 60% B, 45 min: 5% A and 95% B, 55 min: 5% A and 95% B, 60 min: 85% A and 15% B and 70 min: 85% A and 15% B. The flow rate program was used as follows: 0 min: 0.5 mL/min and 15 to 70 min: 0.8 mL/min. The injection volume was 5 µL and the detection was performed at 280, 303, 330 and 360 nm.

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The standards of gallic acid, ferulic acid, syringic acid, cinnamic acid, chlorogenic acid, caffeic acid, (+)-catechin, resveratrol, quercetin, rutin were purchased from Sigma Aldrich, at HPLC purity.

3. Results and Discussions

The highest amount of phenolic compounds was found in blueberries (Fig. 1-3), the total amount reached was 131.44 mg / 100 g dry weight (d.w.), red currant had 105.38 mg / 100 g dry weight and the lowest amount was found in

raspberries that had 5.62 mg / 100 g dry weight (Tables 1-3).

Blueberries had the highest amount of different compounds like rutin (37.51 mg/100g d.w.), gallic acid (16.86 mg/100g d.w.), caffeic acid (15.05 mg/100g d.w.), cinnamic acid (0.70 mg/100g d.w.), ferulic acid (39.59 mg/100g d.w.) and chlorogenic acid (93.23 mg/100g d.w.). The highest amount of syringic acid (32.08 mg/100g d.w.) and (+)-catechin (42.83 mg/100g d.w.) were found in red currant and quercetin (1.70 mg/100g d.w.) in raspberries.

Fig. 1. Chromatogram of blueberry sample: 1-gallic acid, 2-(+)-catechin, 3-syringic acid, 4-cinnamic acid, 5-resveratrol, 6-chlorogenic acid, 7-caffeic acid, 8-ferulic acid, 9-rutin, 10-quercetin

Table 1. Phenolic compounds from blueberries

Standard	Sample area (mAU*s)	Standard area (mAU*s)	Sample mass (mg)	Standard mass (mg)	Standard concentration %	mg phenolic compounds/ 100 g d.w.
Quercetin	3,97561	371,7557	476,15	5,19	95	0,44
Rutin	169,19725	225,8515	476,15	6,34	94	37,51
Gallic acid	164,44165	467,3984	476,15	5,79	98,5	16,86
Syringic acid	85,56851	392,7161	476,15	5,45	95	9,48
Caffeic acid	271,45139	773,6238	476,15	5,21	98	15,05
Cinnamic acid	16,67113	1117,151	476,15	5,68	99	0,70
Ferulic acid	634,38147	673,0148	476,15	5,05	99	39,59
(+)-Catechin	27,18472	100,7379	476,15	5,19	98	11,53
Resveratrol	7,26196	1058,129	476,15	5,04	99	0,29
Chlorogenic	809,37341	356,8267	476,15	5,15	95	93,23
Total						131,44

Fig. 2. Chromatogram of red currant sample: 1-gallic acid, 2-(+)-catechin, 3-syringic acid, 4-cinnamic acid, 6-chlorogenic acid, 8-ferulic acid, 9-rutin

Table 2. Phenolic compounds from red currant

Standard	Sample area (mAU*s)	Standard area (mAU*s)	Sample mass (mg)	Standard mass (mg)	Standard concentration %	mg phenolic compounds/ 100 g d.w.
Quercetin	0	371,7557	478,43	5,19	95	0,00
Rutin	42,62424	225,8515	478,43	6,34	94	9,40
Gallic acid	154,15508	467,3984	478,43	5,79	98,5	15,73
Syringic acid	291,02097	392,7161	478,43	5,45	95	32,08
Caffeic acid	0	773,6238	478,43	5,21	98	0,00
Cinnamic acid	8,59521	1117,151	478,43	5,68	99	0,36
Ferulic acid	18,30626	673,0148	478,43	5,05	99	1,14
(+)-Catechin	101,47439	100,7379	478,43	5,19	98	42,83
Resveratrol	0	1058,129	478,43	5,04	99	0,00
Chlorogenic	33,45549	356,8267	478,43	5,15	95	3,84
Total						105,38

Fig. 3. Chromatogram of raspberry sample: 1-gallic acid, 3-syringic acid, 8-ferulic acid, 10-quercetin

Table 3. Phenolic compounds from raspberries

Standard	Sample area (mAU*s)	Standard area (mAU*s)	Sample mass (mg)	Standard mass (mg)	Standard concentration %	mg phenolic compounds/ 100 g d.w.
Quercetin	14,98559	371,7557	466,31	5,19	95	1,70
Rutin	0	225,8515	466,31	6,34	94	0,00
Gallic acid	8,50858	467,3984	466,31	5,79	98,5	0,89
Syringic acid	24,41914	392,7161	466,31	5,45	95	2,76
Caffeic acid	0	773,6238	466,31	5,21	98	0,00
Cinnamic acid	0	1117,151	466,31	5,68	99	0,00
Ferulic acid	4,17447	673,0148	466,31	5,05	99	0,27
(+)-Catechin	0	100,7379	466,31	5,19	98	0,00
Resveratrol	0	1058,129	466,31	5,04	99	0,00
Chlorogenic	0	356,8267	466,31	5,15	95	0,00
Total						5,62

Resveratrol, quercetin and caffeic acid were not detected in the red currant sample and in the raspberries sample rutin, caffeic acid, cinnamic acid, (+)-catechin, resveratrol and chlorogenic acid were not found, but in the blueberry sample, all the compounds of interest were found.

Conclusions

The study was conducted on three types of berries that had different amounts of phenolic compounds. The highest amount of total phenolics was found in blueberries, as well as the highest amount of most of the compounds individually.

The lowest amount of phenolic compounds was found in raspberries, as well as the most compounds not detected.

Blueberries are the berries that can provide the highest and most varied content of phenolic compounds from the analyzed berries.

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HYSSOPUS OFFICINALIS L. (FAM. LAMIACEAE) A POTENTIAL PLANT FOOD SUPPLEMENTS WITH ANTI-INFLAMMATORY EFFECT

D. HANGANU¹, A. PÂRVU², A. MĂRCULESCU³, I. ONIGA¹,
B. TIPERCIUC⁴, D. BENEDEC¹

Abstract: Plant food supplements, or botanicals, have high acceptance by consumers. Potentially, they can deliver significant health benefits, safely, and at relatively low costs. *Hyssopus officinalis* L. (Hyssop) is one of the popular herbal, traditionally used for medicinal purposes. Some therapeutic uses based on the traditionally uses must be scientifically proven. Therefore the anti-inflammatory potential of the ethanolic extract obtained from aerial parts of *Hyssopus officinalis* was tested using an experimental rats model of acute inflammation as compared to diclofenac. There were four groups (10 animals per group): one group without inflammation used like witness group (W), one positive control group with untreated inflammation (I), one group with inflammation treated with *Hyssopi herba* extract (H) and a group treated with a nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug, diclofenac (D). The experimental acute inflammation was induced by injecting oil of turpentine (0.6 ml/100g b.w.) into the rat's right hind paw. There were evaluated the leucocytary formula, the phagocytic activity and the nitrite/nitrate levels. The results from the treated group with alcoholic extract were compared with the control group (I), and with the diclofenac treated group (D) values. By the total leukocyte count and differential leukocyte count expressed as a percentage we appreciated the effect of the ethanolic extract on the bone marrow acute phase response. Analysing the results from the differential leukocyte count expressed as percentage in the treated groups with extract and diclofenac, there were found that the total leukocyte count changes were induced by the decrease of the phagocytes percentages, respectively polymorphonucleares (PMN) ($p < 0.0001$) and monocytes ($p < 0.01$). The extract reduced Phagocitary activity, P. Index and the levels of nitrite/nitrate in group with inflammation. The *Hyssopus officinalis* L. extract showed a good anti-inflammatory activity, in model of acute inflammation, comparative with the diclofenac.

Keywords: *Hyssopus officinalis* L., anti-inflammatory effect, plant food supplements

1. Introduction

Plant food supplements, or botanicals, have high acceptance by consumers. Potentially, they can deliver significant health benefits, safely, and at relatively low costs. *Hyssopus officinalis* L. (Hyssop) is one of the popular herbal, traditionally used for medicinal purposes. Some of his therapeutic uses based on the traditionally uses must be scientifically proven, such as anti-inflammatory effect.

Inflammation is a dynamic process that is elicited in response to mechanical injuries, burns, microbial infections, and other noxious stimuli that may threaten the well-being of the host. This process involves changes in blood flow,

increased vascular permeability, destruction of tissues via the activation and migration of leucocytes with synthesis of reactive oxygen derivatives (oxidative burst), and the synthesis of local inflammatory mediators, such as prostaglandins (PGs), leukotrienes, and platelet-activating factors induced by phospholipase A2, cyclooxygenases (COXs), and lipoxygenases [1, 2].

An excessive production of nitric oxide following the inductions of inducible nitric oxide synthase (iNOS) is involved in the pathogenesis of inflammation. Lately NO has received much attention because its wide range of biological effects. Physiologically, NO serves both intracellularly, as a second messenger that

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responds to activation of plasma membrane receptors, and extracellularly as a paracrine factor that carries the information between cells. Pathologically NO excess is cytotoxic. In contrast to conventional signaling ligands such as cytokines, hormones, neurotransmitters which function through specific interactions with receptors, the ultimate action of NO in biological systems is dictated by its chemistry. Moreover, NO and the reactive nitrogen oxide species (RNOS) derived from NO can interact with a wide variety of biochemical targets to elicit diverse biological direct effects and indirect effects. Direct effects are those chemical reactions in which NO reacts directly with a biological target molecule. Indirect effects of NO occur during pathophysiological and toxicological events [3, 4, 5, 6].

Nowadays, there is known an important number of plants containing active principles with antiinflammatory activity. Chemically, these are glycosidic structures, flavonoides saponines, essential oils [7, 8]. It was found that some flavonoids block the activation of iNOS gene, by blocking the nuclear translocation of p65 and subsequent nuclear factor-kappaB inactivation [9, 10].

Hyssopus officinalis L. (hyssop), belonging Lamiaceae family, possess a variety of activities, including antiinflammatory, antioxidant, antibacterial, antifungal, and antiviral properties. These effects explain by the content of the flavonoids, polyphenolic acids, triterpenes, tannins, essential oil, etc. [7, 8].

Considering these aspects, it was studied the comparative effect of ethanolic extract obtained from aerial part of hyssop (*Hyssopi herba*) on inflammation-induced nitric oxide synthesis, using a nonsteroidal antiinflammatory drug, diclofenac, like drug references.

2. Material and Methods

The Animals (adult male Wistar rats) weighing 160 to 200g, 8-12 weeks of age, supplied by the Animal Breeding Facility of the University of Medicine and Pharmacy Cluj-Napoca, were housed in temperature-controlled rooms, with 12:12 hours light: dark cycle and received water and food ad libitum. Experimental inflammation and animal treatments were conducted in accordance with the legislation governing experimentation on animals. There were selected four groups (10 animals per group): one group without inflammation used like witness group

(W), one positive control group with untreated inflammation (I), one group with inflammation treated with *Hyssopi herba* extract (H) and a group treated with a nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug, diclofenac (D). The alcoholic extracts was made in rapport 1:10 in ethylic alcohol 700 and the solvent was removed. The experimental acute inflammation was induced by injecting oil of turpentine (0.6 ml/100g b.w.) into the rat's right hind paw. The extract (30 mg/kg b.w.) and diclofenac (30 mg/kg b.w.) were suspended in carboxymethylcellulose 0.5% with an ultrasound bath (Elma T420) and were administrated i.p. (1 ml/animal).

After treatment the animals were killed by decapitation. Blood samples were taken from the retro-orbital sinus, 24 h after turpentine administration, on an EDTA solution, for the test of in vitro phagocytosis [3], total leukocyte count, and differential leukocyte count, both expressed as a percentage [3, 4, 11, 12] and without anticoagulant for colorimetric serum nitrite and nitrate measurement [4, 5, 13, 14].

Chemicals: Oil of turpentine (Carlo Erba Reagent), EDTA (Inc), Türk solution (Merck), May-Grünwald-Giemsa (Merck), ethylenediamine dihydrochloride (Merck), sulphanimide (Merck), vanadium chloride (VCl₃) (Merck), sodium nitrite (Merck), suspension of *Escherichia coli* 4x10³ germs/ml in saline solution 0.9% produced in the Microbiology Laboratories of the Faculty of Medicine Cluj-Napoca.

Total leukocyte count and differential leukocyte count expressed as a percentage

For total leukocyte count a blood sample dilution 1:10 in Türk solution was prepared in a Potain leukocyte-dropper. The count was performed with an optical microscope (Olympus), using a Bürcker-Türk counting-chamber. Differential leukocyte count expressed as a percentage was carried out on May-Grünwald-Giemsa stained smears [3].

Test of in vitro phagocytosis

20µl suspension of *Escherichia coli* was incubated at 37 °C with 0.2ml blood taken on EDTA, for 20 min., under slow rotation conditions. The samples were used for smears, stained May-Grünwald-Giemsa, on which we calculated: Phagocytosis Index (PI) = number of phagocytes/100 leukocytes and Phagocytes Activity (PA) = number of germs phagocyted by 100 leukocytes [3].

Nitrite and nitrate determination: Serum was deproteinized before NO metabolite analysis.

Nitrite/Nitrate levels were measured using the Griess assay as described previously. Briefly, 100µl of VC13 were added to 100 µl of sample, followed immediately by the addition of the Griess reagents (50 µl sulphanilamide and 50 µl ethylenediamine dihydrochloride). We kept the solution 30-45 min. at room temperature and the absorbance was measured at 540 nm using a spectrophotometer (Cecil 3021) [4, 5, 13].

All data represent the mean of at least three independent experiments. The values are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation. The statistical differences between groups were made using the Anova test. 5% level of statistical significance was accepted in all experiments.

3. Results and Discussions

In this study we investigated the effect of *Hyssopi herba* extract on an experimental acute inflammation. Inflammation is the body's response to cell injury at biochemical level. It is a cascade of changes that continues as long as the tissue injury persists. The inflammatory mediators activate local and systemic responses. The bone marrow acute phase response is part of the systemic response. It is activated by inflammatory cytokines (IL-1, IL-6, TNF- α), and consists of an increased leukocytes production, most phagocytes.

The results from the treated group with alcoholic extract was compared with the control group (I), and with the diclofenac treated group (D) values, for the assessment of the anti-inflammatory effect. By the total leukocyte count and differential leukocyte count expressed as a percentage we appreciated the effect of the alcoholic extract on the bone marrow acute phase response. After the experiment time, compared to the control group (I) and to the diclofenac group the tested extract induced a significant decrease in the total leukocyte count ($p < 0.0001$) (table 1). Analysing the results from the differential leukocyte count expressed as percentage in the treated groups, we found that the total leukocyte count changes were induced by the decrease of the phagocytes percentages, respectively polymorphonucleares (PMN) ($p < 0.0001$) and monocytes ($p < 0.01$) (table 1).

The extract reduced the bone marrow acute phase response very significantly by decreasing both types of phagocytes, PMN and monocytes, the effect being stronger than that of the diclofenac.

In acute inflammation, phagocytes are the most important effectors cells. Phagocytosis abnormalities (deficiencies or excesses) are not beneficial, because they may activate a cycle of injury in itself, like the domino effect.

Table 1. Total leukocyte count and differential leukocyte count

Group	Leucocyte/mm ³	PMN%	M %	L%	PI %	PA%
W	4952.7 \pm 1437	55.6 \pm 8.3	7.6 \pm 6.4	37 \pm 7.2	24.4 \pm 2.6	50.8 \pm 1.4
I	13528 \pm 1077	69.5 \pm 3.8	8 \pm 1.05	22,2 \pm 2.3	49.4 \pm 5.4	120.6 \pm 9.9
D	6500 \pm 1580.6	60 \pm 3.86	6.8 \pm 3.1	31.3 \pm 3.13	20.7 \pm 3.8	28.2 \pm 10.8
H	4333.2 \pm 1190	50.8 \pm 4.5	6 \pm 1.33	43.2 \pm 3.91	27.6 \pm 2.4	18.8 \pm 1.4

W-witness, I-inflammation, D-diclofenac, H-*Hyssopi herba* extract, PMN-polymorphonucleares, M-monocytes, L-lymphocytes, PI-phagocitary index, PA-phagocitary activity

In this test PI expresses the rate of phagocyte cells activation from all circulating leukocytes and PA evaluates the level of phagocytes activity.

The extract (H) reduced PI and PA very significantly ($p < 0,0001$), so they present an important anti-inflammatory effect. Compared to the diclofenac group the efect was smaller ($p < 0,01$) (table 2, figure 1).

Fig. 1. Test of in vitro phagocytosis

Nitrite/nitrate levels in treated sample group (H) was slightly smaller (0,0253 mg/ml) than those in the inflammation control group ($p < 0.05$). Compared to the diclofenac group, the effect on the nitrite/nitrate concentration was significantly

smaller ($p < 0.0001$) (figure 2). The results emphasized that the mechanisms of anti-inflammatory action is based on the decreasing of the phagocytes activity.

Fig. 2. Effect on serum nitrites and nitrates

Lately NO has received much attention because its wide range of biological effects. Physiologically, NO serves both intracellularly, as a second messenger that responds to activation of plasma membrane receptors, and extracellularly as a paracrine factor that carries the information between cells.

Pathologically NO excess is cytotoxic. In contrast to conventional signaling ligands such as cytokines, hormones, neurotransmitters which function through specific interactions with receptors, the ultimate action of NO in biological systems is dictated by its chemistry.

Moreover, NO and the reactive nitrogen oxide species (RNOS) derived from NO can interact with a wide variety of biochemical targets to elicit diverse biological direct effects and indirect effects. Direct effects are those chemical reactions in which NO reacts directly with a biological target molecule. Indirect, effects of NO occur during patho-physiological and toxicological events [8, 9, 12].

The initial reaction of NO in an indirect effect is with molecules such as superoxide (O_2^-) or molecular oxygen (O_2) that forms intermediate RNOS *prior* to the reaction with a final target. These RNOS can alter a wide range of biological macromolecules such as proteins, lipids and DNA and are thought to play a pivotal

role in NO mediated cell death. In general, NO chemistry is governed by indirect effects only when the local concentration of NO is high ($1\mu M$) and sustained for prolonged periods of time.

These attributes characterize NO production catalyzed by the inducible isoenzyme, iNOS, suggesting that indirect effects are most likely to occur in the vicinity of activated macrophages or other cells expressing iNOS after immunostimulation and in disease states [8, 9, 11, 12].

The inhibitory effect of *Hyssopi herba* extract on NO synthesis was less important than that on phagocytosis test. That showed that the tested plant extract inhibits other effectors mechanisms of the phagocytes too, not only NO synthesis.

Conclusions

The extracts obtained from aerial part of *Hyssopus officinalis* L. shows a good anti-inflammatory effect, by decreasing the bone marrow acute phase response and the phagocytes activity. The effect is smaller than the diclofenac.

The NO synthesis was not significantly inhibited by the extract, facts which showed

that the tested plants extract have other effectors anti-inflammatory mechanisms.

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MICROWAVES – OUR ALLY IN COOKING?

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Abstract: Nowadays microwaves are present everywhere, in various fields such as TV broadcasting via satellites, communications, agricultural-forestry related industries, RADAR systems, medicine, food industry (the most known device – the microwave oven). In the last years have been discovered not only the benefits brought by the microwaves into the daily life, but the potential side effects of the microwaves on the living organisms. The aim of this paper is to discover the level of knowledge about this form of electromagnetic radiation and also to compare this information with those from specialty literature such that new education strategies can develop.

Keywords: Electromagnetic radiation, microwaves, microwave oven, health.

1. Introduction

The vast array of uses of electromagnetic waves is due to the fact that there are many ways in which EM waves can interact with a vast gamut of substances. Some of the substances contain loaded particles (electrons and protons), from which it can be deduced the fact that EM waves can affect and be affected by matter.

The oscillating electrical field can stimulate the molecular vibration of the atoms, or it can interact with the nucleus of the atoms. The effects of this interaction between substances and electromagnetic waves are dependent of the frequency of the waves (any wavelength) and the properties of the substance which is penetrated by the wave (density, molecular structure etc).

The microwave oven is one of the more common appliances that use this form of EM radiation. The microwave as we all know is made out of a magnetron, a heating chamber and a guide that makes the connection between the two elements.

The magnetron is a tubular formation in vacuum through which electromagnetic waves from the microwave spectrum are generated by an electron field moving through an electromagnetic field. The wave guide is a metallic passage which leads from the magnetron to the heating chamber. The heating chamber is a metal box, serving as a medium in which the microwaves are reflected.

The conventional ovens are heating the air surrounding the food, and it's based on conduction (in case of solid foods) and on convection (in case of liquid foods) to transfer heat to the foods. Microwaves are sent (usually with a frequency of 2450 MHz and $\lambda = 0.122\text{m}$) inside the consumables, and these will penetrate them, raising the molecular temperature [9,10].

2. Research methodology

The present study has as an objective the analysis of the study lots regarding microwave usage in general with special attention to the microwave oven, evaluation of the positive/negative impact of microwaves on biosystems, identification of information sources of the questioned subjects regarding microwaves. Two lots of study, each having 100 people, have been used.

- Lot 1 - students (first year of study) of the Faculty of Medicine, Transilvania University of Brasov (UTBv)
- Lot 2 – students (first year of study) of the Faculty Electrical Engineering and Computer Science (IESC), UTBv

The two lots had similar ages (18-30 years). The administered questionnaire had 39 open and closed ended questions.

The results are congregated in an Excel database. The data was reported through graphs and charts, highlighting the statistical significance of the

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difference between the groups answers (using the features of the SPSS program).

3. Results and Discussions

In the following paper the results of some of the questions addressed to the study lots are presented, other results (regarding the microwave generalities, for instance in the medical domain and also the effects of these waves) are sent to evaluation to another specialty paper having publishing in mind.

In case of the students of the Medicine Faculty, it has to be noticed that the lot is in general made out of females (75%) rather than being mainly composed out of males, like in the other study lot. The majority of students live in the urban area (79% of the Medicine Faculty and 80% of the Engineering Faculty).

More than three quarters of the questioned students already have a microwave oven as it can be seen from this graph.

Fig.1 Distribution of students who possess a microwave oven

Fig.2 Distribution of students in relation to their opinion regarding the reasons of using the microwave oven

It should be noted that over 90% (Medicine - 95%, Engineering - 97%) of the students keep in mind the time saved by using the microwave oven. The second option was to free more space. No student of the Medicine Faculty considers cooking by microwave a healthy method, this method being agreed upon 1% of the Engineering

students. Cooking by microwave is extremely fast because the energy is passed directly to the molecules, because it doesn't rely on heat conduction from the outside to the inside of the foods - a much slower process. High water content based foods will be heated quicker due to the dipolar interaction. Also, while the ions concentration raises, the heating speed also raises because of the microwave-ions interaction [9].

It has been analyzed the subjects repartition in relation with their opinion regarding the uses of the microwave oven.

Fig.3 Distribution of students regarding the uses of microwaves

The majority of the questioned people considered that the most frequent use of the microwave oven is heating food (96% Medicine, 98% Engineering). Second place is held by defrosting food, then preparing food, and some of the students also mentioned other uses such as making experiments, preparing coffee or popcorn.

Microwave oven manuals specify exactly what the uses of this machine are, but it also mentions contraindications. So, this oven can be used for preparing, heating and defrosting foods, it's also not recommended to use its cavity as a storage place or to introduce flammable materials (cloth, wood, weeds, paper, flowers etc) for various purposes.

Fig.4 Distribution of students answers on frequency of microwave oven use

It has been noticed (Fig. 4) that the students from the IESC Faculty use more frequently microwaves than the students from the Medicine Faculty. Hence, 48% (in contrast to 38% - Medicine students) claim they use it daily, 37% (in contrast to 26% - Medicine students) a few times per week, 4%

(in contrast to 16% - Medicine students) a few times per month and 10% (in contrast to 20% - Medicine students) do not use microwaves at all.

Fig.5 Distribution of answers depending on the duration selected to prepare the food

Following the data representing the students' selection by food preparation time it can be noted

the fact that almost a half of them (56% - Medicine students, 55% - Engineering students) choose programs lasting less than 5 minutes.

Fig.6 Distribution of students opinion regarding the destroyed bacteria from food

In the representation above (Fig. 6) most of the subjects appear to believe that most of the germs disappear in a faster rate if the food is cooked using a stove or a grill (46% - Medicine Students, 53% - Engineering students).

Specialized researches show that a variety of pathogens, such as *Escherichia coli* and staphylococci are diminished or even completely removed due to microwaves effect. [4, 5].

The negative influence on health of the microwave oven

Fig.7 Distribution of students who consider that health is affected by the microwave oven

Analysing the representation above (Fig. 7) it is noticed that most of the students (81% - Medicine students, 68% - Engineering students) believe that their health is negatively influenced by the microwave oven. External radiation emitted by microwave overlaps the microwaves emitted by other applications, such as mobile telephony, Wi-Fi equipment and others, producing thermal and nonthermal effects to the organisms (sperm apoptosis [8], eye damage [2], cranial tumors [1, 6], neurotrauma [7, 11]).

It has also been observed that most of the students not only consider the microwave oven harming, but also believe that the food prepared using them affects their health, although they do not know how it is this happening. Some students motivate their choice saying that prepared food containing radiation is carcinogenic, proteins are

denatured and food loses its quality. Specialized researches refute these allegations, whereas there are evidences that show the existence of organoleptic properties of the food prepared using microwaves similar to food cooked by other methods [4].

Moreover, the food cooked this way is also safe regarding bacteriological perspective and contain higher quantities of substances with protective roles (e.g. antioxidant) [3, 5].

A great percentage of people have been shown to not know the actual explanation of the negative side of microwave ovens and food prepared using this device, which is why the specialists (in medicine or gastronomy) should take some actions raising awareness of this subject.

The source of information on microwaves

Fig.8 The distribution of students according to their source of information on microwaves

In the representation above (Fig. 8) it is shown the fact that the internet is the most useful source of information regarding microwaves, where 82% Medicine students and 91% IESC students agree with this statement ($p > 0.5$).

It has been also observed the existence of statistically significant differences between the answers given by the two study groups regarding the use of book ($p < 0.005$) and specialized magazines ($p < 0.05$) in individual researching of this subject.

Conclusions

The studies made on the two study lots have indicated the importance of raising awareness to people regarding microwaves because:

- some aspects regarding the effects of these radiations on biosystems are insufficiently known, concluding that clear, highly scientific information should be given to people.
- the majority of subjects consider that microwaves and products processed through this method have negative impact on biosystems
- internet represents the main source of information about microwaves for both groups of study, so it's imposed that a critical analysis should be made on this informational segment of the population.

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ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS INFLUENCING THE ACTIVITY OF ACETYLCHOLINESTERASE

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Abstract: Environmental factors influence the physiological function of different organs and tissues. Changes in pH could appear as effect of acidosis or alkalosis, associated with changes of environmental factors. Organophosphate pesticides (OP) are widely used to protect plants. All kinds of food products are controlled for the presence of residues of these substances. However, these compounds have a higher toxicity for mammals. One of the prospective methods for the detection of OP pesticides is the using of different enzymatic methods using free enzyme or enzyme-based biosensors. This article describes the changes of kinetics parameters of enzymatic reaction catalyzed by acetylcholinesterase (Ellman method) in different conditions (pH, presence of ethyl-paraoxon).

Keywords: environmental factors, organophosphate pesticides, acetylcholinesterase, enzymatic reaction, kinetic parameters.

1. Introduction

In our days environmental pollution by pesticides is a very important issue [1]. Due to less stability, compared with organochlorine substances, organophosphate (OP) pesticides widely used to protect plants. However, these substances have a higher toxicity for mammals. Once they enter in the human and animal body's with different kind of food or by accidental poisoning, OP pesticides have a severe effect on the nervous system and rapid emergency care need to be done [2]. Also changes of pH values could appear.

This is why the presence of these compounds in the environment must be monitored and, if possible, to reduce the pesticide usage [3].

The mechanism of action of OP pesticides in the body is in their ability to influence activity of acetylcholinesterase (AChE), transforming it into the stable to hydrolysis, which is unable to react with molecules of acetylcholine [4]. One of the prospective methods for the detection of OP pesticides is the using of different biosensors [5].

Detection of organophosphorus pesticides by the inhibition of commercial and mutants AChE activity was used by different research groups using different procedures: biosensor based on acetylcholinesterase (AChE) and carbon nanosphere (CNS) immobilized on a glassy

carbon electrode [6], sol-gel immobilization using TCNQ as mediator [7,8].

Shamagsumova and collab. [9] developed a biosensor based on unsubstituted pillar[5]arene (P[5]A) as electron mediator.

2. Research Method

For the determination of pesticides using enzymes, the greater role is played by factors such as pH of the medium. Optimum activity of cholinesterase enzymes lies within pH 7.5 – 8.0 [10].

The aim of this work was to determine the activity of the acetylcholinesterase with using spectrophotometric analysis (Ellman method) [11], in different conditions.

As the substrate it was used acetylthiocholine (ATCh) from Sigma Aldrich Co (St. Louis, MO, USA). In this case, it is advisable to use an analogue of acetylcholine because as a result of hydrolysis is formed thiocholine, which contains a sulfhydryl group.

Thiocholine interacts with 5,5'-dithiobis[2-nitrobenzoic acid] (Ellman's reagent, Acros Organics, New Jersey, USA) with the formation of 2-nitro-5-mercaptobenzoic acid. This compound is yellow in color, and the color intensity is proportional with the product concentration (2-nitro-5-mercaptobenzoic acid) in the reaction mixture and, therefore with

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thiocholine concentration. It was used acetylcholinesterase, extracted from *Electrophorus electricus* (electric eel) (Sigma Aldrich Co, St. Louis, MO, USA).

The speed of the reaction was determined at concentration of the substrate 0.006 – of 0.133 mM, which includes the phase characteristic of AChE inhibition by the substrate.

It was studied the effect of different pH values on the enzyme acetylcholinesterase and also it was calculated the kinetic characteristics of enzymatic reactions such as Michaelis-Menten constant (K_m) and maximum reaction rate (V_{max}) i.e., the kinetic constants of the enzyme on the appropriate substrate reaction.

This reaction was performed in 0.1 M K-Na-phosphate buffer, at different pH values: pH=6,6; pH=7; and pH=7,4 respectively. The registration signal is carried out using spectral analysis at a wavelength of $\lambda=405$ nm in the continuous conditions, allowing to monitor the progress of the reaction in time.

One of the factors determining the reaction rate is the concentration of product or substrate which was used in the enzymatic reaction. At a constant concentration of enzyme, the rate of reaction gradually increases, at the beginning (linear dependence). By increasing the amount of substrate the reaction rate reaches a certain maximum. It is considered this the maximum speed of the reaction, when all molecules of the enzyme are associated with substrate (enzyme is saturated with substrate). The factor limiting the reaction rate is the concentration of the enzyme, so for our study we kept constant the enzyme concentration. In such conditions there were determined the maximum speeds (V_{max}) and the values of Michaelis-Menten constant (K_m).

We consider the slopes of the linear dependencies of optical density (extinction) versus time for each concentrations of the substrate and we represent them in order to have the kinetic behavior of the enzyme-substrate reaction. For a concentration of substrate 0.0066 mM (pH=7), the results are indicated in Fig.1

Fig. 1. The dependence of optical density versus time; [acetylthiocholine]=0.0066 mM (pH=7)

Linear relationship between velocity of reaction and concentration of enzyme, when the reaction rate is directly proportional to the amount of enzyme present, is valid only in certain conditions [12].

The value of Michaelis-Menten constant is defined as a quantitative parameter of the enzymatic reaction, since it depends on such factors as pH, temperature, substrate used, etc. that is why it is used to characterize a particular enzyme-substrate system under certain condition [12]. The quantitative relationship between substrate concentration and rate of enzymatic reaction expresses the equation of Michaelis-Menten:

$$V = V_{max} \frac{S}{(K_m + S)}, \quad (1)$$

where: - V represents the observed reaction rate at full saturation of the enzyme by the substrate;
 - V_{max} – maximum reaction rate at full saturation of the enzyme by the substrate;
 - K_m – the Michaelis-Menten constant characterizing the enzymatic system, mM;
 - S – substrate concentration, mM.

Determinations of kinetic parameters of enzymatic reactions were performed at various concentrations of substrate and constant enzyme concentration, using Lineweaver-Burk equation (the reverse of Michaelis-Menten equation).

Control sample didn't contain enzyme. Each experiment was conducted in two replications.

3. Results and Discussions

Graphs were constructed based on optical density from the time of the reaction for each concentration of acetylcholine. It was obtained the dependence similar to the type of Michaelis-

Menten behaviour. Sloping streaming chart of the data are linear relationships, proportional to the speed

of the enzymatic process. In the study of enzymatic reactions catalyzed by acetylcholinesterases at various concentrations of substrate, were obtained graphs with using different pH (figure 2 A, B, C).

A

B

C

Fig. 2. The dependence of the rate of the enzymatic reaction; [acetylthiocholine]=0-0,133 mM; A – pH=6.6; B – pH=7; C – pH=7.4

Fig. 3. The Lineweaver-Burk equations for kinetic acetylthiocholine –acetylcholinesterase, at different pH values: A – pH=6.6; B – pH=7; C – pH=7.4

The resulting works were plotted as Lineweaver–Burk dependencies (Figure 3 A, B C) and the values of Michaelis constant K_m and V_{max} in different pH values were obtained (Table 1):

Based on theoretical information, if K_m value is lower, this indicates a stronger affinity between enzyme and the substrate. When using pH=7.4 the rate of the reaction is quite fast, which may

complicate the determination of the inhibition of the enzyme OP.

Table 1. Kinetic parameters of E-S reaction, for different pH values

	K_m (mM)	V_{max}
pH=6.6	0.154	0.0099
pH=7	0.056	0.0047

pH=7.4	0.012	0.165
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Based on the obtained results it can be concluded that further determination of OP pesticides, as cholinesterase inhibitors, is advantageously carried out at pH=7.

Also was studied the influence of paraoxonethyl (E-PO) for enzymatic reaction. The concentrations of pesticides was $0,12 \cdot 10^{-6}$ M. The

time of inhibition of the reaction between pesticide and enzyme was 30 seconds. We consider the slopes of the linear dependencies of extinction versus time for each concentrations of the substrate with presence E-PO and without it. The results of the kinetic behavior of the enzyme-substrate reaction are indicated in Fig.4.

Fig. 4. The dependence of extinction versus time; at different concentrations of ATCh

The resulting works were the values of degree of inhibition and the remnant of enzymatic

activity for different concentration of ATCh. The results are represented in Fig.5 and Fig. 6.

Fig. 5. The dependence of degree of inhibition by $[E-PO] = 0,12 \cdot 10^{-6}$ M versus concentration of ATCh

Fig. 6. The dependence of remnant of enzymatic activity versus concentration of ATCh

Referring to Fig. 5 and Fig. 6, the degree of inhibition by E-PO decrease and remnant of enzymatic activity increase with a raising of ATCh concentration.

Similarly was studied the influence of E-PO with concentration $0.06 \cdot 10^{-6}$ M, for enzymatic reaction

(pH=7) using different inhibition times corresponding to the reaction between pesticide and enzyme. The concentration of ATCh was 0,05 mM. The results of the kinetic behavior of the enzyme-substrate reaction are indicated in Fig.7.

Fig. 7. The dependence of extinction versus time; at different time of inhibition of the reaction between pesticide and enzyme

The results of degree of inhibition and the remnant of enzymatic activity for different time

of inhibition of the reaction between pesticide and enzyme are represented in Fig. 8 and Fig. 9.

Fig. 8. The dependence of degree of inhibition by $[E-PO] = 0,06 \cdot 10^{-6} M$ versus time of inhibition

Fig. 9. The dependence of remnant of enzymatic activity versus time of inhibition by $[E-PO] = 0.6 \cdot 10^{-6} M$

Referring to Figures 8 and 9, the degree of inhibition by E-PO increase and remnant of enzymatic activity decrease with a raising of inhibition time corresponding to the reaction between pesticide and enzyme.

Conclusions

Besides the fact that pesticides are very toxic substances to human, they have a bad influence for foods quality. The use of cholinesterase based-biosensors for the detection of these compounds in environmental samples, including food as well as, is it a widespread. As result of this work, there were determined the kinetic parameters characterizing the enzymatic system using acetylcholinesterase from electric eel, and acetylthiocholine as the substrate. The obtained data concerning the influence of different concentrations of paraoxon-ethyl against the activity of acetylcholinesterase (considering the variation of degree of inhibition and remnant of enzymatic activity) will be used further for the

detection of organophosphorus pesticides, as cholinesterase inhibitors in order to control food safety with the use of enzymatic biosensors.

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PROCESSES RISKS EVALUATION IN ACCORDANCE WITH HACCP STANDARDS

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Abstract: *In this paper we describe a system for ensuring food safety. There are presented the identification, assessment and control of risks specific to the processes in accordance with HACCP system (Hazard Analysis Critical Control Points) based on technical quality requirements. The case study focuses on identifying the critical control points for analyzed process, monitoring and implementation of hygiene procedures at critical control point by controlling the biological risk (microorganisms).*

Keywords: *Critical Control Points (CCP), Hazard Analysis Critical Control Points (HACCP), risks assessment, food safety.*

1. Introduction

Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Point (HACCP) is a risk assessment approach that addresses physical, chemical, and biological hazards [1]. HACCP is designed so that key actions, known as Critical Control Points (CCPs) can be taken to reduce or eliminate the risk of the hazards being realized. HACCP involves focusing on where the control points in a process are. Once these are established critical limits are set. The critical limits are then monitored and the process is verified as being in control (or not) [2].

The hazard analysis of critical control point (HACCP) system combines several approaches (surveillance of diseases, foods and operations) into an action-oriented programme to identify and reduce the foodborne disease problem [3].

The HACCP system is recognized as an important tool in the reduction of foodborne diseases, and it is a global reference in terms of food safety control. It is recommended by the World Health Organization, the International Commission on Microbiological Specifications for Foods, the Codex Alimentarius and food regulatory agencies in various countries [4].

2. Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Point (HACCP) system

The hazard analysis critical control point (HACCP) concept is a systematic approach to the identification, assessment and control of hazards. The system offers a rational approach to the control of microbiological hazards in foods,

avoids the many weaknesses inherent in the inspectional approach and circumvents the shortcomings of reliance on microbiological testing. By focusing attention on the factors that directly affect the microbiological safety of a food, it eliminates wasteful use of resources on extraneous considerations, while ensuring that the desired levels of safety and quality are met and maintained [1, 3].

There are two key components of HACCP [1]:

- Hazard Analysis: Determining what microbiological, physical, or chemical risks are associated with a process.
- Critical Control Point: A point, step, or procedure at which control can be applied.

Additionally the critical control points (CCP) decision-making process may be aided by the utilization of a CCP decision tree. Application of a decision tree should be flexible and requires common sense alongside the good judgment of the HACCP team members. The HACCP team will need access to data to answer the questions accurately in the decision tree.

The tree used and the decision tree decisions should be documented. There are a variety of different decision trees in use but many organizations will opt to use the version suggested by Codex [5].

HACCP can be applied throughout the food chain from primary production to final consumption and its implementation should be guided by scientific evidence of risks to human health. In addition, the application of HACCP systems can aid inspection by regulatory authorities and promote international trade by

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increasing confidence in food safety. The application of HACCP is compatible with the implementation of quality management systems, such as the ISO 9000 series, and is the system of choice in the management of food safety within such systems [6].

3. Risk evaluation in accordance with HACCP system. Case study.

The case study consists in analyzing (qualitative and qualitative) and evaluating the potential risks specific of the cream processing with fat content of 20% by implementation of the HACCP system.

Organoleptic aspects of the cream it is assessed at temperatures of 8-12 °C, targeting the following parameters specified in table 1.

Table 1

Indices	Fermented cream
Aspect	Homogeneous mass, without impurities
Consistency	Viscous, without clumps of fat or protein substances
Colour	White to off-white uniform throughout the mass
Smell and taste	Good taste, fruity, characteristic of lactic fermentation

The microbiological characteristics are specified in the table 2.

Table 2

Characteristics	Conditions of admissibility
0.01 g coliform bacteria	absent
0.1 g Escherichia coli	absent
50 g Salmonella	absent
0.1 g Staphylococcus	absent
1 g Yeast and mildews	100

The conditions to verify the cream quality:

- In order to verify the organoleptic properties of the product the random data are collected daily, a total of two containers of cream immediately after packing.
- Visually inspect of the exterior aspect of the pack and its integrity.
- It is checked the weight of the container using an analytical balance.
- The product is periodically observing in terms of physic, chemical and microbiological analyzes complying with the Sampling under the program of self-control.

Based on a HACCP plan there are monitored throughout the technological process, from supply of raw materials and auxiliary materials, until and delivery of finished products, thus obtaining products with a high standard of food safety.

Table 3

Risk	Risks factors
Physical	Metals, plastic, paper, raffia, glass, personal objects. Non-ferrous parts drawn from the operation of machines, personal objects.
Chemical	Residues of pesticides: - herbicides; - fungicides; - insecticides. Residues of maintenance substances: - hydrocarbons; - lubricants. Heavy metals: - lead; - cadmium.
Biological	Pathogenic flora: - Clostridium perfringens; - Salmonella; - Escherichia coli; - Bacillus cereus; - Bacillus mesenteric. Commonplace flora: - coliform bacteria; - yeast; - mildews.

Fig. 1. Identification of critical control points

The application of decision tree for identification of critical control points (CCP) for analyzed processes it is shown in figure 1.

For risk identification, team work within the organization, use the cause and effect diagram. Based on historical data and the flow diagram it were anticipated the hazards that can occur during the production process. Analysis of each stage and hazard identification of each stage may result in a checklist of potential hazards, applicable at each stage of the process.

During the phase, the team must not be limited to the risk likelihood or its potential to cause disease. All significant potential risks must be considered. The most common hazards are biological hazards, chemical and physical (table 3).

4. Qualitative and quantitative risks analysis

In this phase there are performed the qualitative and quantitative risk analysis, assessing the

probability of occurrence and the impact of risk events on the objectives.

Risks assessment using the risk matrix it consists of:

- assessments of events/scenarios consequences (I);
- assessments of events/scenarios likelihood of occurrence (O);
- assessments of detection (D);
- risk score (S).

Considering the three parameters (I, O, D), the distribution of assessed critical control points is presented in figure 2. The prioritization of evaluated risks consists on analysis and implementation of corrective and preventive action. Therefore, there are identified and assessed each corrective action for each critical control point. Also, the HACCP plan highlights the critical control points and there is indicated in table 4.

Fig. 2. The critical control points evaluation

Table 4

Technological process step	Risk	Corrective measures
PCC1 - supply	The presence of antibiotics, pesticides, hormones, mycotoxins.	-sample rejection; -supply control; -supplier audit.
PCC2 - filtering	Presence of material parts.	- milk filtering ; - maintenance plan of the machines; - personal training.
PCC3 - pasteurization	Inactivation of pathogenic and alteration microorganisms.	- pasteurization; - verification of equipment and system; - verification of measuring and monitoring devices; - personal training.
PCC4 - cooling	Propagating of microorganisms.	- verification of equipment and system; - verification of measuring and monitoring devices; - personal training.
PCC5 - thermostation	Propagating of microorganisms.	- verification of equipment and system; - verification of measuring and monitoring devices; - personal training.
PCC6 - storage	Propagating of microorganisms.	- verification of equipment and system; - verification of measuring and monitoring devices; - personal training.

Conclusions

In this paper it were identified the potential risks and it were assessed the risks scores according to their consequences, occurrence and detection in accordance with HACCP standards.

The HACCP plan is a descriptive document that specifies the practices, resources, sequence of specific activities related to food safety, relevant to a particular process or product aims to ensure an efficient management for food safety.

The main identified risks which led to the identification of a critical control point, in descending order of priority scores are follows:

- The presence of antibiotics, pesticides, hormones and / or mycotoxins (chemical risk);
- Inactivation of pathogenic and alteration microorganisms (microbiological risk);
- Development of micro-organisms (microbiological risk);
- The presence of material parts (physical hazard).

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USING CHITOSAN AS A SORBENT OF ASPIRIN AND PARACETAMOL

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Abstract: Chitosan is able to sorb heavy metals, synthetic dyes, radionuclides and pesticides. Currently, chitosan is used in many spheres of human life. Being a naturally occurring polymer, chitosan is compatible with the tissues of mammals, has a high biological activity and is non-toxic. During the investigation, it was examined the ability of chitosan to interact with 2 drugs: aspirin and paracetamol. Prepared samples were analyzed with HPLC method.

Keywords: chitosan, aspirin, paracetamol, sorption, HPLC method.

1. Introduction

Chitosan is a high molecular polymer of glucosamine obtained by the reaction of deacetylation of chitin, shown in Figure 1. Deacetylation reaction is accompanied by a simultaneous rupture of the glycosidic bonds of the polymer. Therefore, chitosan is a polydisperse (by molecular weight) D-glucosamine polymer, which contains 5-15% acetamide groups, and up to 1% of groups connected to amino acids and peptides (Bykova, 2002).

Fig. 1. The reaction of deacetylation of chitin (Bykova, 2002)

Outwardly, chitosan looks like flakes of the size less than 10 mm or powder of different fineness. It may have a color from white to cream, often with a yellowish, grayish or pinkish tinge. Chitosan is odourless, non-toxic and soluble in diluted organic or inorganic acids, except sulfuric acid. Also, dry chitosan has an astringent taste (Bykova, 2002).

Chitosan is able to sorb metals. Arsenic (Chen and Chung, 2006), cadmium (Dzul Erosa et al., 2001) and platinum (Guibal et al., 1999) could be removed from aqueous solution by chitosan

sorbents. The molecule of chitosan contains a large number of amino groups, allowing it to bind hydrogen ions and acquire the excess positive charge. Moreover, free amino groups and coordinatively bonded metals are able to form chelate complexes (Nianikova et al., 2015)

It has been established (Nianikova et al., 2007) that chitosan effectively extracts iron, copper and aluminum from wine due to various chemical and electrostatic interactions, while the organoleptic properties of the drink are not affected.

Long-term radioactive contaminants are caused by long-lived radionuclides, such as Cs-137, Sr-90, Zr-93, -95, Ru-106, Ce-144, Sm-151, Eu-154, isotopes of transuranic elements (Np-237, Pu-238, -239, -240, Am-241, -243, Cm-244), and radioisotopes formed in structural materials through interaction with neutrons (Co-60, Mn-54). Most of these elements are referred to the heavy metals or transition elements. Mostly, radionuclides exert their toxicity in very low concentrations, a milligram per kilogram of soil or water. Removing such small amounts by conventional chemical methods is inefficient and expensive. In that regard, the most promising sorption method is to use selective sorbents. It was stated (Gorovoi et al., 2009) that chitosan is able to accumulate heavy metals and radionuclides in amounts which are hundreds of times greater than their contents in the environment.

Sorption properties of chitosan were tested against dyes (Nyanikova et al., 2007) About 100

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different wine products and materials have been investigated. A significantly higher activity of chitosan in relation to food synthetic dyes, than to coloring substances, which are present in the natural beverages, was revealed.

Organochlorine and organophosphorus compounds, possessing a high efficiency as a plant protections against pests (mainly insects), have high persistence and toxicity to humans. Organochlorine compounds affect the nervous, digestive, hematopoietic and cardiovascular system of humans. Organophosphorus compounds, mostly, are the basis of nerve agents. Nyanikova and others (2015) presented in their paper the investigation of sorption properties of the chitosan containing sorbent, obtained from the fungus *Rhizopus oryzae*. It was stated that examined biological preparations are able to sorb 85.7-87.0% of DDT and 71.9-75.4% of HCH.

Chitosan could efficiently react with *p*-benzoquinone (Sang et al., 2002) and remove this toxicant in aqueous solution.

Due to the high reactivity of chitosan, as well as to the eternal necessity of improving methods of detoxification of human body, the investigation of sorption properties of chitosan concerning drugs is of great significance and could be used as concomitant therapy in cases of poisoning.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Sorption of the investigated drugs

To prepare the solution of each drug, tablets were triturated in a mortar. The appropriate amount was weighed using the analytical scales and then placed in a beaker with water to the initial concentration of 1 g/L. Chitosan was taken in 5 different concentrations (0.5; 1.0; 1.5; 2.0; 2.5 g/L) and in two different types: powder and flakes. Sorption was proceeded during one hour, in stationary mode, at pH=6.5. The experiment was made in triplicate.

2.2. Determination of pH

The pH value of samples was obtained by using a universal acid-base indicator from Merck. All determinations were made in duplicate.

2.3. Determination of acetylsalicylic acid

Determination of aspirin was implemented by HPLC-method using Agilent 1200 at column Zorbax SB - C18, 150 mm x 4.6 mm x 5 μ m, temperature of column 25°C \pm 1°C, injection volume 10 μ L; mobile phase composition: orthophosphoric acid : acetonitrile : ultrapure water = 2 : 400 : 600 (v/v/v); flow 1.0 mL/min;

detection: DAD; analytical wavelength: 237 \pm 2 nm; wavelength references: 360 \pm 10 nm; response time: 1 s; spectral slot: 4 nm; pressure (aux.) 170 bar (FRX).

2.4. Determination of acetaminophen

Determination of paracetamol was implemented by HPLC-method using Agilent 1200 at column Zorbax SB - C18, 150 mm x 4.6 mm x 5 μ m, temperature of column 25°C \pm 1°C, injection volume 10 μ L; mobile phase composition: water : methanol = 3 : 1 (v/v); flow 1.5 mL/min; detection: DAD; analytical wavelength: 243 \pm 2 nm; wavelength references: 360 \pm 10 nm; response time: 1 s; spectral slot: 4 nm; pressure (aux.) 250 bar (Shah et al., 2015).

3. Results and discussion

Some of chromatograms, which have been obtained during HPLC-analysis, are shown on Figures 2 and 3.

Fig. 2. Chromatograms of some samples obtained after sorption of aspirin

Fig. 3. Chromatograms of some samples obtained after sorption of paracetamol

Concentrations of drugs after sorption were calculated according to formula 1 (Dayle et al., 1978).

$$C_i = \frac{k_i \times S_i \times M_{st}}{S_{st} \times M} \times 100\%, (1)$$

where k_i – correction factor that characterizes the sensitivity of the detector to the substance;

S_i – Sample peak area, mAU*s;

S_{st} – Standard peak area, mAU*s;

M_{st} – Control weight, mg;

M – Sample weight, mg.

The value of sample peak area (S_i) and standard peak area (S_{st}) were counted automatically by the chromatograph's software.

The average concentrations of aspirin (with standard deviations), which belong to each of investigated concentrations of chitosan, are shown in Tables 1 and 2. The results are also presented in Figures 4 and 5.

Table 1. Determined average concentrations of aspirin after sorption by powder chitosan

Concentration of chitosan, g/L	Concentration of aspirin, %	Standard deviation
0.5	60.9	5.5
1.0	58.3	2.2
1.5	56.9	2.2
2.0	54.5	2.7
2.5	46.9	1.3

Table 2. Determined average concentrations of aspirin after sorption by flake chitosan

Concentration of chitosan, g/L	Concentration of aspirin, %	Standard deviation
0.5	73.2	5.2
1.0	72.5	2.8
1.5	69.9	5.6
2.0	67.9	3.8
2.5	59.3	1.0

Fig. 4. Sorption of aspirin by powder chitosan

Fig. 5. Sorption of aspirin by flake chitosan

Referring to Figures 4 and 5, the concentration of aspirin decreases as the concentration of chitosan increases.

The average concentrations of paracetamol (with standard deviations), which belong to each of investigated concentrations of chitosan, are shown in Tables 3 and 4. The results are also presented in Figures 6 and 7.

Table 3. Determined average concentrations of paracetamol after sorption by powder chitosan

Concentration of chitosan, g/L	Concentration of paracetamol, %	Standard deviation
0.5	0.0032	0.0009
1.0	0.0037	0.0006
1.5	0.0052	0.0006
2.0	0.0035	0.0008
2.5	0.0046	0.0009

Table 4. Determined average concentrations of paracetamol after sorption by flake chitosan

Concentration of chitosan, g/L	Concentration of paracetamol, %	Standard deviation
0.5	0.0036	0.0007
1.0	0.0033	0.0005
1.5	0.0039	0.0009
2.0	0.0050	0.0008
2.5	0.0045	0.0007

As illustrated in Figures 6 and 7, the increasing of chitosan's concentration doesn't affect much the process of sorption of paracetamol because, even at the concentration of chitosan equal to 0.5 g/L, chitosan sorbs more than 99.99% of paracetamol.

Fig. 6. Sorption of paracetamol by powder chitosan

Fig. 7. Sorption of paracetamol by flake chitosan

4. Conclusion

The present investigation was devoted to study the sorption of aspirin and paracetamol by chitosan.

It was determined that chitosan sorbs more than 99.9% of paracetamol even if the concentration of chitosan is 0.5 g/L in both flake and powder. At the concentration of 2.5 g/L in flakes chitosan sorbs up to 41.5% of aspirin, in powder chitosan sorbs up to 54.0% of aspirin.

Chitosan is considered to be a good absorbent for paracetamol. Due to the presence of different functional groups, such as hydroxyl, carbonyl, methyl and amino in acetaminophen's chemical structure, the sorption process is able to proceed more efficiently in comparison with the sorption of acetylsalicylic acid, which has carboxyl, carbonyl and methyl functional groups in its chemical structure.

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PHYSICO-CHEMICAL AND RHEOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF YOGURT WITH ADDED *PLEUROTUS OSTREATUS* BIOMASS TREATED WITH ETHANOL

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Abstract: *These days the idea of using fungal extracts as useful additives have become more popular, not only because of the useful modifications of the final product, but also due to the properties of the extracts themselves. Extracts of polysaccharides, derived from fruiting bodies of Pleurotus ostreatus, show a plurality of medical activities, include antibacterial and hypoglycemic activity. In this study, ethanol extract of polysaccharides, isolated from fruiting bodies of P. ostreatus, was introduced into low-fat yogurt. During investigation pH, dry matter, water activity, titratable acidity, syneresis volume and rheological properties of yogurt samples were measured. For comparison, control samples were produced with 0,1% and 1,5% fat content. It was determined, that ethanol polysaccharide extract, incorporated into yogurt, modifies physico-chemical and rheological properties of the product.*

Keywords: *Pleurotus ostreatus, β -glucan, low-fat yogurt, rheological properties, functional food*

1. Introduction

Pleurotus ostreatus is one of the most famous medical and edible mushrooms, known as oyster mushroom; also P. ostreatus is among the most cultivated mushroom species worldwide (Upadhyay and Singh, 2011). In most of the studies, the nutritional values of mushroom have been presented as in dried fruit bodies or various extracts of fruit bodies and mycelia (Deepalakshmi and Mirunalini, 2013). Polysaccharides, obtained from P. ostreatus, have many healthy activities such as antitumor, anticholesterolic, antidiabetic, antiviral and antimicrobial activities (Patel et al., 2012).

Polysaccharides, in particular, fungal β -glucans, are considered to be responsible for the biological activity of medicinal mushrooms. β -glucans are polymers, consisting of D-glucose and connecting by β -links, which naturally occurred in the cell walls of cereals, yeast, bacteria, and fungi (Patel et al., 2012). The main source of fungal polysaccharides is fungal cell walls.

Theoretically, β -glucans might have a huge and still untapped potential for treating diabetes and

concomitant cardiovascular disease (Zhu et al., 2016).

In recent years, fungal β -glucans have attracted attention due to their potential use as therapeutic agents, namely as immunomodulators (agents with oncological and radioprotective properties), and as a means in the diabetes' treating (Zhu et al., 2016). It was revealed that glucans of high molecular weight are more effective as an anticancer and immunostimulating drugs than the low-molecular glucans (Bacic et al., 2009).

Properties of glucans can differ drastically. It depends on the structure of polysaccharides. Thus, a water-soluble (1,3;1,6)- β -glucan differs from a water-insoluble (1,3;1,4)- β -glucan in molecular structure and shows higher biological activity due to multiples branches in structure (Syed, 2009).

Although mushrooms are rich in β -glucans, consumption of their fruit bodies is often not very efficient, due to stability and poor digestibility of mushroom cell walls. Extraction and purification of β -glucans is significantly increasing their costs (Zhu et al., 2016). In addition, mushrooms contain variety of β -glucans, with different biological activities, and some of these β -glucans are water soluble, while others are soluble in

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different solvents. Often their action is synergetic and purification is leading to significant loss of biological activities (Bacic et al., 2009).

Many different cases of possible using for polysaccharides in functional foods are described (Giavasis, 2014). According to some scholars, polysaccharides, obtained from *P. ostreatus*, could be a potential immunostimulant agent for use in functional foods or medicine (Sun and Liu, 2009). It is believed that β -glucan is a valuable functional ingredient that can improve human physiological reaction (Ahmad et.al., 2012). As the preparation represents an edible substance treated with ethanol, it can be included into functional foods without any serious safety concerns (Giavasis, 2014).

Yogurt, as fermented milk product, includes healthy probiotics, is one of the most popular fermented food products worldwide (Zare et al., 2011).

Production of yogurt is developing and expanding currently; many ingredients, such as lentil flour or fungal polysaccharides are added with the purpose of improving nutritional value (Noh et al., 2013). This research investigates the influence of adding of rich with β -glucans preparation from *P. ostreatus* on the physical-chemical and rheological characteristics of yogurt.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Treatment of *P. ostreatus* fruit body biomass.

Powdered fruiting bodies of *P. ostreatus* were exposed to double extraction in a triple volume of 80% ethanol in order to increase the bioavailability of β -glucans. Due to ethanol extraction lipids and low-molecular compounds were removed, and permeability of cell walls was increased. The obtained product was separated by filtration under vacuum, dried to constant weight in an oven and grounded.

The obtained powder was kept at room temperature. Main compounds of obtained preparation were water soluble and insoluble β -glucans, chitin-glucan complex and proteins.

2.2. Yogurt preparation

Yogurt was prepared with the use of thermophile yogurt culture YO-X11

(*Lactobacillus bulgaricus* and *Streptococcus thermophilus*), made by CHR HANSEN company, and romanian commercial milk with 0.1% fat content. Four samples of yogurt were produced with different concentration of polysaccharide power: 0.5% (YP1), 1%(YP2), 1.5% (YP3) and 2% (YP4). Also two control samples were prepared: with 0.1% and 1.5% fat content (C0.1 and C1.5, respectively). All measurements were made at 1, 7 and 14 days since the beginning of the experiment.

2.3. Physical-chemical analysis

The pH value of samples was obtained by using a HANNA HI4522 pH-meter.

For the determination of dry matter content, 5 g of yogurt sample were dried in an oven at 120 ± 5 °C for 4-5 hours to constant mass. To determine the dry matter content, the difference in mass before and after the drying process was used.

The titratable acidity was determined by titration of the samples with 0.1 N NaOH solution with phenolphthalein as an indicator.

Increased syneresis in the storage period is usually associated with severe casein network rearrangements that generate whey expulsion. Tendency to produce syneresis is an important quality indicator of yogurt. Big amount of syneresis is a sign of low quality of the product. During the study, the amount of syneresis, formed on the samples during storage, was measured.

Water activity is a parameter that affects the activity of enzymes and microorganisms and indicates the availability of water contained in the substrate. Novasina Labmaster-aw was taken to determine this characteristic.

2.4. Rheological determination

Yield stress is an important rheological parameter for the product processing. The stress level required to initiate flow is usually called yield stress and is linked to the internal structure of the material, which must be destroyed before flow can appear (Tabilo-Munizaga and Barbosa-Canovas, 2005).

Behaviour of different non-Newtonian fluids is shown on figure 1. For yogurt, the curve which describes the dependence of shear stress from shear rate, corresponds to a Bingham pseudoplastic type of fluids.

Fig. 1. Fluids classification based on the shear stress-shear rate dependency.

Yield stress was determined using the Brookfield YR-1 Yield Rheometer and share stress-share rate dependency was found with HAAKE Viscotester 550.

3. Results and discussion

Value of pH

pH values of samples, obtained in this study, were summarized in table 1.

pH values of samples, obtained in this study, were summarized in table 1.

It is observed, that pH changes in similar way both in yogurt samples with added mushroom preparation, as in control samples. All samples show decrease value of pH during all time of experiment.

Dry matter content

The variations in the proportion of dry matter in the samples during the observed period are shown in figure 2

Table 1. Changes in pH caused by the addition of the extract

	1st day	7th day	14th day
C 0.1	4,45	4,31	4,2
C 1.5	4,55	4,30	4,25
YP1	4,59	4,31	4,23
YP2	4,48	4,23	4,17
YP3	4,52	4,26	4,19
YP4	4,58	4,34	4,29

Fig. 2. Variation of dry matter content

The result shown increase of dry matter in sample, which is proportional to polysaccharide extract content increase. The main change of dry matter content occurred in the second week of study.

Acidity determination

The evolution of acidity in samples during study is represented in figure 3.

Fig. 3. Evolution of acidity

Figure 3 shows an increase of yogurt acidity in all samples over time. It is observed that in yogurt samples with added extract of *P. ostreatus* polysaccharide the acidity level increase higher, than in control samples. However, yogurt, which contained a polysaccharide extract from fruiting bodies of *P. ostreatus* in the amount of 0.5%, has the lowest level of acidity.

Syneresis

The development of syneresis (%) in yogurt samples is shown in table 2.

Ethanol extract of *P. ostreatus* polysaccharide influence syneresis in yogurt. During experiment the rate of syneresis in sample increases, and growth was greater for samples, which include more extract of polysaccharide.

Table 2. Effect of *P. ostreatus* ethanol extract addition on the syneresis, %

	1st day	7th day	14th day
C 0.1	0	0	0
C 1.5	0	0	0
YP1	0	0,14	0,5
YP2	0	0,64	0,85
YP3	0,35	0,71	1,28
YP4	1,57	1,07	1,14

Water activity determination

Measured values of water activity were systemised in table 3.

As it is shown in table 3, water activity of samples does not change drastically and does not

differ from control samples of yogurt. However, adding an aqueous extract slightly reduced the activity of the product.

Table 3. Changes of water activity

	1st day	7th day	14th day
C 0.1	0,975	0,973	0,979
C 1.5	0,976	0,973	0,976
YP1	0,976	0,973	0,979
YP2	0,974	0,971	0,977
YP3	0,978	0,972	0,977
YP4	0,973	0,972	0,976

Rheological properties

Yield stress is a useful parameter, which gives information about the strength of the substances and allows the comparison with other substances.

Yogurt is a non-Newtonian material, thus its viscosity is not constant with respect to the share rate. In all of this the yield stress is the best parameter to determine the differences in rheological properties between the test and control sample of yogurt. Figure 3 shows that viscosity of samples has increased with increasing of added extract. Thus, by adding 1.5% extract a yogurt with similar consistency to that of the control sample obtained from milk with 1.5% fat content can be obtained.

Figure 4 indicates that yield stress of all samples was increasing during the study. With connection of syneresis volume increasing it may be supposed, that yogurt samples will be divided into liquid and solid ones.

Fig. 4 Yield stress value during 14 days of storage

In Figure 5, 6 and 7 can be observed that shear stress values are higher for the samples with added extract. YP3 has the higher value of shear stress followed by YP4. Samples show Bingham pseudoplastic behaviour.

The shear stress fluctuations in figure 6 could

indicate that the yogurt sample develops an inhomogeneous structure after 7 days of storage. It is seen more clearly on the curves of data from 14 days of the experiment (Fig. 7), where the same behaviour is observed to control sample of yogurt with 1,5 fat content.

Fig. 5 Shear Stress of yogurts in 1st day of storage

Fig. 6 Shear Stress of yogurts in 7th day of storage

Fig. 7 Shear Stress of yogurts in 14th day of storage

Yogurt is a shear thinning material, because an increase in relative flow velocity cause a reduction in viscosity, by stirring. The variation in the apparent viscosity data (Fig.8,9,10) confirmed that all yogurts exhibited characteristic shear thinning behaviour. The shear thinning behaviour for the yogurt became more pronounced with increasing storage period. The

apparent viscosity values of all the samples studied increased during the storage period. In the 1st day of storage, all samples show shear thinning behaviour, because viscosity decrease depending on the shear rate (Fig. 8) In 7th day start viscosity value become larger (Fig. 9). The values of the start viscosity for the 14th day (Fig. 10) are less different between the samples

Fig. 8 Apparent viscosity of yogurts in 1st day of storage

Fig. 9 Apparent viscosity of yogurts in 7th day of storage

Fig. 10 Apparent viscosity of yogurts in 14th day of storage

Increasing the values of viscosity has also been observed in concentrated yogurt (Sahan et. al., 2008; Abu-Jdayil et.al., 2002), non-fat plain (Isleten et.al., 2006), and Corni fructus extract supplemented yogurt. The increase in viscosity values of non-fat plain yogurt during 15-day storage may be associated with the rearrangement of protein molecules (Sahan et al.2008).

Conclusion

The present study was designed to develop a low-fat yogurt with improved functional properties and to evaluate the effects of adding *P. ostreatus* polysaccharide-rich preparation, on the physicochemical and rheological properties of the final products during storage.

In the result, *P. ostreatus* preparation, added in yogurt, changes properties of final product. It was found, that test samples show an increase in the dry matter content of 1% yogurt, and also don't present a decrease in viscosity level like the control sample containing low levels of fat in second week of experiment.

Rising yogurt acidity indicates an increase of acid secretion of yogurt microflora, which indirectly indicates the increased growth of lactic acid bacteria cultures. The appearance of syneresis could be interpreted a result of water removal from the yogurt polymeric network and of the size reduction of the cavities in the gel structure (Jaros and Rohm, 2008). Also, the increase of viscosity during the experiment could be explained by protein rearrangement and by hydrophobicity of the hydrogen-bonded regions of β -glucan (Sahan et. al., 2008).

The results have shown, that *P. ostreatus* preparation could serve as a thickening agent for

yogurt. The best concentration of *P. ostreatus* polysaccharide containing preparation, which could be added to produce low-fat yogurt, is located in range of 1,5-2%. In this way we provide a new food that can have health benefits.

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EVALUATION OF ALLICIN STABILITY IN LYOPHILIZED AQUEOUS GARLIC EXTRACT FOR NEW PHARMACEUTICAL SOLID FORMULATIONS WITH BIOAVAILABLE ALLICIN

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Abstract: Allicin, a highly unstable organosulfur compound, is thought to play the major role for garlic's therapeutic properties. It is formed after fresh garlic is crushed so it does not exist in garlic. Allicin content from lyophilized garlic extracts stored at different temperatures was analyzed using a HPLC system. The extract stored at -20 °C was the most stable, although it lost 15% of the initial alliin content in a period of 31 days. Lyophilization conditions also influenced alliin content in the final extracts.

Keywords: alliin, garlic, lyophilization, freeze-drying.

1. Introduction

Commonplace garlic, *Allium sativum*, has been used for over 5000 years both as a remedy and also as a condiment [2]. Part of *Liliaceae* family, garlic has been recognized as an antioxidant agent [10, 15]. Some research and clinical trials have also reported garlic as potentially effective for treating and/or preventing various disorders, including some types of cancer, infections and cardiovascular diseases [3, 5, 7, 8, 10, 11, 17, 19]. Alliin, a highly unstable organosulfur compound, is thought to play the major role for garlic's benefic actions on human body. It is a thiosulfinate formed in the presence of water after fresh garlic is crushed or chopped so it does not exist in raw garlic or dried garlic powder. When alliinase enzyme (S-alkylcysteine

sulfoxide lyase) stored in vacuoles of clove cells is released upon cell lysis, it converts the sulfoxide alliin (S-allyl-L-cysteine sulfoxide) into alliin (diallyl thiosulfinate) via formation of sulfenic acids (Fig. 1). The reaction rate is very high and thiosulfates are formed within seconds, resulting the specific odor of garlic. [8]. After alliin is formed, it begins to degrade quickly in the presence of air and water (half-life in crushed garlic at 23°C is 2.5 days) [8]. The main products of alliin degradation are fat-soluble organosulfur compounds like diallyl disulfide (DADS), diallyl sulfide (DAS) and diallyl trisulfide (DATS), also responsible for garlic's specific odor and for some of the therapeutic attributes of the plant [8].

Fig. 1 Alliin formation in garlic bulb by alliinase-catalyzed transformation of alliin [10]

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Due to allicin therapeutic properties, it's important to focus on its presence when formulating garlic-based supplements.

This is hard to achieve though because allicin is a highly reactive volatile compound. Its melting point is at 25 °C [9] and it begins to decompose rapidly at 37 °C in aqueous extracts [6]. In its high purity form ($\geq 98\%$) it's stored at -80 °C [9]. Therefore, its presence as a stable active ingredient in garlic-based supplements is a challenge.

There are many garlic supplements on the market, mostly based on dried garlic powder and hydroalcoholic extracts. If allicin has shown somewhat stability in certain aqueous and hydroalcoholic extracts [6, 12], dried garlic powder does not even have allicin in the first place. In fact allicin content of garlic can actually be described as "allicin yield" or "allicin potential" [8] since, as mentioned in the beginning of this article, formation of allicin is conditioned by certain parameters.

Moreover, it has been demonstrated that allicin cannot form after ingestion of dried garlic powder because of alliinase inactivation by acidic pH in the stomach [8].

There are also some products like Allisure, Allimax, Alliforce, Allitru, Alli-C that claim to contain stabilized allicin in liquid and dried extracts.

Therefore, this study aimed to evaluate the stability of allicin in a lyophilized aqueous garlic extract, to be used as part of a pharmaceutical solid formulation with allicin as active compound.

2. Materials and Methods

Garlic bulbs from S.C. Aroma Plant S.R.L.'s own crop and harvested in 2015 were used.

A Hitachi Elite LaChrom HPLC system equipped with a L-2130 pump, temperature controlled L-2200 Autosampler, L-2300 Column oven and a DAD UV-Vis L-2455 detector was used for allicin quantification. The separation was done on a LiChrospher® 100 RP-18 (5 μm) LiChroCART® 250-4 column. Mobile phase was degassed using an Elmasonic P 180 H ultrasonic bath.

The freeze-drying process was achieved using a ScanVac CoolSafe 55-4 freeze dryer.

HPLC grade methanol from Merck was used. Formic acid 99.8% was purchased from VWR, purchased from Fluka and the water was filtered

with a water purification system MilliQ Direct 8 from Millipore.

The garlic bulbs were industrial processed at Hofigal Export Import S.A.

They were chopped in big pieces with a plant cutting machine and dried at 40 °C with a constant air flow, according to optimal drying conditions to obtain high allicin potential dried bulbs [1, 16].

The dried bulbs were grinded into powder and mixed with water at room temperature in an ultrasonic bath at ratios of 1:5 and 1:10, filtered, then lyophilized at -50 °C for 2 days (1:5) and for 6 days (1:10). The resulted lyophilized extracts were then analyzed and stored at 24 ± 2 °C (room temperature), 3 °C (refrigerated) and -20 °C (freezer) in plastic flasks.

The dried bulbs, the aqueous extract after filtration and the resulted lyophilized extracts were analyzed using the HPLC assay described in European Pharmacopoeia [4]. The freeze-dried extracts were analyzed after 31, 60, 74 and 90 days to evaluate allicin stability.

Due to allicin reactivity it's unpractical to use allicin standard, therefore internal standard method is preferable.

BHB was used as internal standard and methanol-formic acid 1% 60:40 (v/v) as an isocratic mobile phase flowing at 0.8 ml/min. Detection wavelength was set at 254 nm and the injection volume was 10 μl .

3. Results and discussions

The HPLC assay used gave satisfactory chromatographic separation with the available column (Fig. 2, Fig. 3). Allicin spectrum is shown in fig. 4.

Fig. 2 HPLC chromatogram of dried garlic bulbs.

Fig. 3 HPLC chromatograms of the extracts after 90 days of storage at (from bottom to top) -20, 3 and 23 °C.

Fig. 4 Allicin spectrum.

The dried bulbs yielded around 0.3% allicin and the aqueous extracts analyzed after filtration have lost some of their allicin content, depending on the time taken for filtration.

Allicin yield from dried garlic was calculated according to the formula which describes allicin percentage resulted by following European Pharmacopoeia method of sample preparation [4]:

$$A = \frac{S_1 m_2 22.75}{S_2 m_1} \cdot [\%] \quad (1)$$

S_1 , S_2 are allicin and BHB areas in the chromatogram, m_2 is the amount of BHB in 100 ml solution and m_1 is the weigh of the sample.

The filtered aqueous extracts were analyzed by modifying equation (1) into a form that can be

used to calculate allicin amount from liquid extracts, using 10 ml of sample to be analyzed:

$$A = \frac{S_1 m_2 1.137}{S_2} \cdot [\%] \quad (2)$$

The resulted freeze-dried extracts were not analyzed using the sample preparation method from European Pharmacopoeia, since allicin was already formed in the extracts prior to freeze-drying process.

Instead, a quantity of each extract were dissolved in 19 ml of mobile phase and 1 ml of BHB, ultrasounded and filtered through 0.22 μ m prior to injection (10 μ l). Allicin amount was calculated as follows:

$$A = \frac{S_1 m_2 8.65}{S_2 m_1} \cdot [\%] \quad (3)$$

Extract ratio of 1:5 resulted in a 0.27% allicin extract and extract ratio of 1:10 resulted in a 0.135% allicin extract.

These results indicate that lyophilization time had a strong impact on allicin content in the final extracts, probably due to increased allicin volatility under strong vacuum conditions. (Fig. 5). This indicates that the plant-solvent ratio needs to be as higher as possible to minimize lyophilization time and, by so doing, allicin evaporation.

Fig. 5. Influence of freeze-drying time on allicin content of the final extract.

It is probably also needed to use a lower lyophilization temperature in order to decrease allicin volatility. Even after 2 days of freeze-drying process allicin content in the extract was about the amount of allicin in the dried garlic used in the research. Only the extract with higher allicin content was used for thermostability tests.

As other studies have shown, allicin stability is a function of various parameters, including temperature [6, 10, 14].

Therefore the lyophilized extract stored at -20 °C was the most stable and lost 15% of the initial quantity in a period of 31 days. The extract stored at 4 °C lost 26% of allicin content in about same period of time and the extract stored at room temperature lost about 63%. After analyzing the extracts at 60, 74 and 90 days, it was found that the loss rate was higher in the first 31 days of storage and then decreased at a somewhat constant rate.

After 90 days of storage the extract stored at -20 °C lost about 23% of allicin content, the extract stored at 4 °C lost about 45% and the extract stored at room temperature lost about 83%. We extrapolated allicin loss at 30, 40, 60 and 80 °C just to complete the graph on allicin loss according to temperature.

As seen in fig. 6, after 90 days of storage at high temperatures the extracts would lose all allicin content. Although there was few data from this study to estimate long half-life of allicin in the extract stored at -20 °C and the change in loss rate after 31 days would have also influenced the calculations, a relative half-life of allicin was estimated from the exponential decay curves shown in fig. 7. This was done to illustrate the half-life of allicin as a function of temperature as seen in the Arrhenius plot (Fig. 8). The equation for the exponential decay curve was used:

$$N = N_0 e^{-kt} \quad (4)$$

Fig. 6 Allicin loss of the extracts after 90 days of storage at different temperatures

Fig. 7 Exponential decay curves of allicin in the extracts stored for 90 days at different temperatures

Fig. 8 Arrhenius plot showing the exponential decrease in allicin half-life as a function of temperature

N , N_0 are the allicin amounts at a specific time (t) and at the initial time, respectively. The k value is the rate constant for allicin decay and was obtained from the exponential decay curves for each extract (Fig. 7).

Table 1. Allicin half-life

Temperature	$t_{1/2}$ (days)
23	31
3	100
-20	231

Alliin half-life ($t_{1/2}$) was calculated by rearranging equation (4), knowing that at the moment of $t_{1/2}$ the N/N_0 ratio is 0.5:

$$\frac{N}{N_0} = e^{-kt_{1/2}} \quad (5)$$

After taking the logarithm of equation (5), the following equation is obtained:

$$\ln\left(\frac{N}{N_0}\right) = -kt_{1/2} \quad (6)$$

which gives:

$$t_{1/2} = \frac{-0.693}{-k} \quad (7)$$

The estimated half-life values are presented in Table 1 and in fig. 8 on Y axis with a logarithmic scale. It is important to mention that the temperatures used in the research were not achieved by using laboratory equipment but using a fridge and the fluctuating temperature of the laboratory.

Also, the fact that the rate constant (k) decreased after 31 of storage, probably indicates a higher alliin half-life of the extracts stored at -20 and 3 °C than the results obtained from the exponential decay curve.

Conclusions

The present study confirms literature data about alliin thermostability and also shows that alliin was relative stable in lyophilized garlic extracts stored at a very low temperature (-20° C), having a relative half-life more than 231 days. Also, for a high alliin content in the lyophilized extracts it is necessary to minimize the freeze-drying time as much as possible and use high quality and adequately dried garlic bulbs with high alliin potential.

Given the fact that the extracts analyzed in the present study were stored in half filled plastic flasks, it is possible that by minimizing the air contact with the extracts, e.g., storing them in capsules, would increase alliin stability.

The results give room for further research to stabilize alliin in lyophilized garlic extracts and provide data for formulating new garlic-based supplements with bioavailable alliin.

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INHIBITORY EFFECT OF *CINNAMOMUM CASSIA* ESSENTIAL OIL AND HIS COMPONENTS ON DIFFERENT MICROORGANISMS

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Abstract: *The antibacterial and antifungal potentials of cinnamon essential oil and two of his compounds (cinnamaldehyde and eugenol) were investigated in this study. For the antibacterial study were used two strains of bacteria Escherichia coli and Proteus mirabilis and for the antifungal study a yeast strain Saccharomyces cerevisiae. The disk diffusion assay showed that Cinnamomum cassia oil and his major compound, cinnamaldehyde, have an important antibacterial and antifungal effect. We observed that this two have a major inhibitory effect against E. coli and S. cerevisiae while against P. mirabilis the inhibitory effect is less important. The eugenol has a low inhibitory effect against all three microorganisms. In conclusion C. cassia oil has an effectively inhibition effect over E. coli and S. cerevisiae.*

Keywords: *Cinnamomum cassia essential oil, Cinnamaldehyde, Eugenol, Inhibition, Disk diffusion assay, Bacterial growth curves;*

1. Introduction

Cinnamon is a spice used for thousands of years and nowadays is one of the most used.

In Europe cinnamon has appeared during the 16th and 17th centuries when the Portuguese found cinnamon in Sri Lanka.

The genus Cinnamomum (family Lauraceae) comprises over 300 aromatic evergreen trees and shrubs, located in almost all tropical regions of Earth.

The most used species are Cinnamomum zeylanicum Blume (Cinnamomum verum J. Presl, Sri Lanka cinnamon or Ceylon cinnamon) and Cinnamomum aromaticum Nees (Cinnamomum cassia (L.) J. Presl, Chinese cinnamon or false cinnamon) due their multiple uses worldwide.

Cinnamon volatile oils are obtained from bark, leaves, flowers and buds.

The oil is a sweet yellowish liquid with a strong cinnamaldehyde taste. With time darkens to brown-red.

The chemical composition of cinnamon oil varies depending on the part of the plant used for distillations process.

The main constituent of cinnamon bark oil is cinnamaldehyde, whereas eugenol is the main constituent of cinnamon leaf oil.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Chemicals

Cinnamon essential oil (Cinnamomum cassia) was purchased from MLW FRAGRANCE (Bonneuil sur Marne, France). Cinnamaldehyde, Eugenol were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA). All solutions were prepared in absolute ethanol. Working solutions were obtained from stock solution by serial dilutions. All the culture media components were purchased from either Biokar diagnostics (Allone, France) or Carlo Erba Reagents (Val de Reuil, France).

Other chemicals used in this study were analytical grade and obtained either from Carlo Erba Reagents or Sigma-Aldrich.

2.2. Bacterial and yeast strains and growth conditions

Two strains of bacteria were used in this study: Escherichia coli ATCC 25922 and Proteus mirabilis WT19 (corresponding to the clinical isolate U6450). These bacteria were grown in LB broth (Tryptone 10g/L, NaCl 10g/L, Yeast extract 5g/L, pH7) or LB agar plate (15g/L) at 37°C.

The yeast Saccharomyces cerevisiae strain used in this study was W303.1B and was cultivated on YPD medium (Tryptone 20g/L, Yeast extract

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10g/L, pH7, Glucose 20g/L) or YPD agar plate (15g/L).

2.3. Bacterial growth curves

Growth curves were performed in 96 well plates. A 7-hours pre-culture was diluted to an OD_{600nm}, l=1cm = 0.02 in LB ((2,22±0,16)×10⁶ CFU/mL for *E. coli* and (4,5±0,73)×10⁶ CFU/mL for *P. mirabilis*). 125µL of cell suspensions were inoculated in wells containing 125µL of cinnamon essential oil or cinnamaldehyde with a final concentration ranging from 81.7 to 413.6 µg/mL or 78,8-399,9 µg/mL. The plates were incubated in a Polarstar Omega microplate reader (BMG Labtech, Ortenberg, Germany) at 37°C. OD_{600nm}, l=1mm values were recorded every 15 minutes. Three replicates were performed for each concentration.

2.4. Disc diffusion assay

E. coli and *P. mirabilis* were cultivated in LB for 16 hours at 37°C and *S. cerevisiae* in YPD at 30°C. Cultures were adjusted to an OD_{600nm}, l=1cm = 0.001 ((1,11±0,08)×10⁵ CFU/mL for *E. coli*, (2,25±0,36)×10⁵ CFU/mL for *P. mirabilis* and (8,70±0,08)×10⁷ CFU/mL for *S. cerevisiae*) with sterile tryptone-salt Broth (Tryptone 1g/L, NaCl 8.5g/L, pH 7). 100 µL of the bacterial and yeast suspensions were spread on LB agar or YPD agar. Filter paper discs (Whatman n°3, 7 mm in diameter) were incubated on the agar surface and soaked with 5 µL of each dilution tested of Cinnamon cassia

oil, cinnamaldehyde or eugenol (0,5%, 1%; 2%, 4%, 8%, 10%, 12%, 16%, 20%, 25% which corresponds to 0,025; 0,05; 0,1; 0,2; 0,4; 0,5; 0,6; 0,8; 1; 1,25 µL of tested compounds). After 30min at room temperature, the plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours and respectively at 30°C for 48 hours for yeasts.

The diameters of the inhibition zones were measured in centimeters. Values are described as mean ± SD as assays were performed in triplicates.

3. Results and Discussions

3.1. Disc diffusion assay for antibacterial and antifungal activity of *C. cassia* oil

The antibacterial and antifungal activities (diameter of inhibition zone) of *C. cassia* oil, cinnamaldehyde and eugenol to *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922, *Proteus mirabilis* WT19 and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* W303.1B are summarized in Table 1, 2 and 3.

The inhibitory effect strengthened significantly with increasing amount of tested compound per disc. Discs with 5 µL of 25% (v/v) *C. cassia* oil and cinnamaldehyde solution resulted in highest inhibition zones around 3-4 cm. Among tested bacteria, *E. coli* and *S. cerevisiae* are most sensitive to *C. cassia* oil and cinnamaldehyde.

Table 1 Inhibitory zone of different concentration of *C. cassia* oil against microorganisms (cm)

Cinnamon oil	Concentration (% V/V)										
	0	0,5	1	2	4	8	10	12	16	20	25
<i>E. coli</i>	1,10 ±0,08	1,31 ±0,14	1,41 ±0,14	1,47 ±0,03	1,51 ±0,11	2,11 ±0,07	2,43 ±0,09	2,68 ±0,35	2,93 ±0,31	3,23 ±0,07	3,86 ±0,20
<i>P. mirabilis</i>	0	0	0	0	0,75 ±0,05	1,41 ±0,27	1,75 ±0,21	2,2 ±0,17	2,6 ±0,31	2,78 ±0,36	3,31 ±0,24
<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	1,08 ±0,12	1,21 ±0,08	1,22 ±0,10	1,23 ±0,03	1,4 ±0,32	2,34 ±0,18	2,58 ±0,10	2,64 ±0,14	3,08 ±0,17	3,43 ±0,20	4,16 ±0,15

Table 2. Inhibitory zone of different concentration of Cinnamaldehyde against microorganisms (cm)

Cinnamaldehyde	Concentration (% V/V)										
	0	0,5	1	2	4	8	10	12	16	20	25
<i>E. coli</i>	1,10 ±0,09	1,23 ±0,02	1,31 ±0,05	1,35 ±0,12	1,43 ±0,12	2,11 ±0,16	2,36 ±0,15	2,56 ±0,15	2,87 ±0,26	3,5 ±0,21	4,07 ±0,09
<i>P. mirabilis</i>	0	0	0	0	0,93 ±0,11	1,6 ±0,34	1,75 ±0,23	2,43 ±0,20	2,83 ±0,23	3,08 ±0,10	3,4 ±0,13
<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	1,08 ±0,08	1,125 ±0,02	1,17 ±0,03	1,25 ±0,05	1,33 ±0,13	2,1 ±0,16	2,56 ±0,31	2,95 ±0,07	3,53 ±0,15	3,85 ±0,07	4,05 ±0,07

Table 3. Inhibitory zone of different concentration of Eugenol against microorganisms (cm)

Eugenol	Concentration (% V/V)										
	0	0,5	1	2	4	8	10	12	16	20	25
<i>E. coli</i>	1,08 ±0,08	1,13 ±0,02	1,21 ±0,06	1,25 ±0,15	1,43 ±0,09	1,46 ±0,11	1,49 ±0,02	1,5 ±0,1	1,78 ±0,16	2,2 ±0,2	2,4 ±0,11
<i>P. mirabilis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1,48 ±0,10	1,5 ±0,1	1,6 ±0,08	1,79 ±0,18
<i>S. cerevisiae</i>	0,98 ±0,08	1,1 ±0,05	1,18 ±0,10	1,18 ±0,02	1,18 ±0,08	1,2 ±0,17	1,21 ±0,19	1,4 ±0,08	1,63 ±0,20	1,8 ±0,2	2,13 ±0,11

Antibacterial activity of *Cinnamomum cassia* oil and compounds against *Escherichia coli* by disc diffusion method.

Fig. 1. Antibacterial activity of *Cinnamomum cassia* oil and compounds against *Escherichia coli* by disc diffusion method

Antibacterial activity of *Cinnamomum cassia* oil and compounds against *Proteus mirabilis* by disc diffusion method.

Fig. 2. Antibacterial activity of *Cinnamomum cassia* oil and compounds against *Proteus mirabilis* by disc diffusion method

Antibacterial activity of *Cinnamomum cassia* oil and compounds against *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* by disc diffusion method.

Fig. 3. Antibacterial activity of *Cinnamomum cassia* oil and compounds against *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* by disc diffusion method

Table 4. Antibacterial activity of *C. cassia* oil, cinnamaldehyde and eugenol against microorganisms by disc diffusion method. Representative disc diffusion image. Antimicrobial activity was determined by forming a clear zone around the disc

3.2. Bacterial growth curves

We observe that the lowest concentration of *C. cassia* oil and cinnamaldehyde, 0.0079% (v/v), increased the lag phase of all tested bacteria. At the concentration of 0.016% (v/v), *C. cassia* oil delayed the log phase of *E. coli* for about 8 h. *C.*

cassia oil at the concentration of 0.02% (v/v) or above completely inhibited the growth of *E. coli*, while for *P. mirabilis* is 0,016(v/v) or above. The cinnamaldehyde completely inhibited the growth of *E. coli* and *P. mirabilis* from a concentration of 0,025% (v/v).

Fig. 4. Growth curves of *E. coli* in LB broth containing different concentrations of *C. cassia* oil
Proteus mirabilis growth curve in presence of
different concentrations of *Cinnamomum cassia* oil (V/V)

Fig. 5. Growth curves of *P. mirabilis* in LB broth containing different concentrations of *C. cassia* oil

E. coli growth curve in presence of
different concentrations of Cinnamaldehyde (V/V)

Fig. 6. Growth curves of *E. coli* in LB broth containing different concentrations of cinnamaldehyde

Proteus mirabilis growth curve in presence of
different concentrations of Cinnamaldehyde (V/V)

Fig. 7. Growth curves of *P. mirabilis* in LB broth containing different concentrations of cinnamaldehyde

Conclusions

The disk diffusion assay showed that Cinnamomum cassia oil and his major compound, cinnamaldehyde, have an important

antibacterial and antifungal effect. We observed that this two have a major inhibitory effect against *E. coli* and *S. cerevisiae* while against *P. mirabilis* the inhibitory effect is less important. The eugenol has a low inhibitory effect against

all three microorganisms. From the growth curves we observe that C. cassia oil and cinnamaldehyde have an inhibitory effect using very low concentrations but is the cinnamon oil that has the most important antibacterial effect. The results suggest that C. cassia oil and cinnamaldehyde can be used as natural antimicrobial agents in food industry.

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PHYSICO-CHEMICAL AND RHEOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF YOGHURT WITH DRY MATTER CONTENT INCREASED BY ADDING DIFFERENT POWDERS

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Abstract: Increase of dry matter content, made by introducing different powders, has an influence on the properties of produced yogurt. In this study was examined the effect of adding powdered whole-milk, flour rice and starch on characteristics of natural yogurt. Titratable acidity, dry matter, water activity and viscosity were measured in yogurts at 7, 14 and 21 days of storage at refrigerated temperature. Addition of powdered whole-milk resulted in increase of viscosity, dry matter and acidity comparing with other two samples. Yogurt with added starch has the highest water activity value. During 3 weeks of storage yogurt processed with whole-milk powder presents the best physico-chemical characteristics.

Keywords: yogurt, powdered whole-milk, flour rice, starch, dry matter, viscosity.

1. Introduction

Yogurt is one of the most popular fermented dairy product consumed all over the world (Verman and Sutherland, 2004; Peng et al., 2009; Karam et al., 2013; Puvanenthiran et al. 2014). Yoghurt is a product from milk through the lactic acid fermentation by addition of a starter culture: *Streptococcus thermophilus* and *Lactobacillus delbrueckii* ssp. *Bulgaricus* (Mckinley, 2005). Tamime (2002) presents in his paper that in some countries less traditional microorganisms, such as *Lactobacillus helveticus* and *Lactobacillus delbrueckii* ssp. *lactis*, are sometimes mixed with the starter culture.

There are three major types of yogurt: drinking set and stirred yogurt.

It is known that yogurt is an excellent source of protein, calcium, phosphorus, vitamins (B2, B1 and B12), magnesium and zinc (Karam et al., 2013). Research conducted worldwide have shown that regular consumption of dairy fermented products can cause an overall improvement in the health of the consumer, both because of their chemical and, mainly, because the microflora "transported" in the digestive tract (Costin, 2007; Mckinley, 2005). Are mentioned effects such as increasing the immune response, balancing the colon microbiota, reducing the activity of enzymes involved in irritation of the colon, stopping diarrhoea, lowering cholesterol, etc. (Costin, 1999).

Viscosity, for yoghurt, plays an important role in the product acceptance by the consumers. It is

therefore important to determine how yogurt can be improved in terms of rheology to be according to the sensory requirements. In order to improve the rheological properties of yoghurt are used methods to increase the dry substance.

Starch has a wide range of applications in the food industries, being a main component of some foods (Nemtanu, 2008; Singh et al., 2006; Yousif et al., 2012; Tufeanu et al., 2015).

This carbohydrate has remarkable physicochemical properties due to his polymeric components: amylose and amylopectin (Wang, 2012).

Rice flour is obtained by milling whole rice and is a good source of energy due to its amounts of starch and fibre. It has a low content of saturated fat, cholesterol, and sodium and is used as thickening agent in food products. Also rice flour is a very good source of vitamins and minerals (Souza Montes et al., 2015).

The addition of milk powder for yogurt preparation is considered a standard process (Karam et al., 2013). Addition rates of milk powder varies, but was proved that the addition of 2% Skim milk powder is the most appropriate concentration for obtaining a yogurt with texture improved (Tamime and Robinson, 2007).

In the present study was examined the effect of adding powdered whole-milk, flour rice and starch on characteristics of natural yogurt. Physico-chemical characteristics and viscosity were measured in yogurts at 7, 14 and 21 days of storage at refrigerated temperature.

2. Material and Methods

The materials used for the yogurt production were purchased from Romanian commercial system. Four samples of yogurt were produced: Y- plain yogurt; Ymp- yogurt with powdered whole-milk; Yrf- yogurt with rice flour; Ys- yogurt with maize starch. These samples were analysed at 7th day, 14th day and 21st day.

Determination of dry matter content

For this determination was used Moisture analyser AND ML-50. Principle of the method for the determination of total dry matter % consist in the evaporation of water in thermo balance with halogen lamp at 120 ° C. Moisture analyser is built using a Super Hybrid Sensor (SHS) adopted in an analytical balance. Therefore, the result is more accurate.

Determination of acidity

The acidity is determined by titration with NaOH alkaline solution to neutralize the sample of the yogurt in the presence of phenolphthalein as an indicator.

There will be made two determinations for each product and the difference between parallel samples should not exceed 1°T.

Determination of water activity

The link between the water from food and activity of enzymes, microorganisms is highlighted by water activity. Water activity was determined using Novasina Labmaster aw.

Rheological determination

In order to characterize the viscosity of the yoghurt was used the rheometer Brookfield YR-1 Yield Rheometer, an available instrument which uses the vane spindles to determine the yield of the viscoelastic material.

3. Results and Discussions

Dry matter content determination

The results obtained after determining the dry matter content of the yogurt at thermo balance are shown in Figure 1.

In figure 1. is observed that the yogurt with added powdered whole-milk has the highest dry matter content, because this evolves by fermentation processes.

For the analysis the whey was removed from the surface.

The highest amount of whey has been recorded by the plain yogurt (1.6 ml whey at 14 days). Constant syneresis was observed at the yogurt with added powdered whole-milk (at every 7 days approximately 0.5 ml whey). The lowest syneresis was recorded in the case of yogurt with added starch (0.2 ml whey after 14 days).

Fig. 1. Dry matter content

Acidity determination

The evolution of acidity for the yoghurt without powder (Y) and for yogurt assortments with milk powder (Ymp), rice

flour (Yrf) and starch (Ys), was monitored for 21 days. Results are shown in figure 2.

Fig. 2. Acidity evolution

It is observed that acidity increases considerably in all types of yogurt, noting that yogurt with added milk powder has acidity higher, because the powder comes with a higher intake of lactose which is fermented by lactic acid bacteria. Instead, the yogurt with added starch shows a slower growth of acidity.

Water activity determination

The results for water activity are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Activity water evolution

	7 th day	14 th day	21st day
Y	0,990	0,990	0,990
Ymp	0,992	0,992	0,992
Yrf	0,995	0,994	0,994
Ys	0,996	0,996	0,997

The result show that a_w is approximately constant for all types of yogurt. The highest value is observed in yogurt with added starch followed by the yogurt with rice flour, the yogurt with powdered whole-milk and plain yogurt.

Rheological determination

The results concerning the viscosity of different yoghurts are shown in Figure 3.

It is observed that the highest viscosity is presented by the yogurt with powdered whole-milk, followed by the yogurt with rice flour and with starch. The plain yogurt has the lowest viscosity because the dry matter content wasn't improved by powders.

From the figure can be observed that the viscosity decreases during storage due to the syneresis process (the separated whey is not removed).

Fig. 3. Viscosity evolution

Conclusions

According to the results obtained, it could be concluded that an increase of dry matter content leads to the increase of yogurt viscosity. The smallest viscosity is presented by the yogurt produced with starch, then by the yogurt with rice flour and the highest viscosity has the yogurt with powdered whole-milk.

The improvement of rheological and physico-chemical characteristics can be achieved by adding one of these three powders used in this study: powdered whole-milk, flour rice and starch.

During storage period, yogurt processed with whole-milk powder presents the best physico-chemical characteristics, followed closely by the other two assortments of yogurt.

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STUDIES ON SELECTION OF REPELLENTS COMPOUNDS FROM PLANTS FOR TEXTILE DEVELOPMENT, WITH THE ROLE OF PREVENTING THE SPREAD OF INFECTIOUS DISEASES DUE TO TICKS

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O.IORDACHE²

Abstract: *The necessity of creation of textile fabrics with repellent properties is determined by the presence of a increasingly number of tick that lead to diseases difficult to treat. Textile fabrics with repellent properties can be used as barriers to eliminate or reduce risk of infection caused by ticks especially in forest, agriculture and tourism areas. The main objective is developing new multifunctional textile structures, including in nanostructures biologically active compounds extracted from plants, with the role to prevent the spread of infectious diseases such as borreliosis and other bacterial diseases caused by ticks.*

Keywords: *multifunctional textiles, essential oils, repellent, tick.*

1. Introduction

Since the middle ages, essential oils have been widely used for bactericidal, fungicidal, insecticidal, medicinal and cosmetic applications, especially nowadays in pharmaceutical, sanitary, cosmetic, agriculture and food industries.

In recent years, the use of essential oils derived from aromatic plants as low-risk insecticides has increased considerably. Essential oils have easily produced by steam distillation from plant material and contain many volatile compounds, low-molecular-weight terpenes and phenolics.

Some essential oils have repellent activity on a large variety of insects. Some compounds have neurotoxic effects on insects through several mechanisms. Some positive characteristics of volatile oils are: low mammalian toxicity and short environmental persistence. Using volatile oils to repel ticks, helps us to eliminate the amount of chemicals humans are exposed to comparable with synthetic products. Some volatile oils are suitable for direct skin contact, while others work best sprayed on/in clothing. It is important to note that most essential oils cannot be applied directly to the skin without being diluted. As general rule, essential oils must be diluted in a carrier (vegetable oil) no more than 3-5% concentration

2. Material and Methods

The process of extraction used in the Hofigal Company is steam distillation. Most essential oils produced on industrial scale, are obtained by steam distillation of water.

Thus, it has been found that extracts of plants containing the repellent active compounds are the following oils:

1. (*Juniperi Aetheroleum* - juniper oil): obtained from unfermented mature fruits (berries), of *Juniperus communis* from *Cupressaceae* family and adding antioxidant.
2. (*Eucalyptus Aetheroleum* - eucalyptus oil) obtained by steam distillation from the fresh leaves of *Eucalyptus globulus* terminal branches and/or *Eucalyptus polybractea* R.T.Baker and/or *Eucalyptus smithii* R.T.Baker.
3. (*Lavandulae officinalis Aetheroleum* - lavender oil) obtained by steam distillation from *Lavandulae angustifolia*, *Lavandulae officinalis* L floral stems.
4. (*Rosmarini Aetheroleum* - rosemary oil) obtained by steam distillation of water from the aerial parts of the flowering plant of *Rosmarinus officinalis* L, *Lamiaceae* family.

All selected oils were physico-chemical and microbiological characterized: appearance, color, smell, taste, chromatographic profile, relative density, optical rotation, refractive index,

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peroxide value, fatty oils and others. We were used methods from European Pharmacopoeia edition in use.

Conditions of Gas Chromatography analysis

Equipment:

In the present study, we used a mass spectrometer - Thermo Scientific GC-MS (DSQ) Gas Chromatograph coupled with the Trace GC. RTx-5MS, capillary Collar has 30 m length, diameter and film thickness 0.25 μm - Phenyl methyl polysilixan.

The Chromatographic System:

a) Gas Chromatograph equipped with:

- Detector MS (mass spectrometer);
- Automatic integration of peaks in the chromatograms obtained Areas;

b) Column: macrogol 20 000 R (film thickness 0, 25 μm); l = 60 m; \varnothing = 0.25 mm.

Conditions:

- Reservoir of Helium gas-for Chromatography;
- Flow rate: 1.5 mL / min;
- Split ratio: 1/50;
- Volume injected: 1 ml.

3. Results and Discussions

The effectiveness of a compound depends on its composition, the concentration of the constituents, and their type regarding repellency against ticks. The most effective components of the selected oils are α - terpineol (10.04% in juniper), pinene (25.02% in juniper, 14.41% in rosemary), eucalyptol (40% in rosemary, 91.51% in eucalyptus) and limonene. So, it was taken into account eucalyptus volatile oil, for the future studies, having the suitable composition for the intended purpose. It was analyzed in more details so the results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Characterization of Eucalyptus essential oil

Nr. Crt.	Features	Admissibility conditions
1	Description: - appearance - color - smell -taste	- Clear - Colorless to pale yellow - Characteristic - Characteristic
2	Identification: A: α -terpineol si cineol (TLC) B: profil cromatografic (GC)	Positive Positive
3	Relative density, d_{20}^{20}	0,906-0,927
4	Refractive index	1,458-1,470
5	Fatty oils	Nothing remains - translucent or fatty stains
6	Chromatographic profile	As European Pharmacopoeia edition in use
7	Water in the volatile oil sample	Oil sample remains clear
8	Foreign esters in volatile oil	No forming crystals in oil in the first 30 minutes
9	The evaporation residue, %, max.	1,5

GC is performed according to the physico-chemical methods of analysis, developed by the European Pharmacopoeia, edition in use.

Limits are summarized in the following area:

- α - pinene 0,05 - 10% ;
- B- pinene 0,05 - 1,5% .;
- Limonene 0,05 - 15%;
- 1,8-Cineol: minimum 60%;

Textile fabrics with repellent properties should provide comfort to the body's own temperature, permeable to air and water vapor (sweat).

Choice of fabrics to achieve protective effects is done depending on final usage (sportswear / leisure equipment foresters, etc.) and critical features necessary for protection, comfort and performance. Take into account the properties and performance characteristics such as compactness material, abrasion resistance, breathability, air permeability, water resistance breakout force and elongation properties.

Nr.	Nume Component	RT	Peak Area	Area %	S/N	Satura ted
	Pinene- α	26.79	1514325468	2.18	146294.08	No
	Pinene- β	30.78	195598094	0.28	19313.22	No
	Myrcene- β	32.05	311193079	0.45	34630.13	No
	Phelandrene - α	33.16	341023238	0.49	36387.12	No
	Mentadiene-p	34.27	73672752	0.11	7766.83	No
	Limonene	35.20	5351100269	7.69	463790.95	No
	Cimene-p	35.80	2274756835	3.27	160464.80	No
	Eucaliptol(Cineole)	36.29	56561782304	81.32	3105439.67	No
		36.91	40278076	0.06	4857.14	No
	Terpinene-g	37.63	1970546610	2.83	210802.23	No
	Cimene-o	39.91	131323116	0.19	14035.55	No
		43.44	47688970	0.07	5336.85	No
	Pinocarvenol	46.89	49133115	0.07	4914.02	No
	Mentol-p	49.16	195801188	0.28	19024.96	No
	Terpineol	50.86	462458754	0.66	49023.09	No
	Mentil acetate-p	60.74	30393755	0.04	3015.79	No

Fig. 1 Eucalyptus oil cromatogram

Conclusions

-Were analyzed in detail plant extracts (volatile oils) to identify active substances used in encapsulation experiments, through specific methods in accordance with the European Pharmacopoeia edition in use, chromatographic techniques: GC-MS (Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry) and HPLC (High Pressure Performance Liquid Chromatography);

-From the obtained results was selected eucalyptus volatile oil as Chemical Complex Structure, which has the role of natural repellent of ticks.

-In The future will be tested both on tick repellent optimal doses that must be encapsulated.

-The most important parameter for multifunctional textile treatment is the sustainability of repeated washing and extended storage.

This parameter will be tested to compare the effect of repellency for different variants of microcapsules containing the active product with quick release repellent agent, and long term release.

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THE EVOLUTION OF ACETALDEHYDE AND CITRIC ACID IN YOGURT DURING STORAGE

R. TUFEANU, M. A. TIȚA, O. TIȚA

Abstract: Yogurt is a product consumed all over the world. Studies have shown that the most significant aromatic components in yogurt are acetaldehyde, acetone, acetoin, and diacetyl in addition to acetic, butanoic, formic, and propanoic acids. In this study was followed the variation in time of the concentration of citric acid and acetaldehyde in yoghurt with chia powder and pumpkin seed powder by the enzymatic analysis. Two types of yogurt were obtained by adding chia powder and pumpkin flour into semi skimmed cow milk. Measurements were performed during 4 weeks, at each 7 days, using the Stat Fax 1904 chemistry analyser. The results showed that the yogurt with pumpkin seed powder has citric acid concentration higher than yogurt with chia. The concentration of acetaldehyde follow almost same trend for both products. After analysis was proved that the concentration of citric acid and acetaldehyde increases during storage at 4°C.

Keywords: yogurt, chia powder, pumpkin seeds powder, acetaldehyde, citric acid.

1. Introduction

Yogurt is consumed and popular in many parts of the world due to its nutritional and health benefits. Two typical strains for yogurt production are *Streptococcus thermophilus* and *Lactobacillus delbrueckii* subsp. *bulgaricus*, whose role consists in milk acidification and synthesis of aromatic compounds (Güler and Park, 2011).

According to Tamime and Robinson (2001) flavour compounds that contribute to the final aroma of yogurt may be categorized in: non-volatile acids (lactic or pyruvic), volatile acids (butyric or acetic), carbonyl compounds (acetaldehyde or diacetyl) and other compounds (amino acids).

Studies have shown that lactic acid, acetaldehyde and diacetyl concentrations, and their proportions are essential for the final aroma of yogurt (Beshkova et al., 1998; Güler and Gürsoy-Balcı, 2011, ; Kaminarides et al., 2007; Routray and Mishra, 2011).

According to Ott et al. (2000) carbonyl compounds of yogurt are influenced by several factors including: the type of starter culture, type and quality of raw milk, incubation, cooling and storage. Variations in the strains can affect the synthesis of carbonyl compounds, even if *Streptococcus thermophilus* and *Lactobacillus delbrueckii* subsp. *bulgaricus* are lactic acid bacteria used for yoghurt production (Zourari et al., 1992; Tamime and Robinson, 2001).

In the present study was analysed the concentration of citric acid and acetaldehyde in

yogurt with chia powder and pumpkin flour at 7th day, 14th day, 21st day and 28th day.

2. Material and Methods

Materials

Semi skimmed milk was purchased from Romanian commercial system. Mixed yogurt cultures were from CHR.HANSEN, obtained in freeze-dried form and stored at -18°C until use. Chia powder and pumpkin flour were also purchased from commercial system.

Yogurt preparation

Yogurt samples were obtained by adding chia powder (0.5 %) and pumpkin flour (0.5 %) into semi skimmed milk. Milk with powder was heated at 45°C and inoculated with starter culture.

Each mix was distributed in plastic containers and incubated at 42°C for approximately 3.5 hours, until the acidity reached 65°T. Then the yogurt was cooled at 25 °C for 30 minutes and stored at 4 °C for 28 days.

The enzymatic analysis was performed using the Stat Fax 1904 chemistry analyser. The enzymatic determinations are based on the specificity of enzymes, the accuracy of enzyme-catalysed reactions and recognition coefficients extraction of substances that absorb light.

All enzymatic methods to which we refer as UV method is based on measuring the increase and decrease in absorption of NADH or NADPH coenzyme at 340 nm.

3. Results and Discussions

In figure 1 and 2 are represented the results obtained after determining the concentration of citric acid in yogurt with chia powder, respectively yogurt with pumpkin seed powder.

Measurements were performed at 7 days, 14 days, 21 days and 28 days.

Fig. 1. Concentration of citric acid in yogurt with chia powder

Fig. 2. Concentration of citric acid in yogurt with pumpkin seed powder

In Figure 3 and 4 are represented the results obtained after determining the concentration of

acetaldehyde in yogurt with chia powder, respectively yogurt with pumpkin seed powder.

Figure 3. Concentration of acetaldehyde in yogurt with chia powder

Fig. 4. Concentration of acetaldehyde in yogurt with pumpkin seed powder

According to the figures presented above, the concentration of citric acid and acetaldehyde increases over time. It can be observed in the yogurt with pumpkin seed powder, citric acid concentration is higher than in the yogurt with chia powder. In the case of acetaldehyde, the content follows almost the same trend for both products.

Conclusions

Differences were found in the content of citric acid for the yogurt samples analysed in this study. The yogurt with pumpkin seed powder has higher citric acid content due to the addition of powder. It was concluded that acetaldehyde content is almost the same for both products,

with a very small increase in the case of yogurt with pumpkin seed powder. Thus the final flavour of yogurt, associated with the presence of acetaldehyde, is more powerful with the increasing of storage time

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VARIATION OF PHYSICO-CHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF MOLDY CHEESES DURING STORAGE AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

M. A. TIȚA, R. TUFEANU, O. TIȚA

Abstract: Cheese is a complex and varied product, with characteristics that depend on several factors, including: ripening agents, the composition of fresh cheese and environmental conditions during aging. Temperature and humidity are important parameters in cheeses ripening and for their measuring and monitoring, EBI 20 TH1 device was used. For this study were used three types of mouldy cheeses: Camembert, Brie and Roquefort. Their physico-chemical characteristics were determined for 14 days at different temperatures, respectively: 2°C, 10°C, 14°C. The results showed that with the increase of temperature, humidity and time in the storage room have increased acidity, dry matter and sodium chloride content of samples.

Keywords: mouldy cheeses, storage, temperature, humidity

1. Introduction

Cheese is one of the most interesting, complex and diverse product obtained by processing milk, which must correspond to certain requirements concerning sensory characteristics, physicochemical and microbiological (Al-Otaibi et al., 2015; Tița, 2005). Fermented cheeses with noble moulds belong to the group cheese fermented with soft paste, some of the most popular being Camembert, Roquefort or Gorgonzola (Tița, 2005).

The cheese complex ecosystem is constituted by three factors: ripening agents, represented by enzymes and microorganisms, the composition of fresh cheese and environmental conditions during aging (Lessard et al., 2012; Al-Otaibi et al., 2015). These factors play an important role in determining and defining the sensory quality of the final product, and also in the variety of chesses produced worldwide (Alemena-Aliste and Miettton, 2014). The most common ripening fungi used to obtained Camembert-type cheese are *Penicillium camemberti*, *Geotrichum candidum*, *Kluyveromyces lactis* and *Debaryomyces hansenii*.

These ripening strains are the principal contributors to the sensory characteristics of chesse due to their biochemical and microbiological changes during ripening period (Spinnler and Gripon, 2004; McSweeney, 2004, Boutrou et al., 2006).

Temperature-dependent storage of most foods has three major roles: to allow ripening of products, to prevent quality defects and to

control pathogen growth. To decide if a food requires time/temperature control for safety, the properties of the product must be considered (Bishop and Smukowski, 2006).

The changes that occur during cheese ripening are complex and take place in a certain order. Quantitative changes refers to: reducing the moisture of cheese, corresponding to the duration and conditions of temperature and humidity in the ripening room; increasing the salt concentration as a result of dehydration in the process of cheese ripening; almost total disappearance of the lactose that is converted to lactic acid, which may remain as such or is degraded to other flavour compounds; reducing the amount of protein casein by their hydrolysis under the influence of proteolytic enzymes. Qualitative changes refers to: change in consistency of cheese, whose rubbery paste consistency, compact, elastic, becomes more plastic, more unctuous; defining the cheeses rind, characteristic for every sort; flavour formation, a consequence of the accumulation quantity of flavouring substances (Tița, 2005).

The aim of this study is to determine the physico-chemical *characteristics* of mouldy cheeses for 14 days at different temperatures, respectively: 2°C, 10°C, 14°C.

2. Material and Methods

For this study were used three types of mouldy cheeses: Sample 1 – Camembert; Sample 2 – Brie; Sample 3 – Roquefort.

Measuring and monitoring the temperature and humidity

Temperature and humidity were measured in the storage room and for this purpose was used the EBI 20 TH1 device (figure 1).

For viewing and reading monitored data, this device is connected to a computer. Cheeses were monitored at temperatures: $2^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 1\%$, $10^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 1\%$ and $14^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 1\%$.

Fig. 1. EBI 20-TH1 Humidity/Temperature Logger (www.ebro.com)

Dry matter content was measured using Moisture analyser AND ML-50.

The operation of this moisture analyser is based on the principle of thermo-gravimetric analysis, achieving the drying of samples using halogen lamp and obtaining moisture content in%.

Acidity determination

The acidity is determined by titration with NaOH solution to neutralize the sample in the presence of phenolphthalein as an indicator.

Sodium chloride determination.

Argentometric titration

The chlorides are extracted from the sample with hot water, $70\text{--}80^{\circ}\text{C}$ and chlorine ions are titrated with a solution of silver nitrate, in the presence of potassium chromate as indicator.

3. Results and Discussions

Measuring and monitoring the temperature and humidity

Results obtained by measuring these parameters with EBI 20 TH1 device are shown in the following figures:

Dry matter content determination

Fig. 2. Variation in time of temperature and humidity at $2^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 1\%$

Fig. 3. Variation in time of temperature and humidity at 10°C ± 1%

Fig. 4. Variation in time of temperature and humidity at 14°C ± 1%

The results show that during a day appear temperature and humidity fluctuations.

Dry matter content determination - Results obtained by determining the dry matter

content for the cheese samples are shown in Figure 5.

Fig.5. Dry matter content variation for 1-Camembert; 2 – Brie; 3 – Roquefort.

From the figure can be observed that with the growth of temperature increases the dry matter content for all products analysed. The highest dry matter content is registered by Roquefort cheese.

Acidity determination

The results from acidity determination for the mouldy cheeses are shown in figure 6.

Fig. 6. Acidity variation for 1-Camembert; 2 – Brie; 3 – Roquefort

The results indicate that for all types of cheese, the acidity increases with the increase of

temperature. Roquefort cheese has the highest acidity than the other two assortments.

Sodium chloride determination.

Argentometric titration

Fig. 7. NaCl content variation for 14 days

From the figure it can be concluded that with the growth of temperature increases the amount of salt in the product. Roquefort cheese has the highest salt content, followed by Brie assortment.

Conclusions

The dry matter content, sodium chloride content and acidity of the cheese have increased depending on the parameters: temperature, humidity and time. Dry matter and salt content, and acidity increase with increasing temperature. It is very important to monitor the factors temperature and humidity, because they have influence on the product properties.

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HEALTHY EATING HABITS OF PUPILS FROM URBAN AREA FROM REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA

A. TOPADA¹

Abstract: *The purpose of the research was to study the main food consumption among pupils in urban areas from Moldova in the day that preceded the questionnaire. The survey is based on a sample of 1453 pupils (719 boys, 734 girls) from VIIIth-XIIth grades from lyceum from Chisinau and Balti. It was found that food menu included in the great majority of pupils: cereals, meat dishes, dairy products, potatoes, fruits and vegetables (raw or cooked). Are not included in the alimentation of most pupils following groups of products: raw fruit juice, eggs, fish and legumes.*

Keywords: *pupils, eating products, urban area.*

1. Introduction

The needed resources of protein, carbohydrates and fat child growing body receives from the diet. To satisfy all necessities of body child needs a diet rich and diverse in fruits, vegetables, meat, fish, dairy, legumes and eggs. Depending on age and gender are calculated daily intake of such products [1].

The evidence for a protective effect of greater vegetable and fruit consumption is consistent for cancers of the stomach, esophagus, lung, oral cavity and pharynx, endometrium, pancreas, and colon. The types of vegetables or fruit that most often appear to be protective against cancer are raw vegetables, followed by allium vegetables, carrots, green vegetables, cruciferous vegetables, and tomatoes. Current USA vegetable and fruit intake, which averages about 3.4 servings per day, is discussed, as are possible non cancer-related effects of increased vegetable and fruit consumption, including benefits against cardiovascular disease, diabetes, stroke, obesity, diverticulosis, and cataracts. [2].

Studies show that there is a positive association between egg consumption and risk of cardiovascular disease or type 2 diabetes [3,4]. Europe faces obesity epidemic: half of adults and one in five children in European Region now announces WHO are overweight. Another problem is the double burden of child malnutrition, undernourishment and obesity are found simultaneously, especially in some countries in Eastern Europe. Anemia arising from malnutrition, which affects a sizeable proportion

of preschool children. Moldova is facing deficiency of iodine, iron and folic acid as public health problems. About one third of children aged up to 5 years, a fifth of women of childbearing age and 40% of pregnant women suffer from anemia [13].

More than half of the disease from Europe, measured in DALY (years of healthy life lost due to disability and premature death; 2005 WHO) is due seven nutritional risk factors: high blood pressure (12.8%); alcohol (10.1%); high serum cholesterol (8.7%); overweight (7.8%); low fruit and vegetables consumption (4.4%) and physical inactivity (3.55%) [12].

2. Material and Methods

To achieve the goal and objectives, were used following research methods: sociological, analytical, descriptive statistics and mathematical. The research was conducted by survey on a sample of 1453 pupils from VIIIth-XIIth grades from Chisinau and Balti (719 boys and 734 girls). Sample structure has been divided into two parts according to the language of teaching, so in high schools with teaching in Romanian were included 735 pupils (349 boys and 386 girls) and high schools with teaching in Russian 718 pupils (370 boys and 348 girls). Anonymity was preserved. Mathematical and statistical processing of primary data was performed using the Statistical Package for the Social Program Science and variation methods were used for analysis and mathematical modeling. Differences were considered

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statistically significant at $p < 0.05$. The questionnaire used to collect the data of 39 items was based on the frequency of food intake of schoolchildren. The questions are geared towards assessing the consumption of certain foods on the day preceding the questioning: fruits, raw fruit juice, raw and cooked vegetables, meat dishes, fish, cereals, milk, eggs and legumes consumed day preceding the questioning. Also were collected demographic data from respondents including: gender, residence, grade and family data. The study results are necessary to ensure an intervention at the school level by introducing at class hours, civics, biology some topics about nutrition.

3. Results and Discussions

According to the survey it was found that did not eat raw fruits on the day preceding the questioning 19.7% of pupils (girls - 21.6%, boys - 17.6%) from high schools with tuition in Romanian and 20.2 % of pupils (girls - 21.8%, boys - 18.5%) with teaching in Russian. While questioning took place in October, when in Moldova are abundant fruits and vegetables it was found that once a day ate raw fruits 38.2% of pupils (girls - 41.6%, boys - 38.2%) teaching in Romanian and 33.9% of pupils (girls - 37.2%, boys - 31.0%) with teaching in Russian. Two or more times a day ate raw fruits 42.1% of pupils (girls - 36.8%, boys - 48.1%, $p < 0.05$) with tuition in Romanian and 45.9% of pupils (girls - 41.0%, boys - 50.5%) with teaching in Russian.

Raw fruit juice consumption is a practice used less by pupils, so on the day, preceding the questioning did not drink raw fruit juice 83.3% of pupils (girls - 84.6%, boys - 81.8%) from high schools with tuition in Romanian and 68.4% of pupils (girls - 69.9%, boys - 67.1%) of the Russian-language high schools ($p < 0.001$). Of those who drank raw fruit juice pacified that drank only once a day 12.6% of pupils with tuition in Romanian and 19.5% of pupils with instruction in Russian; drank twice a day raw fruit juice 4.1% of pupils from high schools with tuition in Romanian and 12.1% of pupils from high schools with teaching in Russian.

Although is recommended by WHO [5] daily consumption of fruit and raw vegetables, those who ate raw vegetables are in a share of 46.4% of pupils (girls - 43.3%, boys - 49.7%) from high schools with tuition in Romanian and 25.4% of pupils (girls - 25.8%, boys - 24.9%) of the Russian-language high schools ($p < 0.001$). Once,

on the day preceding the questioning, consumed raw vegetables 35.3% of pupils from high schools with tuition in Romanian and 38.2% of pupils from high schools with teaching in Russian. Twice a day consumed raw vegetables 18.3% of pupils from high schools with tuition in Romanian and 36.4% of pupils from high schools with tuition in Russian. ($p < 0.001$).

It was found that didn't eat cooked vegetables (boiled, crushed, roasted, canned) a share of 27.8% of pupils (girls - 28.2%, boys - 27.2%) from high schools with tuition in Romanian and 31.9 % of pupils (girls - 30.2%, boys - 33.7%) of high schools teaching in Russian. Cooked vegetables are consumed every day by 48.6% of in pupils from high schools with tuition in Romanian and 44.2% of pupils with instruction in Russian. Twice a day eat cooked vegetables 23.6% of pupils from high schools with tuition in Romanian and 23.8% of pupils from high schools with teaching in Russian.

Although potatoes are vegetables, WHO includes them in the base of food pyramid with cereals, and frying potatoes in oil trained as an element of the top of pyramid with high fat. [6]. Didn't eat potatoes the day before that preceded the questioning of 50.0% of pupils (girls - 54.9%, boys - 44.5%, $p < 0.05$) in high schools with tuition in Romanian and 49.5% of pupils (girls - 56.1%, boys - 43.3%, $p < 0.05$) in high schools with teaching in Russian. Once a day ate potatoes 42.2% of pupils from high schools with teaching in Romanian, and 39.9% of pupils from high schools with teaching in Russian. Consumed potatoes two or more times a day 7.8% of pupils from high schools with tuition in Romanian and 10.6% of pupils from high schools with teaching in Russian.

Although the questionnaire was not stipulated type of meat that is consumed, white or red, processed or not, 27.2% of pupils (girls - 33.2%, boys - 20.7%, $p < 0.05$) in high schools Romanian-language and 22.9% of pupils (girls - 27.3%, boys - 18.8%) of the Russian-language secondary schools say they have not eaten meat dishes. Consumed meat dishes once on the day preceding the questioning 51.9% of pupils from high schools with tuition in Romanian and 48.8% of pupils from high schools with teaching in Russian, and 20.9% of pupils (girls - 12.1% boys - 30.4%, $p < 0.01$) in high schools with tuition in Romanian and 28.3% of pupils (girls - 19.1%, boys - 36.9%, $p < 0.01$) of high schools teaching in Russian consumed twice or more meat dishes.

A share of 85.5% of pupils (girls - 86.3%, boys - 84.7%) in high schools with tuition in Romanian and 87.8% of pupils (girls - 86.7%, boys - 88.8%) of the Russian-language does not consume fish.

The share of pupils surveyed who did not eat dishes of legumes (beans, peas, chickpeas, soybeans, grain, etc.) is very impressive 87.4% of pupils (girls - 91.5%, boys - 82.9% $p < 0.01$) in high schools with tuition in Romanian and 91.7% of pupils (girls - 93.1%, boys - 90.5%) of high schools teaching in Russian.

It is focus on consumption of milk and dairy products, started from European programs introducing school milk to WHO global strategy [7].

The study found that 30.4% of pupils (girls - 34.6%, boys - 25.7%) of high schools with tuition in Romanian and 30.6% of pupils (girls - 33.2%, boys - 28.1 %) of the Russian-language high schools do not eat daily milk and dairy products such as kefir, yogurt, cottage cheese, cheese, etc.

In the group of Romanian-language study subject did not eat cereal products 1.2% of pupils and 98.8% other pupils who ate cereal products on the day preceding the questionnaire said following products: bread (77.4%), rolls (31.3%) pies (28.2%), macaroni (17.9%), soft mushes of cereals (16.1%) and polenta (4.8%). Russian-language pupils did not eat cereal products 1.4%, other 98.6% have consumed the following products: bread (72.5%), rolls (26.9%) of cereal porridges (24.7 %) pies (22.5%), pasta (21.6%) and polenta (3.1%).

A share of 73.7% of pupils (girls - 77.7%, boys - 69.3%, $p < 0.05$) in high schools with tuition in Romanian and 70.4% of pupils (girls - 75.8% boys - 65.4%, $p < 0.05$) in high schools with teaching in Russian did not consume eggs on the day preceding the questioning.

Consumed once eggs 24.9% of pupils from high schools with tuition in Romanian and 25.1% of the pupils taught in Russian; two or more times a day ate eggs 1.4% of pupils from high schools with tuition in Romanian and 4.5% of pupils from high schools with teaching in Russian.

Through the Youth Risk Behavior Survey study (YRBS) conducted in the United States by CDC in 2013 among pupils of IXth-XIIth grades was found that nationally, 61.5% of pupils ate vegetables from one or several times a day. The share is two times higher than that obtained in our study (35.3% pupils with tuition in Romanian

and 38.2% pupils with teaching in Russian). It was found that 40.3% of pupils have consumed dairy products one or more times daily, quota of pupils in our study is 1.5 times higher (69.6% pupils with tuition in Romanian and 69.4% of pupils taught in Russian) [8].

There are limited data about children's consumption of fruit and vegetables to in Europe, but one study suggests that it is between 6% and 24% of European children reach WHO recommendations [9]. When combined fruit and vegetables, the largest quantities are consumed in Austria (24.1%) and Portugal (21.4%) and lowest in Iceland (7.8%) and Spain (9.7%). Type of consumed vegetable varies by geographic location. In the north, consumption of raw vegetables was higher 5.9% in Denmark, 16.4% in Norway, while in southern Europe were the main sources of vegetable soups vegetables 22.7% in Portugal and 1.0 % in Spain [10]. In the study conducted by us consume raw vegetables 3-5 times more pupils (53.6% of high schools with tuition in Romanian and 74.6% with teaching in Russian) than those in European countries, and cooked vegetables are consumed by a number of 3-6 times higher (72.2% pupils in schools with tuition in Romanian and 68.0% pupils from high schools with teaching in Russian) as in Europeans.

In Norway and Slovenia daily use fresh juices, fruits and vegetables 48-50% of children [11]. According to our information daily consume fresh juices (16.7-31.6% of children), fresh fruit (79.8-80.3% of children) and fresh vegetables (53.6-74.6% of children).

Conclusions

1. Foods included in the daily ration of the vast majority of pupils are cereals, meat dishes, dairy products, potatoes, fruits and vegetables (raw or cooked).
2. Are not included in the diet to most pupils following food groups: raw fruit juices, eggs, fish and legumes.
3. Boys consume significantly more meat dishes, eggs and potatoes than girls. Boys from high schools with tuition in Romanian consume significantly more raw fruits and vegetables than girls.
4. Pupils from high schools with teaching in Russian consume significantly more raw fruit juice and raw vegetables than those in high schools with tuition in Romanian.

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STUDY CONCERNING THE APPLICATION OF THE ANALYTIC HIERARCHY PROCESS IN OPTIMIZING THE SUPPLIERS' SELECTION PROCEDURE IN THE COMPANIES FROM THE HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY

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Abstract: *Suppliers' selection and evaluation are of a crucial importance for the success of a company from the sector of tourist hospitality, because the cost and quality of tourist services directly depend on the cost and quality of the previously acquired goods and services, on the logistic chain. This paper integrates itself in the research effort to elaborate suppliers' selecting methods from the tourist hospitality logistic chain, proposing for this aim the analytic hierarchy process, a useful instrument in solving complex, unstructured and with multiple objective problems. Based on the fundamentals of the method, there is introduced a case study, with detailed exemplification of the items that are followed within an application that may sustain managers in effectively improving the suppliers' selection and evaluation process, by using criteria specific to sustainability. Considering our knowledge up to now, this is the first application of the analytic hierarchy process in a Romanian company from the hospitality system.*

Key words: *supplier selection, analytic hierarchy process, multi-criteria decision-making, tourism sustainability*

1. INTRODUCTION

It is obvious the apparition of a competition not only between companies from tourist hospitality domain, but also between logistic chains in which these ones are integrated as performers of tourist services towards the final consumer. This competition imposes an attentive selection, based on scientific rigor of suppliers on the logistic chain. The study of suppliers selection methods has shown that there is a large paddle of approaches, from simpler techniques, with one objective, such as the cost method, up to the most complex ones, such as the methods of linear programming with multiple objectives. Among these ones, a method of supplier selection proper to decisions specific to activity management from tourist hospitality system, that requires both quantitative and qualitative aspects, is analytic hierarchy process (AHP – Analytic Hierarchy Process), method elaborated by Thomas Saaty (1980).

As in the case of multi-criteria analyses, by reducing complex decisions to a series of comparisons and by result synthesis, AHP captures elements of subjective and objective analyses, but also including a useful technique to verify evaluation consistence made by decision-makers, which assures a reduction of aleatory factor influence. Because there is presupposed a larger organizational effort and mathematic calculations of medium difficulty, it is recommended to apply AHP method in case of material resources from the principal ones group or in case of investigations in equipments and installations.

2. WORK METHOD-THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL ASPECTS CONCERNING THE PROCEDURE OF HYERARCHIC ANALYSES-

Basically, AHP approach starts from a hierarchy construction, consisting in defining

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an aim, selection criteria and a set of alternative options, on bases of which there is elaborated a series of matrixes that contain relative values of the criteria and alternatives. It is important to remember that, as certain criteria may be in opposition, the best solution is not the one that optimizes a special criterion, but the one that assures the best compromise in relation to whole criteria. At the highest level of the hierarchy there is situated the final aim of the demarche, and at inferior levels there are situated all possible alternatives. Criteria weight and alternative scores are used as elements of the decision in the second stage of the decision process. In order to simplify his missions, the decision-maker is asked to express his options based on comparisons of decision attributes (criteria and alternatives), taken two by two. Options are expressed by giving notes (weights and scores) regarding an attribute importance, in relation to the attribute with which it is compared. Weight value v_i and the scores one r_{ij} , are deduced from these comparisons and are included in a decision table. In the last step of AHP method, all qualifiers from the decision table are aggregated by determining the sum of the products between alternative scores and criteria weight, thus:

$$R_j = \sum_i v_i * r_{ij}$$

The R_j priorities so obtained are finally used for the classification of alternatives and selection of the one that satisfies the best the final aim defined on the first hierarchy level (Sevkly et all, 2008). The first and the last step of the method are relatively simple and do not imply discussions, while the step of attribute importance evaluation (criteria and alternatives), on the bases of the comparison of pairs of attributes, constitutes the most important stage of AHP method. One starts from the hypothesis that the decision-maker may compare any attribute A_i and A_j , situated on the same hierarchic level, as well as he may give a mark of the importance of A_i attribute comparatively to the A_j attribute, mark noted with a_{ij} . In case the decision-maker considers that A_i attribute is more important than A_j attribute, then

$a_{ij} > 1$. Another basic hypothesis consists in the reciprocity property: $a_{ji} = 1/a_{ij}$, no matter which it may be $i=1,2,3...n$ and $j=1,2,3...n$.

Any set of comparisons for n elements needs $[n(n-1)]/2$ evaluations of the decision-maker. In general, the second set of evaluations, for the elements situated under the main diagonal of the comparison matrix, is not made, having in view the application of the reciprocity principle. Evaluations are made on basis of the 9 step written test, which begins with the first step, corresponding to an equal importance of the two compared attributes, up to the 9th step, corresponding to an extremely big importance of one of the attributes, in relation to the attribute with which it is compared. After the expert evaluates the suppliers 'selection criteria, there is calculated the specific priority of each supplier/alternative, on the bases of marks given by the decision-maker, referring to the degree in which every supplier/alternative satisfies every criteria request, face to the supplier/alternative with whom it is compared (Tung and Tang, 1998).

The marks are mentioned in a matrix, whose particular form allows making all following calculations until suppliers/alternative selection that satisfies at the highest degree the final aim. In the case of each mark matrix it is determined a priority vector $w_i = (w_1, w_2, w_3, \dots w_n)^T$, by applying prioritization techniques such as the average value method or the method of the smallest squares (Sevkly et all, 2008). The set of n relative priorities may be normalized by dividing each of them at their sum, so that:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \bar{w}_i = 1$$

where $\bar{w}_i > 1$, no matter which $i=1,2,3...n$, \bar{w}_i being normalized relative priorities.

Hereinafter, there is determined the evaluation consistence rate (RC), in order to establish the decision-maker's evaluation consistence degree in relation to a rate of aleatory evaluation consistence, determined by the author of the method in function of the

order of the evaluation square matrix (Saaty, 1980). If the consistence rate exceeds 0,1 then it is considered that evaluations are not to be trusted (they have been made without responsibility or without knowing the concrete situation).

In the last stage, there is elaborated the optimum performance matrix and there is obtained the final preference vector, the one

that offers the answer to the problem, respectively the relative merits of every offer face to the final aim of the tourist company.

The problem of the supplier's selection has been treated by using the questionnaire method applied to a group of specialists from the interior of a tourist company. The research framework is presented in figure no. 1:

Figure no. 1 – Methodological framework of the paper

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

- CASE STUDY: APPLICATION OF AHP METHOD FOR THE SELECTION OF THE DISHWASHER LINE OFFER FOR A RESTAURANT -

The offer selection criteria have been established on the basis of the options of five managers from relevant compartments from the company owning the restaurant that was to use the installation: supply department, investment department, production department,

maintenance and repair department and restaurant managing director.

In order to express their opinion, experts have been proposed to use the Saaty comparing question test, presented in table no. 1, in order to evaluate the relative importance of an attribute, comparatively to another (attributes are to be compared two by two), by reporting to the element from the immediately superior hierarchic level. The evaluation is made from top to bottom, starting from the highest level towards the inferior level, by filling in the questionnaire.

Table no. 1 – Criteria and alternative comparison questionnaire test

Importance intensity	Significance	Explanations
1	Equal importance	The two criteria have an equal contribution to reach the aim established by the decision-maker or the two suppliers and offer a solution that equally satisfies the criteria
3	Moderate importance	One of the criteria has a higher moderate contribution to reach the aim or one of the two compared suppliers

		offers a better moderate solution in relation to the reference criterion
5	Big importance	One of the two compared criteria has a significantly higher contribution to reach the aim or one of the two compared suppliers offers an obviously better solution in relation to the reference criterion
7	Very big importance	One of the two compared criteria has a much higher contribution to reach the aim or one of the two compared suppliers offers a much better solution in relation to the reference criterion
9	Extreme importance	One of the two compared criteria has the highest possible contribution to reach the aim or one of the two compared suppliers offers the best possible solution in relation to the reference criterion
2,4,6,8	Intermediate values	Values used in case of a compromise between the situations described in the above lines

The Saaty questionnaire test offers the decision-makers the possibility to intuitively and naturally include in evaluation both their experience and knowledge.

Figure no. 2 presents the structure of the hierarchy of the problem to select the dishwasher line supplier that comprises three levels. The highest level is assigned to the final aim of the analyses, respectively the choice of the supplier which offers the best delivery conditions and the best appropriate equipment to concrete restaurant necessities, and, at the next level there are the supplier's selection

criteria, including the size of line, the price of the offer, the delivery term, the guaranty period, the time limit for payment, energy and water consumption, maintenance, characteristics of the used consumable items in current exploitation. The number of eight selected criteria is situated at the maximum limit indicated by Saaty (1980), as a consequence of observing that decision makers facing more than seven alternatives (plus/minus two) become confuse, and the evaluation consistence is affected. The third hierarchy level is designed to potential suppliers and their offer.

Figure no. 2 – Hierarchic structure of the problem to select the offer of dishwasher line

Arranging the aim and attributes (criteria and alternative offers) in a hierarchic structure offer the advantage of an overview perspective upon complex relations between factors that contribute to solve the problem and their importance in relation to the analyses final aim.

As a consequence of the process of evaluation of pair attributes, there are created a number of square matrixes, named raw matrixes of relative preferences.

Respecting the evaluation principle from upside down, in the first stage experts are asked to compare the selection criteria of the best dishwasher line, in conformity with the grid with nine importance appreciation steps. The marks given by experts have been aggregated, in order to get a single evaluation afferent to a comparison, the marks noted in raw matrixes of relative preferences resulting by determining the geometrical mean of individual evaluations (Bahurmoz, 2003), as they are presented in table no. 2

Table 2 – Raw matrix of evaluation of the importance of selection criteria

CRITERIUM	Size of dishwasher line	Acquisition price	Delivery term	Guarantee period	Time limit for payment	Energy and water consumption	Maintenance	Bio consumable utilization
Size of dishwasher line	1	5	7	7	9	3	5	2
Acquisition price	1/5	1	4	4	3	1	2	2
Delivery term	1/7	1/4	1	3	1	1/2	1/2	1/3
Guarantee period	1/7	1/4	1/3	1	3	1/2	1	1/3
Time limit for payment	1/9	1/3	1	1/3	1	1/2	1/2	1/3

Energy and water consumption	1/3	1	2	2	2	1	1	1
Maintenance	1/5	1/2	2	1	2	1	1	1/2
Utilization of bio consumables	1/2	1/2	3	3	3	1	2	1

On the main diagonal, there is noted the figure 1, because every criterion has an equal importance comparing itself. In giving qualifiers, the decision-makers have taken into consideration the restriction concerning the dimensions of the space where the dishwasher line was to be placed, reason for which the line size criterion is significantly more important than the acquisition price criterion, therefore on line 1, column 2 there is written the figure 5, and, according to the reciprocity principle, on line 2, column 1 there is written the fraction 1/5. There has also been appreciated that the line size criterion is very important in comparison to the delivery term criterion and the guarantee term criterion, as well as extremely important face to the time limit for payment criterion. Considering the ever growing pressure made by state institutions concerning the environment protection, as well

as the options of the society leaders in this direction, the line size criterion is appreciated as being of a slightly bigger importance than the criterion of biodegradable consumable utilization in the line current exploitation. A higher qualifier has been obtained by the line acquisition price criterion, as it might have been estimated since the beginning of the analyses, which is considered to be significantly more important than the delivery term criterion and the guarantee period criterion and moderately more important than the time limit for payment criterion, which presupposes that the commercial society owner of the restaurant disposes of necessary cash in order to purchase the line. In conformity with the reciprocity principle, on the corresponding positions under the main diagonal there are written the corresponding sub unitary fractions (table no. 3):

Table 3 – Raw evaluation matrix of selection criteria importance with the mark sum on column

CRITERIUM	Size of dishwasher line	Acquisition price	Delivery term	Guarantee period	Time limit for payment	Energy and water consumption	Maintenance	Utilization of bio consumables
Size of dishwasher line	1	5	7	7	9	3	5	2
Acquisition price	1/5	1	4	4	3	1	2	2
Delivery term	1/7	1/4	1	3	1	1/2	1/2	1/3
Guarantee period	1/7	1/4	1/3	1	3	1/2	1	1/3
Time limit	1/9	1/3	1	1/3	1	1/2	1/2	1/3

for payment								
Energy and water consumption	1/3	1	2	2	2	1	1	1
Maintenance	1/5	1/2	2	1	2	1	1	1/2
Utilization of bio consumables	1/2	1/2	3	3	3	1	2	1
Sum on column	2,6302	8,8333	20,3333	21,3333	24,0000	8,5000	13,0000	7,5000

After normalization of the raw matrix of evaluation of selection criteria importance by relating every qualifier to the qualifier sum on column (table no. 3 and table no. 4), applying the arithmetic mean method

on matrix line, there is calculated the relative preference vector of the evaluation criteria of dishwasher line offer:

Table 4 – Normalized matrix of the evaluation of selection criteria importance

CRITERIUM	Size of dishwasher line	Acquisition price	Delivery term	Guarantee period	Time limit for payment	Energy and water consumption	Maintenance	Bio consumable utilization
Size of dishwasher line	0,3802	0,5660	0,3443	0,3281	0,3750	0,3529	0,3846	0,2667
Acquisition price	0,0760	0,1132	0,1967	0,1875	0,1250	0,1176	0,1538	0,2667
Delivery term	0,0543	0,0283	0,0492	0,1406	0,0417	0,0588	0,0385	0,0444
Guarantee period	0,0543	0,0283	0,0164	0,0469	0,1250	0,0588	0,0769	0,0444
Time limit for payment	0,0422	0,0377	0,0492	0,0156	0,0417	0,0588	0,0385	0,0444
Energy and water consumption	0,1267	0,1132	0,0984	0,0938	0,0833	0,1176	0,0769	0,1333
Maintenance	0,0760	0,0566	0,0984	0,0469	0,0833	0,1176	0,0769	0,0667
Bio	0,1901	0,0566	0,1475	0,1406	0,1250	0,1176	0,1538	0,1333

consumable utilization								
Sum on column	1,0000	1,0000	1,0000	1,0000	1,0000	1,0000	1,0000	1,0000

The relative preference vector is a vector on column that, from reasons of space economy, we are presenting as a line vector: $w_i^{criteria} = (0,3902; 0,1386; 0,0588; 0,0581; 0,0405; 0,1014; 0,0794; 0,1331)^T$. These eight figures describe the relative importance given by tourist company decision makers to evaluation criteria of dishwasher line offers. The number 0,3902 means that decision makers valorize the line size criterion as being the most important from all criteria; 0,1386 and 0,1331 mean that they confer the „acquisition price” and „bio degradable consumable utilization” criteria a relatively high importance and approximately equal between them; the other numbers denote that decision makers consider that the restaurant may solve the dish, cutlery and glass washing

problem for a period of time, appealing to hand work, as in present too, that company technicians may assure the equipment maintenance without needing the suppliers ‘specialist and the payment may be done in a short term, without affecting the society financial liquidities.

Coming back to the four suppliers, there are hereinafter compared, two by two, the potential suppliers, in function of the degree of satisfaction face to the accomplishment of each of the eight criteria. The first table/matrix presents the decision-makers ‘ evaluation referring to the manner in which potential suppliers fulfill the request of the „dishwasher line size” criterion, by calculating the geometric mean of individual evaluations:

Table no. 5 – Raw matrix of potential suppliers ‘comparisons after the criterion of dishwasher line size

SUPPLIER	S1	S2	S3	S4
S1	1	1/3	2	1/2
S2	3	1	5	2
S3	1/2	1/5	1	1/3
S4	2	1/2	3	1

Given qualifiers denote that the offered line by the potential supplier S2 is significantly more adapted to space restrictions comparatively to the line offered by the potential supplier S1, it much better solves this problem comparatively to the line offered by S3 and a little better than the line offered by S4. A good solution, in function of this criterion, is also the one offered by S4, which is considered a little better than the one offered by S1 and moderately better than the one offered by S3. The relative priority vector for this matrix is

$w_i^{size} = (0,1575; 0,4824; 0,0883; 0,2718)^T$. The rate of evaluation consistence is $0,0054 < 0,1$.

The following six matrixes (tables no. 6 – 11), presented in annex, include the evaluations of the satisfaction degree offered by the four offers, considering the following six mentioned criteria. A special situation has been registered in case of determining the raw matrix of the comparison of potential suppliers ‘offers after the last criterion.

Table no. 12 – Raw matrix of potential suppliers ‘comparisons after the bio degradable consumable utilization criterion

SUPPLIER	S1	S2	S3	S4
S1	1	1/4	1/3	½
S2	4	1	1	3
S3	3	1	1	2
S4	2	1/3	1/2	1

From the point of view of respecting the conditions of environment protection, experts consider the dishwasher line offered by S2 confers a significantly better solution than the line offered by S1, it is moderately better face to the offer S4 and has the same impact upon the environment as the offer S3. The relative priority vector for this matrix is $W_i^{\text{environment protection}} = (0,0978; 0,4004; 0,3369; 0,1648)^T$. The evaluation consistence rate is $0,1458 > 0,1$. In case of this matrix, the consistence rate exceeds the 0,1 threshold and indicates an evaluation aleatorily or without book made by experts. This situation highlights the particular importance of the

determination of the evaluation consistence rate. Although, the overtaking of the threshold is of only 458 hundredth, this doesn't significantly affect the final decision concerning the selected offer. A consistent overtaking of the 0,1 threshold would have indicated the criteria incoherence or the lack of clarity of the manner in which there must be achieved the evaluation by the experts designed by the tourist company. But this type of confusions must be solved. That is why the tourist company experts have been asked to retrace the evaluation, the revised form of the matrix being presented in table no. 13:

Table no. 13 – Raw matrix of potential suppliers ‘comparisons after the bio degradable consumable utilization criterion, revised form

SUPPLIER	S1	S2	S3	S4
S1	1	1/2	1/2	1/2
S2	2	1	2	1
S3	2	1/2	1	1
S4	2	1	1	1

The relative priority vector for the revised matrix is $W_i^{\text{environment protection}} = (0,1409; 0,3373; 0,2401; 0,2817)^T$. The evaluation consistence

rate becomes $0,06 < 0,1$ (acceptable consistence).

The final stage of method application consists in building a matrix of optimum performance, where there appear criteria on the column, and on the line there are written the

scores got by every offer/alternative in function of tourist company experts 'evaluations:

Table no. 14 – Optimum performance matrix

SUPPLIER/ OFFER/ ALTERNATIVE	Dishwasher line size	Acquisition price	Delivery term	Guarantee period	Time limit for payment	Energy and water consumption	Maintenance	Bio consum able utilizati on
Criterion priority	0,3747	0,1546	0,0570	0,0564	0,0410	0,1054	0,0778	0,1331
S1	0,1575	0,1717	0,2857	0,0646	0,2333	0,0909	0,1111	0,1409
S2	0,4824	0,2684	0,1429	0,1650	0,1397	0,0909	0,2222	0,3373
S3	0,0883	0,4618	0,2857	0,2755	0,0847	0,5455	0,4444	0,2401
S4	0,2718	0,0981	0,2857	0,4949	0,5423	0,2727	0,2222	0,2817

This matrix sums up the dishwasher line capabilities, in comparison to tourist company expectations. Scanning the scores obtained by every offer/supplier/alternative, in function of every criterion, leads to several simple observations: the line offered by S2 is much better than the others, from the point of view of the size and conditions concerning environment protection, while the line offered by S3 is superior to the others in function of the offer price, energy and water consumption and possibilities to assure maintenance. The offer S4 is best appreciated after the criterion of accorded guarantee period and the time limit criterion. The offer S1 has not classified on first position in the top after any criterion, considering the tourist company opinion. In case the tourist company would modify the evaluation criteria, it is possible for the position of the four offers to be totally different.

It results that, if the dishwasher line size were the only criterion of offer appreciation, then the tourist company would choose the line offered by S2; if the only request were the lowest acquisition price, the winning offer would be the one presented by S3 so on and so forth.

But the tourist company has a more comprehensive approach of the problem to select the most favorable offers, reason for which in the table, on the first row, there are mentioned the relative priorities of the selected criteria. In order to adopt the decision that mostly satisfies whole the criteria, it is weighed the mark given to each offer with the score of each criterion and it is summed up on the line, for every offer/supplier/alternative. It is thus obtained a vector of the degree how the dishwasher offer satisfies the tourist company needs. The resulting vector is $W_i^{general\ performance} = (0,1520; 0,3172; 0,2638; 0,2670)^T$ and may be expressed in words as it follows:

$$Performance \times Request = General\ performance$$

Consequently:

- The line offered by S1, which has got the 0,1520 score, seems to mostly satisfy the reunited requests of the 8 chosen criteria by the company experts and, therefore, the final aim of the analyses, respectively the choice of the supplier who offers the best delivery conditions and the most adequate equipment to the restaurant concrete necessities;

- The offers S3 and S4 have got relatively close scores, 0,2638 and 0,2670, resulting that they meet in a rather little measure the tourist company expectations;
- The potential supplier S2 has got the highest score, 0,3172, his offer being the one that will be selected by the tourist company, although he has classified on the last position in the experts' appreciations after the delivery criterion and after the energy and water consumption criterion in current exploitation. The relatively higher importance accorded by the tourist company to restrictions concerning the dishwasher line size, as well as to those referring to the environment protection have placed the S2 offer on the first place, by applying the method of hierarchic analyses resulting that this alternative offer utmost satisfies whole the requests.

4. CONCLUSIONS

(1) The advantages of this suppliers' selection method are:

- There are reduced uncertainties, time and effort assigned for the selection of the best available supplier;
- Tourist company strategies are reflected in the activity of supply or investment;
- Superior transparency, because by using the hierarchic analyses

procedure there are reduced the risks induced by individual decision-makers' reasonings and interests, as well as by possible errors or certain consulted experts' vagueness;

- The AHP method allows tourist companies to identify strong and weak point of the logistic chain, hence to act in order to adequate suppliers' objectives to their own objectives.

(2) There is proposed an innovative approach of the problem of tourist company supplier selection, by incorporating certain criteria linked to the application of sustainability principles. It is recommended to apply the procedure on a larger scale in order to put the obtained results a higher trust, because the main disadvantage consists in applying the hierarchic analyses procedure in a singular case of an equipment supplier selection for a company from the hospitality sector.

(3) The hierarchic analyses procedure does not take into consideration the uncertainty induced by the suppliers' behavior and its dynamics in a past period, whose knowledge would improve the selection process.

(4) AHP models are characterized by a high degree of specificity, in function of the context of the decision, which presupposes after the modification of the supply objective or the tourist company needs will determine the modification of hierarchy structure, of the criteria and their weight.

Annex:

Table no. 6 – Raw matrix of potential supplier comparisons after the acquisition price criterion of dishwasher line

SUPPLIER	S1	S2	S3	S4
S1	1	1/2	1/4	3
S2	2	1	1/2	3
S3	4	2	1	3

S4	1/3	1/3	1/3	1
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$W_i^{price} = (0,1717; 0,2684; 0,4618; 0,0981)^T$; the rate of evaluation consistence is $0,07 < 0,1$.

Table no. 7 – Raw matrix of potential suppliers' comparisons after the delivery term criterion of the dishwasher line

SUPPLIER	S1	S2	S3	S4
S1	1	2	1	1
S2	1/2	1	1/2	1/2
S3	1	2	1	1
S4	1	2	1	1

$W_i^{delivery\ term} = (0,2857; 0,1429; 0,2857; 0,2857)^T$; the rate of evaluation consistence is $0 < 0,1$ (perfect consistence).

Table no. 8 – Raw matrix of potential suppliers' comparisons after the guarantee period criterion

SUPPLIER	S1	S2	S3	S4
S1	1	1/3	1/4	1/7
S2	3	1	1/2	1/3
S3	4	2	1	1/2
S4	7	3	2	1

$W_i^{guarantee\ period} = (0,0646; 0,1650; 0,2755; 0,4949)^T$; the rate of evaluation consistence is $0,0076 < 0,1$.

Table no. 9 – Raw matrix of potential suppliers' comparisons after the time limit for payment criterion

SUPPLIER	S1	S2	S3	S4
S1	1	2	3	1/3

S2	1/2	1	2	1/4
S3	1/3	1/2	1	1/5
S4	3	4	5	1

$W_i^{\text{time limit for payment}} = (0,2333; 0,1397; 0,0847; 0,5423)^T$; the rate of evaluation consistence is $0,019 < 0,1$.

Table no. 10 – Raw matrix of potential suppliers' comparisons after the energy and water consumption criterion

SUPPLIER	S1	S2	S3	S4
S1	1	1	1/6	1/3
S2	1	1	1/6	1/3
S3	6	6	1	2
S4	2	1	1/2	1

$W_i^{\text{energy & water consumption}} = (0,0909; 0,0909; 0,5455; 0,2727)^T$; the rate of evaluation consistence is $0 < 0,1$.

Table no. 11 – Raw matrix of potential suppliers' comparisons after the maintenance criterion of the dishwasher line

SUPPLIER	S1	S2	S3	S4
S1	1	1/2	1/4	1/2
S2	2	1	1/2	1
S3	4	2	1	2
S4	2	1	1/2	1

$W_i^{\text{maintenance}} = (0,1111; 0,2222; 0,4444; 0,2222)^T$; the rate of evaluation consistence is $0 < 0,1$.

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TERMS OF DEFINING SOME NOTIONS OF TOURISM - CONSENSUS AND CONTRADICTIONS

N. ȚANE

Abstract: *The necessity of creation of textile fabrics with repellent properties is determined by the presence of a increasingly number of tick that lead to diseases difficult to treat. Textile fabrics with repellent properties can be used as barriers to eliminate or reduce risk of infection caused by ticks especially in forest, agriculture and tourism areas. The main objective is developing new multifunctional textile structures, including in nanostructures biologically active compounds extracted from plants, with the role to prevent the spread of infectious diseases such as borreliosis and other bacterial diseases caused by ticks.*

Keywords: *multifunctional textiles, essential oils, repellent, tick.*

1. Tourism - an industry?

To this question, the answers given by experts in this field are contradictory. A first cause that led to this is the different opinion on what is considered the notion "tourism": from the point of view of the beneficiary (tourists), from the point of view of suppliers of tourism products (economic units in the field) or more broad, global view of the symbiosis between those who produce and those who consume tour packages.

The first two approaches have led to simplistic interpretations, tourism is considered to be either a person's trip for recreation, curative purposes, business, etc., or an amount of services to meet the requirements of tourists. Totally incorrect.

Of course, the evolution of human society throughout history has created conditions for the permanent dynamism of the tourism parameters, so nowadays the phenomenon of tourism has taken a special scale and established socio-economic and cultural connections that require us to define it as a leading industry of the national economy.

According to the dictionary, the industry is a "branch of the material production and of the national economy, in which occurs the exploitation of natural assets, and their transformation, alongside others, into means of production and into consumer goods" [4].

In another sense, the word denotes a business group using the same method for generating profits, such as: the film industry, the meat industry and meat products industry, the media, etc. and, why not, the tourism industry.

The Faculty of Food and Tourism from Transilvania University of Brasov have used this

designation, officially, since 2008 authorizing and subsequently accrediting for the first time in Romania, a program of undergraduate studies called "Engineering and Management in the Tourism Industry" designed to train specialists with complex, interdisciplinary skills, that can be able to satisfy the requirements of this industry that is in constant development.

The tourism industry is composed of two major sub-sectors: hospitality and travel industry (Figure 1.1).

Fig.1.1 Tourism industries

The **Hospitality Industry** coordinates the hotel industry, restaurant industry, and activities of leisure and travel industry, activities focused to plan and organize trips or tourist stays, to provide information to tourists and communicate with them, as well as to link these activities with the elements related to the logistics of the tourism phenomenon.

This definition of the tourism industry better highlights the contribution of each component to achieve the finished product, which is the product / package tour. And at the same time allows a

more fluid flow of information necessary for making decisions in regards to companies' activities.

The accommodation that provides the specific activities of the hotel industry (included in the hospitality industry, which is in turn included in the tourism industry) are the ones known and classified as: hotels, motels, hostels, guest houses, cruise, villas, bungalows plants, camping sites, etc.

Of course, all these accommodations can serve other guests than tourists, but the overwhelming number of accommodated tourists compared to the other categories of persons, makes this sector rightly placed in the tourism industry.

The same question arises in the case of food services. Analysis of the similarity between the term "food service" and "restaurant industry" will be done in Section 2.

Travel industry specific activities are provided by tour operators, travel agents, national, regional or local tourism offices, and other units with an activity specific to this domain.

It is a great error to fully overlap the concept of "tourism" with the "travel industry". In support of this assertion comes the universally accepted definition for the tourism activity "The tourism activity is considered the activity that meets the defining parameters of tourism, or, that uses the same basis of accommodation and food, and consumes the same packages of tourism products".

The phrase "hospitality and tourism" excludes the hotel and restaurant from the tourism industry, which is a big mistake!

The explanation "it goes the same for others, with a bigger tradition in tourism" shows the lack of specific meaning, in Romanian or in other languages (especially English), the convenience of thought and the tendency to adapt the Romanian tourism to the European one by copying and not through integration.

2. The phrases "food service" and "restaurant industry" - are synonymous?

DEX (explanatory dictionary of the Romanian language) quite succinctly defines the phrase "food service" as the "network of commercial enterprises serving the population with food and drink".

Building on this definition, we can say that the "food service" means the activity that deals with the production of a variety of meals and / or drinks, which are served to the consumers in their

own specially designed units. Production and service of preparations is ensured by personnel with specific training.

By serving consumers we understand all methods, means and systems used for the transportation, the presentation, and the offering to consumers of culinary products and beverages in a public eating establishment.

Food services are conducted in two distinct directions: proper feeding of certain categories of the population, and ensuring the need for entertainment and socialization of customers through the specific environment that is being created in specialized units.

In the catering establishments there are two sectors: the production sector, and the retail sector.

The manufacturing sector is carried out in the kitchens of restaurants, bars, canteens or other types of food service establishments, in confectionery - pastry laboratories, in factories for culinary products, or in culinary production complexes.

The distribution sector include lounges (dining rooms) of restaurants, bars, canteens or other types of food service establishments, the selling stands from specialized shops, malls, super markets, etc. as well as distribution networks of profile products for home delivery.

Based on the way of serving products we can distinguish:

- direct food (when the product is consumed on the spot, in a specially arranged lounge);
- transit food (when the product is consumed "on the fly" during the daily activities);
- food at home (when the product is consumed at the client's doorstep, at work, or in another location, after purchasing goods from specialized booths or after a delivery at home).

Based on the customer's nature, food services are as follows:

- general food (for meals taken by customers during their free time, regular or occasional, aimed at the need for everyday meals, the meals from the tourist's travels, as well as those caused by events);
- collective food (aimed at serving food for groups of people with common activities: for the sick people in hospitals, for the military - soldiers or officers - from military units, for the elderly in nursing homes, for children, pupils or students in schools, etc.).

Lately, the term "restaurant industry", used in place of the phrase "food service", hardly makes its way against the opposition of conservatives in

the field. According to the dictionary, “restaurant industry” has several meanings, depending on the area we refer to:

- in history: it signifies that period in the history of states, characterized by restoring the throne to dynasties that were removed following revolutions, coups, etc.;

- in art: a French style of art, characterized by curved lines, rounded and graceful ornaments, which maintain inspiration from ancient art, however which under the influence of romanticism, shows interest in Gothic and Renaissance styles as well;

- gastronomy: a recent word, used more frequently in literature instead of the term “food service”, for the domain of activity that includes culinary production (culinary, pastry and confectionery preparation) and loosening (loosening nu e bine, dar nu stiu sigur la ce te referi, la servire? Daca te referi la servire atunci e “and its serving” in loc de “and loosening”) as well as the beverages (serving for use on site or delivery order, outside the location), activity held under certain specialized business units (from the French restauration).

Analyzing in depth the general sense (or the majority) given in the Romanian language to these phrases, it is possible to differentiate them. Thus, the largest scope of coverage is held by the food service, that covers the specialized units of the type: restaurant (all types), bar, fast - food,

coffee, tea, confectionery, bakery, dining room (social, school, student, hospital, mess hall), stands selling culinary products, beverages and semi-culinary preparations, some sectors, with outlets for factories of culinary products and semi-prepared meals, etc.

“The restaurant industry” through the inner essence of meaning, covers only specialized establishments of the following type: restaurant (all types), bar, fast - food, coffee, tea, pastry and confectionery, etc., having a high share in the tourist industry. Therefore, it is recommended for the tourism sector to use the term “restaurant industry” instead of “food service”.

Graphically, the theory set out above is shown in Figure 2.1.

3. Agri-tourism - tourism form included in rural tourism?

Agritourism is a form of tourism that, through its activities, uses the economic potential of local households (farms), by developing hosting services and services that capitalize on products obtained by self holding (sau exploitation) or holdings from the area.

Fig.2.1 Overlap areas between food service and restaurant industry

The relationship between rural tourism and other forms of tourism in rural areas is particularly important, because it sets the correlation of natural, human, economic and social parameters, in order to ensure all the factors that lead to the growth of the tourism phenomenon, and to the sustainable development in the rural area.

Linking rural tourism - agro-tourism - ecotourism - tourism in natural areas is summarized in Figure 3.1.

Fig.3.1 The overlap of different types of tourism, with rural areas

Conclusions

-Were analyzed in detail plant extracts (volatile oils) to identify active substances used in encapsulation experiments, through specific methods in accordance with the European Pharmacopoeia edition in use, chromatographic techniques: GC-MS (Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry) and HPLC (High Pressure Performance Liquid Chromatography);

-From the obtained results was selected eucalyptus volatile oil as Chemical Complex Structure, which has the role of natural repellent of ticks.

-In The future will be tested both on tick repellent optimal doses that must be encapsulated.

-The most important parameter for multifunctional textile treatment is the sustainability of repeated washing and extended storage.

Classic rural tourism is the only form of tourism incorporated in its entirety in the rural tourism. Other forms of tourism discussed overlap more or less with the rural tourism (in descending order: agritourism (70 ... 75%), ecotourism (30 ... 35%), tourism in natural areas (5 ... 10%) [3].

This parameter will be tested to compare the effect of repellency for different variants of microcapsules containing the active product with quick release repellent agent.

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STUDY ON CALORIFIC VALUE TO WOOD PELLETS

GH.C. SPIRCHEZ, A. LUNGULEASA, L. GACEU, T. GRIU

Abstract: Biomass in the form of wood, I have been and will, remain a combustible material remained deep in people's consciousness, a material that can provide energy needs of the population at a reduced price. The importance of using woody biomass result from that is part of the renewable resource of energy. Woody biomass is a source of neutral combustible in terms of carbon dioxide emissions. Worldwide, it highlights concerns in using biomass for energy purposes. Romania has a potential of 60% in the production of energy from existing biomass sources. Romania has an area of 6300 ha, which represents 27% of the existing territory.

Keywords: biomass, calorimeter bomb, gross calorific, wood pellets

1. Introduction

Biomass resources are the raw material resulting from woodworking, agriculture, municipal waste and animal manure. Romania is a country which has great potential in the field of obtaining biomass energy source.

Wood has a high power capacity and can be provided at much lower price compared to fossil fuels each consumer. The importance of wood calorific value analysis and in general of the whole called biomass could change the vision of logging and exploitation rights.

Increasing continuous development of human society and continued growth in energy demand has led to new insights in manufacturing and energy needs global energy market, namely providing material inexhaustible energy.

Heat treatment or torrefaction of biomass is a promising method for the future and to promote biomass energy material with value close to those of fossil fuels.

In Romania in 2010 was used for agriculture and forestry in an area of 229973 km² of which was forest land area of 4,7%.

This data highlights once more the large amount of forest material that currently exists across the European Union and worldwide.

After Tudora (2009) notion of biomass describe in very broad and complex that includes plant biomass, animal biomass, microbial biomass, aquatic biomass. The recent decades the term is commonly used biomass energy. We have noticed that biomass is constantly growing. This growth materializes in the direction of using biomass and products result from the processing of biomass, biogas separated in materials processing and biofuel.

Biomass is divided into 4 categories described in EN 14961-1 norm SR:

- forest production: wood, wood cutting waste, sawdust, trees, shrubs, wood chips, bark of tree resulting from the operation and cleaning;
- waste from agricultural production, grain waste, municipal organic waste;
- energy grain: starch crops (maize, wheat and barley), crops of sugar (sugarbeet and sugar beet), oilseeds (sunflower, soya, safflower), forage crops (grass, lucerne, clover);
- aquatic plants (herbs water, water hyacinth, algae, reed, rush).

The pellets are obtained by mechanical processing of the wood as a result the products of small size. Pellets are solid fuels with a low moisture content (up to 12%) obtained from sawdust, wood chips, bark of trees, wood shavings, wood-powder (Lunguleasa, 2009).

Wood pellets are clean fuels with low carbon dioxide emissions. Energetic pellets capacity is 19700 KJ/Kg at moisture content of 0% (Berkesy 2011). In literature it is estimated that the energy potential of biomass in 2050 will reach 1500 EJ/year.

Forest and agricultural biomass will provide an annual capacity of 50-150EJ/year (Gaddonneix, 2010).

Evaluation calorific value to wood pellets

The term calorific power is issued by the bodies was first used by Kepler, and in the scientific literature by Thomas Young. Determination of calorific wood is similar to that of coal (as well as solid fuel). Determination of calorific wood is similar to that of coal (as well as solid fuel) and with few changes from the liquid fuels (gasoline)

or gaseous (biogas). To plant used to determine the calorific value of wood biomass combustion calorimeter was explosive XRY-1C type, produced by Schanghai Changji Geological Instrument Co of China (fig.1).

Calorimeter bomb is very usual for determining calorific wood.

Fig. 1 Calorimeter bomb

Preparing the timber for testing consists in taking a small part (0,6-0,8 grams) of whole material. Preparation for the test plant refers to verification of water in the calorimeter. Test sample binds to the cotton thread and put in the bomb crucible 3. Work diagram is presented in figure 2.

Fig. 2. Work diagram

Before making the actual attempt is made bomb calorimeter with benzoic acid. Calorific

value of wood varies between 15480-19440 KJ/Kg depending on the species and moisture content of the material used as solid fuel. To determine gross calorific using relationship:

$$PCS = k (tf-ti/ml) - qs - qb \text{ (KJ/Kg);}$$

where:

k- calorimetric coefficient (KJ/Kg); tf- finale temperature; ti- initiale temperature; ml- wood mass;

Calorific value of wood calorific is determined based on relation:

$$PCI = PCS - 6 (U + 9h) \text{ (KJ/Kg);}$$

where:

PCS- gross calorific power; U- wood humidity; h- hydrogen.

Nichelina thread binds 4 sample and cotton thread, then position the protection cover 5. The crucible is linked to the bomb calorimeter cover 6 by the electrodes 7 and 8.

By screwing the lid engages bomb 11 through the opening 12 introducing oxygen cylinder in 30 atmospheres. The test contains three distinct periods (fig.3).

Fig. 3 Three distinct period at calorimeter bomb

The three distinct periods are:

- initial period aims to assess variations in temperature of the water in the bowl calorimetry due to heat exchange with the outside before firing;
- the main period begins with ignition proof and has consequent increase water temperature in the calorimeter vessel;
- final period aims at determining the average water temperature variation in calorimeter vessel.

For oak pellets gross calorific value is 19007 KJ/Kg and net calorific value is 18748 KJ/Kg.

Conclusions

The advantages of using the facility for determining the calorific value of the pellets are:

- existing software eases the laboratory calculations;
- providing the burning time of the sample by the computer program.

Biomass has played an important role in providing energy from the beginning of civilization and still plays an important role in the economics of developing countries.

Today biomass has a new global vision.

The material obtained from biomass produces a large amount of energy that can be available to any consumer.

Burning woody biomass is an ecological process, but indispensable human activity thanks to the thermal energy it produces.

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RESEARCH OPPORTUNITIES FOR SOLAR ENERGY USE IN A HOTEL COMPLEX AREA OF AN ISOLATED MOUNTAIN

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Abstract: This paper addresses the problem of reducing the energy consumption of conventional sources, due to the use of solar energy. The hotel complexes in isolated mountain areas leverages solar energy using photovoltaic collectors and solar collectors consequential for domestic hot water. Requirements panels and solar collectors is dependent on the capacity of the hotel complex and the services offered to tourists. It notes the importance of the hotel complex orientation to the sun and the seasons with maximum requests for its services.

Keywords: resort, mountain area, solar energy.

1. Introduction

Resorts up in isolated mountain areas are increasingly sought after by tourists from Romania for indicative of the conditions in which they are located: quiet, clean natural environment, the opportunity for winter sports and hiking trails etc.

Also, the resorts is designed for carrying out scientific or business promotion.

Comfort requirements imposed on such units is spread over a wider range, starting with the specific minimum cottages and ending with 5 star hotels, the services are complex and at the highest level.

The increasing use of renewable energy is favorable preserve the environment (sustainable development), but also to

achieve energy independence of these business units

Experimental data on the characteristics of solar energy coming from the mountains in Brasov County. Also considered solar technical equipment to be used in a hotel unit of this type are the next generation in terms of efficiency and reliability

2. Materials and metods

Solar potential in Romania is represented by average energy density of incident solar radiation, horizontally exceeding 1000 kWh/m²/year.

In Romania have identified several geographic areas with differentiated level of energy flow recorded, and the regime of geographical

distribution, solar energy potential shows that more than half of Romania's area benefits from a flow annual average of 1000 kWh / m² / year.

Fig.1 shows the map of solar radiation in Romania

Using solar energy for hot water supply has proved to be a perfectly viable solution. The operating principle of heating water system with solar energy is simple and the technology is already well known and reliable. Solar energy is clean, inexhaustible, clean and safe.

This facilitates saving energy resources, without producing waste or emit polluting gases, such as carbon dioxide.

Above pollution problems and the impact of greenhouse gases, hot water supply represents a considerable part of the energy bill of buildings, which can be reduced by using solar energy.

Solar energy can be used in order to meet energy needs in isolated geographic areas or with limited access to power grid.

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Collecting solar energy:

Direct capture of solar energy involves artificial means, called solar collectors, which are designed to capture the energy, focus sometimes by direct sunlight.

Energy once captured is used in thermal processes, photoelectric or photovoltaic. In thermal processes, solar energy is used to heat a gas or a liquid, which is then stored or distributed. The photovoltaic solar energy is converted directly into electricity without the use of mechanical devices intermediate.

Solar collector is the essential element of a solar plant that converts radiant energy into another form, useful energy.

Solar collector works by heating a liquid (usually water, oil, air or glicoolul) which then releases the heat thermal system.

Flat solar collectors

Solar collectors have top flat sheet of glass high transmissivity and the inner side of aluminum foil, with a very good insulation (vacuum). Inside the panel there copper pipe through which a heat carrier glycol. Collectors are flat, the surface area of solar collectors that absorb a certain amount of solar radiation is the same as the surface area that intercepts the amount of solar radiation. They have the following main advantages:

- Uses both direct sunlight and diffuse;
- Have a simple construction;
- Involves easy maintenance.

The field of application of these probes is at the moderate temperatures of the order of 100 ° C above the ambient temperature.

After absorbing the surface, radiation sensors without concentration may be planar, cylindrical, semicircular, etc. In most cases, the absorbent surface is flat (or nearly flat) and respective collectors are called simply "flat collectors".

In the figure below are some variants of installation of pipes on the flat surface absorbing.

Fig 2. Types of pipe on flat surface absorbent collector

Figure 2 presents two versions of installer wings copper or aluminum with copper pipe, hot water circulation through the panel forced circulation (pump) or thermosiphon. 10x0,5mm copper pipe has dimensions and welded with laser technology on board mirqtherm as in the figure below, thereby ensuring a very good heat transfer between the two elements.

The next figure shows the components of a solar collector flat

Fig 3. The components of a solar collector flat
[www.windupbattery.com]

The frequently used flat collector panels include a housing isolated with a transparent covering of the solar radiation absorber. The absorber is generally a sheeting of dark copper, with a special coating, which absorbs heat and transmits it to a heat transfer fluid. The heated fluid is transported towards the tank by pipes.

The cost of manufacture of the flat collectors is relatively low, but they suffer from more heat loss than vacuum collectors. In comparison with vacuum collectors, the same power consumption requires a larger surface of collectors.

Vacuum tube solar collectors

This type of solar collector is used in complex solar systems for domestic hot water all year round and for additional contribution from domestic-heating

Vacuum tube is composed of conductive tubes operates on thermal (evaporative condensing)

Fig. 4. Schematic of a vacuum tube collector
[www.wiessmann.com]

These collectors are made of borosilicate glass tubing with a thickness of 1.6 mm, which provides high mechanical strength (hail), and the absorbent is made of the "black nickel", which provides an absorption coefficient $a = 92$ e-emission% and 8%, with a good $a / e = 11.5$.

Inside the tubes is evacuated (5.10⁻³Pa) and heat transfer medium can reach out of the panel, temperatures max 210 ° C, which provides power 1000 W / m², being from this point of view some of the best solar collectors plane, but their cost price is three times higher than conventional solar collectors, which provides power between 450 ... 550 W / m². The return on these types of collector is so high due to the use very effectively to diffuse radiation of the sun and unnecessary collector orientation depending on the angle of incidence of the rays.

Solar radiation captured by solar collectors depends on their surface, such as the surface of solar collectors is higher the amount of energy captured and grow.

In figure 5 shows the distribution of solar radiation on the surfaces of the two types of solar collectors, vacuum tube solar collectors that flat plane

Fig. 4. Distribution of solar radiation flat plate collectors and vacuum tube collectors

In the above figure can be seen the difference between the surfaces of the two types of solar collectors, vacuum tube solar collector thus have an area greater absorption of solar radiation than flat solar collectors.

The location solar collectors

When installing solar collectors will consider compliance with principles such as: solar collector will always be oriented on south. The title must be as short possible. If necessary, a subtitle is provided.

Fig. 5. The orientation of solar collectors

- The angle of inclination of the collector from the horizontal is chosen according to:
 - Geographic latitude of the locality;
 - The conditions of the environment (pollution degree, the degree of shading plantations and construction, etc.).
- Solar collector can be mounted on the roof or on a metal frame type for the roof terraces.

3. Methods

Determination of surface collecting solar energy unit hotel.

The surface of solar power (S_p)

$$S_p = \frac{Q_z}{q_r \cdot \eta \cdot \eta_s} \quad (1)$$

$$S_p = \frac{140000}{6000 \cdot 0,5 \cdot 0,8} = 58,3m^2$$

$$Q_z = N_p \cdot q_p \cdot (t_e - t_i) \quad (2)$$

$$Q_z = 50 \cdot 70 \cdot (50 - 10) = 140000 \text{ kcal/zi}$$

Q_z – daily flow of heat,

N_p – the number of people who prepare hot water, N_p – 50 people

t_e – hot water temperature at out of the installation; $t_e = 50^{\circ}C$.

t_i – cold water temperature before entering the unit; $t_i = 10^{\circ}C$.

q_r – daily solar radiation density;

$$q_r = 6000 \text{ Kcal} / \text{zi} \cdot \text{m}^2$$

η – plant efficiency; $\eta = 0,5$

η_s – battery thermal transmission efficiency.

$$\eta_s = 0,8$$

To cover the hot water needs per unit of hotel with a capacity of 50 people are required 30 solar collectors, a solar collector area is 2 square meters

Solar energy is an inexhaustible source of energy, so using specific technology can achieve

remarkable results for the supply of heating domestic hot water to the hotels in the mountain areas. Geographic data of our country are favorable for the use of solar energy.

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SIMULATION FLOW ANALYSIS OF SAFETY OVERFLOW VALVE

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Abstract: *An approach for simulation fluid analysis of safety overflow valve is presented. This valve used in devices on food industry. The simulation fluid analysis are carried into by 3D geometrical model of assembly units, theoretical dependences and the limiting conditions for working pressure and fluid rheology indexes for chocolate mass. Also is created demo model for presentation of speed distribution of flow in the valve. Developed methodology for animation simulation analysis in education. The results could be used for training of students master degree and postgraduates in this field of CAD design.*

Keywords: *simulation, analysis, fluid, safety, overflow, valve, food industry, design, education, students.*

1. Introduction

Regarding the contemporary economical and marketing conditions, the companies strive to use innovative technologies in order to preserve competitiveness since the requirements of the market grow incessantly.

For the purpose of being responsive to these challenges, the companies strive to found usage of contemporary technologies for parallel engineering [1,2].

One of the essential stages within the process of computer-aided designing of assembled units is simulation of motion and animation.

The most frequently used means are the frequency analysis [11] of rolling elements and revision of their condition of exploitation [8,10]. All of these apply to machines, devices and technologies from the food industry for the purpose of provision of biological products.

To this end, it is advisable to perform simulative, fluidity analysis by the use of database and an appropriate software.

This necessitates that the issues should be solved by team-based work as the team should consist in various specialists and the work should include the technology of PLM.

Therefore, all these circumstances are the grounds to discuss the necessity of skills and knowledge of the engineers as they should match the requirements for team-based work at the companies which use high-end manufacture technologies [4,5].

All this is exceptionally relevant for the purpose of training of students and PhD students that are educated in our universities which study the procedures of designing and manufacture of technical products [9].

The goal of our present work is to research the behavior of a certain type of fluid throughout the process of hydro-mechanical designing of a device as it is to be performed by the use of a computer-aided simulation within the scope of a working process at the mode of standard and working pressure.

The main tasks are following:

- > developing a three-dimensional geometric model of the assembled unit - safety overflow valve;

- > generating a library a database to determine the pressure distribution and the velocity field in the valve holder;

- > created demo model for presentation of speed distribution of flow in the valve;

- > determination of the force upon the valve holder depending on the debit of the overflow;

- > determination of the size of opening of the valve depending on the nominal debit of the overflow;

- > determination of the pressure at the inlet depending on the scale of opening of the valve at a nominal value of the debit.

The object of research is a 'Protective overflow valve', a model RV4 which is to be utilized with a rotor pump Johnson at facilities of The Food Industry (shown on Fig.1).

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Fig. 1. Internal gear pump

The purpose of the valve is to protect the pump from malfunction at the moment when pressure exceeds its working level as it could vary from 1 to 4 Bara while the standard (nominal) pressure is at the rate of 5 Bara.

In order to perform a simulative, fluidity analysis, one has to use the 3D geometrical model of an assembled unit as it's shown on Fig.2. as one should use the Flow Simulation module of the Solid Works software [14].

Fig.2 Three dimensional geometrical model

2. Input Database:

Fluid debit $Q = 2 \text{ m}^3 \text{ h}^{-1} = 0,000555555 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ и fluid pressure $p = 5 \text{ Bara} = (72.5 \text{ N} \cdot \text{m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}) = 500\,000 \text{ Pa}$.

Surface of the input and the output section: вход – $S_1 = 0,56 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ m}^2$ и изход- $S_2 = 0,9 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ m}^2$;

Fluid velocity at the inlet - $v = 1 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$; at the outlet - $v = 0,62 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$; Density of the fluid ρ : for chocolate $1325 \text{ kg} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$ (13000 Nm^{-3}); Axial

displacement of the holder at the opening phase of the valve is of $X = 0..7 \text{ mm}$, as $X_{\text{max}} = 7 \text{ mm}$.

The model of viscosity is that one of Hershel Burkley's [7] as it is described by the dependence of: $\gamma = 1050 + \mu$, as γ is the rate of deformation. Thermo technical indexes have the following values: inherent heat capacity $c = 1,83 \text{ kJ/kgK}$; heat conductivity $0,106 \text{ W/mK}$.

3. Simulation based analysis of the assembled unit

After the conduct of the simulative, fluidity analysis, an inner task has been solved as it refers to a tin flow of a type of non - Newtonian fluid which runs through the valve. It's assumed that the fluid does not exchange heat with the ambience through the material of the valve. The roughness of the inner material of the object has been measured as $R_z = 10 \mu\text{m}$.

The thermo dynamical, velocity and the turbulent parameters are assumed as supposition. In order to obtain the exact solution, a sixth stage of resolution of the net is assumed as the settings for minimum size of the looseness, and the minimum thickness of the material are to be introduced manually.

The marginal conditions have been presented in Fig.2.

The goals of the project are obtaining of the fields of pressure and the fields of velocity, the point lines of the flow between the inlet and the outlet of the valve as well as the axial force on the closing.

The task has been solved by the use of a six-core personal computer as the cores work in parallel mode.

4. Results obtained from the flow simulation

Overall, this task shows stability and similarity in its course of solving. The distribution of the forces within the longitudinal section is shown on Fig.5, whereas the static pressure is shown on Fig.4. The lines of current are shown on Fig.4. It is most apparent that the current does not have rolling motion before it enters the valve since the input section is larger than the one of the model (1,5 from the diameter of the middle, transitional section) as the flow appropriates ascertained character before it gets into the zone of interference.

The distribution of pressure and velocity according to an imposed line that goes from the inlet to the outlet is shown on Fig.7 and Fig.8. The results that concern the distribution of pressure before the closing of the valve are to be

used for the purpose of calculation of the value of the axial force $\cdot zF$

Fig.3 Imposed line of the flow

Fig.4 Field of pressure

Fig.5 Field of velocity

Fig.6 Point lines

Fig.7 Velocity along the length of the imposed line at the opening of h=7mm

Fig.8 Pressure along the length of the imposed line at the opening of h=3mm

Fig.9 Shifting of the axial force upon the closing depending on the opening phase of the valve

5. Methodology for animation simulation analysis in education

The proposal simulation analysis is necessary for training of students from the professional qualification of 'General Engineering', specialty "Industrial Engineering", Master degree in subject 'Expert systems'.

This proposition has been based on the accumulated experience and on the curricular process of development of 3D models and mechanical products [3]. It also stems from the motivation of the students who study a technical subject that involves CAD systems throughout the process of designing.

For this purpose should be used methodology that includes certain data, search results, discussion about the investigation and conclusion. Determination the behavior of the fluid in the valve by means of the following parameters: field and speed of pressure as a function of the viscosity of the fluid.

6. Database for the purpose of simulation analysis

6.1 Given:

- > Volumetric flow [m.h-1];
- > Standard and working pressure, [Bar];
- > Viscosity of flow (non-Newtonian flow) [$\mu\text{Pa.s}$].

6.2 Analysis and solutions:

- > Determination the behavior of the fluid in the valve by means of the following parameters: field and velocity of pressure as a function of the viscosity of the fluid [6,7];

- > The graphic dependence on the distribution of velocity along the length of the specified line;
- > Analysis of the results and decision creative decisions from the perspective the design of high-tech and economically viable products [12,13].

Finally the students must to know the meaning the usefulness from simulation analysis to verify created by them three-dimensional computer models in the design process.

Conclusion

The example demonstrates the capabilities of Flow Simulation concerning solutions of tasks related to non-rotating objects. On the basis of the characteristics of the axial force upon the closing (fig.9), one can see that it is non-linear as this corresponds to the experimentally obtained characteristics which are presented in the relevant filed of literature. Taking into account the complexity of the geometry, the presence of narrow canals, the opportunity to obtain credible prognosis about the characteristics of the product becomes a positive fact.

Developed methodology for animation simulation analysis in education.

The results could be used for training of students master degree and postgraduates in this field of CAD design. Also for the Study of hydraulic systems and gas equipment by means of simulation analysis in the process of their design.

This results will improve the requirements of the European Credit System. (ECTS) that serves for the purpose of realization of mobility via the

Central European Education Program System which has been established between the Technical University of Sofia, University of Ruse and the universities abroad.

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STUDY REGARDING THE MANAGEMENT MECHANISMS FOR TOURISTIC INTEGRATION OF OLTINA PLATEAU FROM SOUTHERN DOBROGEA

M. POPESCU* R. GRUIA**

Abstract: Located in South-Western Dobrogea, the Oltina Plateau has a diverse natural and cultural heritage, offered by contrast between environmental factors with activities and traditions of the local population. The purpose of this paper is to define the touristic specific and to identify solutions for socio-economic efficiency by integration in agri-touristic circuit to the sustainable development of local communities in this area, predominantly rural. The research methodology consisted in bibliographic documentation, field research to catalogue the resources with valuable touristic potential and their mapping, and identification of feasible agri-touristic programs based on sustainable management. There are analyzed the contrasting territorial landscapes determined by relief, Danube, lakes, natural protected areas, rural settlements with cultural resources and specific socio-economic activities. The touristic potential of this area resulting from the traditional farming activities associated with the presence of sights of cultural, historical, religious interest, and multicultural local traditions. Data processing outlines an integration model of villages in touristic routes with diverse themes and programs: cultural tourism, religious tourism, ecotourism, wine tourism, gastronomy tourism, api-tourism, fishery tourism and bird watching.

Keywords: management, optimization, plateau, sustainability, tourism

1. Introduction

The Oltina Plateau is situated in South-Western part of Southern Dobrogea, between Danube River (W-NW), the border with Bulgaria (S), the Medgidia Plateau (N), and the Cobadin - Negru Vodă Plateau (E-NE). The studied region covers an area of 1,254 square kilometers, a population of 31,621 inhabitants, it has a diverse natural and cultural heritage, offered by contrast between environmental factors with activities and traditions of the local population [3,11].

It is known as the efficient management of territorial landscape [5,7] contributes to sustainable economic development of the respectively area. In this context, the integrated management of rural tourism is an important factor contributing to the sustainable development of tourism [7,8] in the Oltina Plateau, as a territorial subsystem of Southern Dobrogea. Offering the support development of agri-tourism, it will sustain the development of local communities, as component of the territorial system [19].

Specific activities of agri-tourism can boost the economy of villages [1,6,10,13], can contribute to upgrading the infrastructure, can attract investors, if the residents of the rural area takes a favorable attitude, to be perceived correctly by tourists, who prefer this type of tourism, and whether the local authorities are involved enough in development of this profitable economic activity.

The **overall objective** of this paper is to define the touristic specific, the territorial diagnosis and identifying solutions to the social-economic efficiency, through the integration into agri-touristic circuit to the sustainable development of local communities in this area, predominantly rural.

The **specific objectives** are related to: the identification, structuring and optimization of touristic resources linked to the traditional activities of local population to emphasize the polyvalence and increasing of touristic effectiveness from research area.

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2. Material and Method

In order to the inventory of touristic resources from Oltina Plateau, the research methodology is represented by bibliographic and cartographic documentation, field research, to identify the managerial mechanisms necessary to integration of this territorial system in the touristic circuit [2,9]: building an instrument of cooperation or partnership between local authorities; identify villages where can be implemented projects for touristic development; solutions for development of infrastructure; identifying strategies for cooperation and dialogue between the local population, authorities and experts or other possible stakeholders; training of open mentality oriented to sustainable rural tourism; awareness of the role of tourism as an “engine” of medium and long-term local development [4,15,18].

The analysis of the spatial distribution of touristic resources in territorial system of Oltina Plateau, linking them with local traditions and activities, processing of cartographic [16,20] and statistical information, the mapping will emphasize the potential networks and nodes to

optimization of routes and agri-touristic programs based on sustainable management.

3. Results and discussions

The Southern Dobrogea region, and Oltina Plateau, its South-Western part, belongs of Pre-Balkan Platform with a pleated foundation of green schists, which were deposited Cretaceous and Tertiary limestone and sandstone rocks.

The relief consists of two individualized levels along Danube: the Danube’s Dobrogea of South-West, consisting of Levantine terrace, and in Southern, the Oltina Plateau in fact, with an altitude over 170 m (fig. 1) [11].

This area is a part of continental-temperate climate, with average annual temperatures of 10-11°C and rainfall of 400-450 mm annually.

The vegetation is typical to steppe and forest-steppe zone, developed on white soils, typical of this region, and therefore the natural vegetation has been replaced by agricultural crops on large areas [11].

Fig. 1 Physical Map of Oltina Plateau

This region belongs hydrographic basin of the Danube with fluvial lakes and short rivers (fig. 1) [11].

The land use (fig. 2) is represented by 125,364 ha, of which: 8,895 ha - lakes and wetlands; 18,268 ha - forest areas; 90,802 ha - agricultural lands (possible resources as support for agri-

tourism) that includes: 82% arable land (especially for cereal and industrial crops), 12% grass-lands (for livestock), 5% vinecrops (4,317 ha, Ostrov Vineyard), 1% orchards (683 ha, predominantly apricot, peach) [19].

Fig. 2 Land Use Map of Oltina Plateau

The population of Oltina Plateau territorial system of 31,621 inhabitants is grouped into **10 administrativ-territorial units (ATU)**: 1 town (Băneasa) and 9 communes (Adamclisi, Aliman,

Deleni, Ion Corvin, Lipnița, Oltina, Ostrov, Peștera, Rasova), which together with component villages totaling localities, creating a predominantly rural area - 82% (fig. 3) [19].

Fig. 3 Administrative Map of Oltina Plateau

Infrastructure of roads communication (fig. 4) which provides the access to agri-touristic resources consists 66 km of national roads (Ostrov - Adamclisi - Constanța), 64 km of

county roads (Ion Corvin - Cernavodă, Băneasa - Oltina), 256 km of local roads connecting other villages to each other and the main roads that cross the tableland.

Fig. 4 Road Map of Oltina Plateau

In the Oltina Plateau stands out the contrasting territorial landscapes determined by relief, Danube, lakes, natural protected areas, rural settlements with cultural resources and specific socio-economic activities. The touristic potential of this area resulting from the traditional farming activities (viticulture, fruit growing, fish breeding, beekeeping or sheep breeding) [3,12,17] associated with the presence of sights of cultural, historical, religious interest, and multicultural local traditions. Data processing outlines an integration model of villages in

touristic routes with diverse themes and programs: cultural tourism, religious tourism, wine and gastronomy tourism, api-tourism, fishery and bird-watching tourism, ecotourism.

Types of natural touristic resources are: Danube and fluvial lakes (*Bugeac, Oltina-Iortmac, Vederoasa, Dunăreni*), forest areas (*Tălășman, Cetate, Bratca*), protected areas (*Canaraua Fetii Forest, Esechioi Forest, Aliman Fossil Point, Bugeac, Oltina-Iortmac, Vederoasa, Dunăreni Lake Birds Area*) (fig. 5) [11].

Fig. 5 Natural Touristic Resources of Oltina Plateau

The natural touristic resources **grouped by ATU** are: *Esechioi* Forest, *Bugeac* Lake, the Right Branch of *Danube* (**Ostrov**), the Right Branch of *Danube* (**Lipnița**), *Oltina-Iortmac* Lake, *Bratca* and *Cetate* Forests, the Right Branch of *Danube*, „*Iepurașului*” Island (**Oltina**), „*Canaraua Fetii*” Forest (**Băneasa**), „*Mihai Eminescu*” Spring, closer to „*Sf. Andrei*” Cave (**Ion Corvin**), *Tălășman* Forest (**Adamclisi**), *Aliman* Fossil Point, *Vederoasa* Lake, *Dunăreni* Lake, the Right Branch of *Danube* (**Aliman**), the Right Branch of *Danube*, „*Lung*” Island (**Rasova**).

Types of cultural touristic resources are: „*Tropaeum Traiani*”, *Durustorum*, *Altinum*, *Sacidava*, „*Păciul lui Soare*” (historical sights), *Dervent*, „*Sf. Andrei*” Cave, *Strunga*, *Lipnița*,

„*Sf. Filip*” (monasteries), *viticulture*, *fruit growing*, *fish breeding*, *beekeeping* or *sheep breeding* (traditional agricultural activities), local traditions and customs, specific holidays (fig. 6).

The cultural touristic resources **grouped by ATU** are: „*Dervent*” Monastery and „*Izvorul Tămăduirii*” Spring, „*Păciul lui Soare*” Island, *Durustorum* Fortress (**Ostrov**), *Strunga* Hermitage, *Lipnița* Monastery (**Lipnița**), *Altinum* Fortress, Stone Fountain from XIX-th Century (**Oltina**), Roman settlement, *Getian* Cemetery (**Băneasa**), „*Sf. Andrei*” Cave and Monastery (**Ion Corvin**), „*Sf. Filip*” Monastery, „*Tropaeum Traiani*” Museum and Monument (**Adamclisi**), *Sacidava* Fortress (**Aliman**) [14].

Fig. 6 Cultural Touristic Resources of Oltina Plateau

The traditional agricultural activities are: **beekeeping** (Oltina, Băneasa, Ion Corvin, Lipnița) [12], **pisciculture** and **viticulture** (Ostrov, Lipnița, Oltina, Aliman, Rasova) [17], **fruit-growing** (Ostrov, Lipnița, Băneasa, Ion Corvin, Adamclisi, Peștera), **pisciculture** (Ostrov, Oltina, Adamclisi, Rasova).

Figure 7 shows the proposed touristic routes with polyvalent potential from Oltina Plateau, which are described in table 1.

Proposals for an efficiency agri-touristic management in Oltina Plateau:

Organizing a *Local Center of Promotion and Information for Tourism*, information points and info-kiosks for tourists in potential villages

(Ostrov, Adamclisi), and clear signaling of sights on thematic itinerary;

Arranging the accommodations, food, sports and leisure under specific conditions, specific resources, with principles of tourism planning and sustainable development indicators;

Residents, small businesses and local community must be interested to create an association to promote *Local Touristic Products* to be included in *Thematic Touristic Package*: cultural and religious tourism, wine and gastronomy tourism, api-tourism, fishery tourism, bird watching and ecotourism.

Table 1 Touristic Routes with polyvalent potential from Oltina Plateau

Nr. crt.	Type of Touristic Route	Description of Route
1	Ecotouristic Route	Ostrov (Esechio Forest, Bugeac Lake Bird Area) - Băneasa ("Canaraua Fetii" Forest) - Oltina (Oltina Lake Bird Area, Bratca and Cetate Forests) - Aliman (Aliman Fossil Point, Vederoasa Lake Bird Area) - Rasova
2	Cultural-religious Route	Ostrov („Dervent” Monastery and „Izvorul Tămăduirii” Spring) - Lipnița („Strunga” Hermitage, „Lipnița” Monastery) - Ion Corvin (“Sf. Andrei” Monastery and Cave, „Mihai Eminescu” Spring and Forest) - Adamclisi („Sf. Filip” Monastery)
3	Cultural-historic Routes	Ostrov („Păcuil lui Soare” Byzantine Fortress, „Durostorum” Fortress) - Băneasa (Archaeological sights, Roman Settlement, Getian Cemetery) - Adamclisi (“Tropaeum Traiani” Museum and Monument); Ion Corvin - Oltina („Altinum” Fortress, Stone Fountain from XIX-th Century) - Aliman ("Sacidava" Fortress)
4-5	Wine and Gastronomy Route with fish cuisine along Danube	Ostrov (Wine Cellar, Bugeac Lake) - Lipnița (Wine Cellar)- Oltina (Wine Cellar, Oltina-Iortmac Lake) - Aliman (Wine Cellar, Dunăreni Lake) - Rasova (Vederoasa Lake)
5	Beekeeping Route	Oltina - Băneasa - Ion Corvin (beekeeping producers)
6	Orchard Route	Ostrov - Lipnița - Oltina - Ion Corvin - Adamclisi - Peștera (fruit-growing resources)

Fig. 7 Touristic Routes of Oltina Plateau

Conclusions

1. Specific features with touristic polyvalent potential of territorial system Oltina Plateau are represented by Danube and fluvial lakes, protected areas, monasteries, historical sights, typical villages from Southern Dobrogea.

2. Oltina Plateau has original and diversified touristic resources, but are only partially valorized, a reason being lack of accommodation's infrastructure, excepting some possibilities at „Dervent” and „Sf. Andrei” Monasteries.

3. The touristic relevance of Oltina Plateau resulting from association of **traditional**

activities of local communities with other touristic resources, especially valorisation of vineyards and fisheries, as agri-touristic components, in the context of polyvalent touristic route proposed along Danube, these can contribute to sustainable socio-economic development in rural area of this region.

4. Developing on direction of natural and cultural touristic resources from Oltina Plateau reveal optimal conditions for building rural pensions in villages with touristic resources and **Guest houses**: with *beekeeping* specific (Ion Corvin), *orchards* specific (Peștera), *wine growing* specific (Adamclisi, Lipnița), *wine and fish growing* specific (Rasova, Aliman, Oltina), *polyvalent* specific (Ostrov - *monastic, fishing and wine tourism*).

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INFLUENCE OF PARAMETERS OF SUBCRITICAL WATER EXTRACTION OVER YIELD OF TARGET COMPONENTS FROM GRAPE POMACE

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Abstract: *The influence of parameters of extraction process of grape pomace (GP) by subcritical water (SCW) has been researched, the antioxidant activity of these extracts has been analyzed, the parameters of the process, ensuring the maximum yield of the desired component - dry and reducing substances, titratable acids, polyphenols have been determined.*

Extraction was performed in the temperature range T 100°C ÷ 1600C, pressure P = 12 MPa, exposure dose τ from 30 to 90 min., hydro ratio 1: 5 and 1:10. It has been found out that under the extraction of SCW dry extract yield is more than two times higher than by washing sweet pomace with hot water. Yield of polyphenolic compounds exceeds the amount of polyphenols obtained in the extraction with organic solvents and water at temperatures up to 60°C. The extracts obtained in the medium of SCW are characterized by high antioxidant activity. Yield of acids under extraction at temperatures (100-120 °C) of SCW is comparable with the number of acids in the original grape pomace.

Key words: *grape pomace, subcritical water, extraction, target component*

1. Introduction

Grapes (*Vitis vinifera* L.) are the largest fruit crop with a world production of more than 70 million tons per year. As a result of the processing of grapes up to 20% waste is produced. Secondary raw materials - SRM, which remain in the press after squeezing juice from fresh grapes or wine from fermented mash consists of ridges, grape skins, seeds and residual liquid (must, wine). [1]

Yield of pomace (with ridges) after using extruding machines is on average 13-15%, hydraulic presses - 17% and screw presses - 20-23%.

The individual components of the grapes are present approximately in unfermented pomace according to the following ratio: grape skins - 50%, ridges - 25% and 25% of the seed [2].

As to their chemical composition GP are a valuable raw material for extracting a variety of products, including tartaric acid [3, 4], tannins [5, 6], ethanol

[7], polyphenols [8,9], furfural [10] and other products [11]. It is necessary to emphasize the high antioxidant activity of GP extracts, suggesting to use them as natural antioxidants [12, 13].

In order to extract different target products (TP), including biologically active substances (BAS) conventional extraction methods are used: maceration, remaceration, percolation, repercolation [14, 15]. These methods are easy to perform, they do not require expensive equipment, however the active substances are not fully taken out (less than 90%), the process time is long, too high content of ballast substances in extracts, high labor intensity of the process, significant losses by diffusion and evaporation of extragent.

For the extraction of the target components (TC) water-ethanol mixture [16, 17], methanol [18, 19] and other organic solvents, sometimes with the use of

additional physical extraction techniques are used in the vast majority of cases. For example, a water-ethanol mixture with pulsed electric fields (PEF) [20, 21], ethanol with waves in a microwave oven [22], ultrasound [23, 24], high voltage electrical discharges (HVED) [25 26] and high hydrostatic pressure [27] are used.

The use of organic solvents is problematic due to their toxicity, high cost and problems with utilization. Thus phospho- and glycolipids, acylglycerols, esters of sterols and other esters which have biological activity almost completely disappear from the content of extracts.

In the last decade it was suggested to use solvents with a low boiling point - liquefied gases: carbon dioxide, propane, ammonia, methane, ethylene and some other compounds with low critical temperatures as extractants [28, 29]. However, carbon dioxide – one of the major greenhouse gases like methane, ozone, nitrogen oxides, as the gases that contain fluorine. Some fluid substances, such as methane, are toxic substances [30], some of them possess narcotic effects [31].

Thus, all of the above methods for extracting BAS from GP have certain drawbacks this fact emphasizes the relevance of the development of environmentally friendly methods of extracting the desired components from raw materials obtained as a result of processing of grapes.

For the extraction of biologically active compounds it is suggested to use subcritical water (SCW) [32-35].

Even small variations in temperature and pressure in SCW change all its physical and chemical properties: dielectric permeability, viscosity, specific heat capacity, diffusion coefficient and density. Water in these conditions behaves like a polar organic solvent.

The main advantages of SCW as a solvent are: a combination of the properties

of gases at high pressures (low viscosity, high diffusion coefficient) and liquids (high resolving ability); combination of negligibly small interfacial tension with low viscosity and high diffusion coefficient, which allows the SCW to penetrate into the porous medium more easily as compared with fluids; high sensitivity of the resolving ability of SCW to a change in pressure or temperature; ease of separation of SCW and dissolved substances at relieving pressure. These properties and the possibility of using the SCR as the solvent (reagent, catalyst) are related to its microstructure and characteristics of the processes occurring at the molecular level. The dependence of the resolving ability of SCW on the state parameters is largely due to the special nature and dynamics of hydrogen bonds (HB) [36, 37].

Hydrogen bonds largely determine the behavior of water and are a major cause of its significant differences from the other liquids. The nature of these highly anisotropic intermolecular interactions contributes to the manifestation of specific thermodynamic and structural properties of water, as well as the dynamic behavior that is unique in comparison with other substances. Properties of liquid water, by which such important processes as the dissolution of various substances and transport of protons are determined, are the result of the movement of molecules in a constantly changing grid structure of HB. [38]

High compressibility, which leads to significant changes in density with little change in pressure and a significant decrease in the dielectric constant from 80 under normal conditions, up to 6 at supercritical (SC) conditions allows non-polar compounds to be dissolved in the SC water [39].

Water is a non-toxic, non-flammable and inexpensive substance; it has easy division with the target products after

the completion of the process. Using SCW instead of organic solvents increases the environmental safety of production, as well as the purity of the products obtained, given their lack of traces of toxic organic solvents and impurities contained therein.

From the list of possible TC (target components) of extracting GP SCW, considering the use of extracted BAS in the food and pharmaceutical industries, this study addressed the following TC: dry and reducing agents, titrable acids, polyphenols.

Grape pomace is valuable because it is rich in lipophilic, polysaccharide and acidic complexes, contains a significant amount of phenolic substances. Polyphenol complex is represented by phenolic acids, flavonoids, tannins, proanthocyanidins, stilbenes.

Grape polyphenols that are concentrated in its skins, seeds and ridges of the bunch of grapes have hygienic and health properties, which are determined mainly by antioxidant, antimutagenic, antibacterial, P-vitaminic activity, i.e., have complex biological activity.

Polyphenols of grapes in native form are mainly flavonoids - poorly water-soluble substances. When this distribution in GP is: 12-20% in the skin of grapes, in a 1% in pulp, 60% in seeds, 19-24 in the ridges of bunch of grapes [7,8].

Numerous studies have found out that while creating biologically active products from grape pomace it is preferable to obtain the total polyphenols dissolved in the liquid phase.

Due to the fact that the flavonoids are poorly soluble in water in its normal condition when conventional extraction processes are used, the use of SCW will significantly increase the efficiency of the process [7, 8], since in subcritical condition water is experiencing larger changes than most other liquids - it turns into almost non-polar medium out of a polar liquid. At 200^oC the density of water drops to 0.8

g/ml, and under the critical temperature, it becomes miscible with both organic solvents and gases. The rate of diffusion increases and its oxidizing ability increases. These circumstances allow positioning of SCW as the most effective solvent, which should be used in designing the process of extracting polyphenols out of GP.

Since 60-70% of polyphenols is gallic acid, known for its antioxidant activity, calculation of analyzed polyphenolic compounds must be carried out according to gallic acid as a substance with a strong polyphenol structure.

GP polysaccharides, composed of the residues of corresponding monosaccharides including glucose, constitute up to 60% by weight of the dry GP, in this regard, to estimate the output of sugars it is necessary to determine yield of a dry extract according to the process parameters and reducing substances in terms of the equivalent amount of glucose.

The most valuable product obtained by complex processing of GP and yeast residuas is, other than ethyl alcohol, tartaric acid and its salts.

The acid indicator is an important indicator which characterizes the process of extraction including from the point of view of the formation of simple sugars from polysaccharides that makes it necessary to determine the total acidity of extracts.

Given the above mentioned, the purpose of the research was to determine the rational parameters of the extraction process of GP SCW which provides maximum yield of the target component (dry and reducing agents, titrable acids, polyphenols) and analysis of the antioxidant activity of extracts obtained.

II. Materials and methods.

2.1. Plant material

Moldova grape variety was purchased in late September in the retail network in

Donetsk (Ukraine) from the manufacturers - the Republic of Moldova. Moldova is table grape variety. The average weight of a bunch is up to 350 grams. The berry is big (2,5 x 1,9 cm), oval, dark purple, with a thick waxy coating. The skin is thick, dense and tough. The flesh is meaty and crispy.

2.2. Preparation of raw materials

Crushing of berries with peduncles was carried out on an industrial juice extractor to a moisture content of grape pomace - 55% [16]. Drying of original pomace at 75°C ± 2°C to constant weight was carried out in porcelain bowls placed in cabinet drier ТПЦ02 ТИІ-1 with occasional stirring. Residual moisture of pomace after drying was 4-7 (% abs.). The resulting agglomerates were crushed to fraction passing through a sieve with aperture of 3 mm.

Equipment used for the extraction of SCW is designed and manufactured in a Laboratory of Fluid Technologies of Donetsk National University of Economics and Trade named after M. Tugan-Baranovsky (DonNUET), Ukraine. The used ratio of raw material and extractant (water) was – hydro ratio - 1: 5 and 1:10. The temperature was varied from 100 to 160°C with step 10°C and maintained by pitch controller with an accuracy of ± 10°C. Dwell time - 30 min, 60 min and 90 min. Repetition of the experiments - three times.

The magnitude of the pressure $P=12$ MPa, which provided subcritical conditions and a high yield of extractable substances due to the destruction of cell membranes, was established on the basis of its thermodynamic properties described by differential equations of thermodynamics of International system of equations of 1997 (Formulation IF - 97) [42, 43].

2.3. Methods of assessing the yield of dry extract

The dry extract was determined by evaporation of a precise volume of extract (50 ml) at 105°C under vacuum on a rotary

evaporator ИП-1М with temperature controller ЭРА-М to a constant weight [44].

2.4. Methodology to evaluate the extraction of reducing substances

Determination of reducing substances was carried out by standard methods [45] using the Fehling's reagent.

2.4. Methodology to evaluate the extraction of polyphenols

Total content of polyphenolic compounds was determined at based on gallic acid using a the method of Folin-Ciocalteu (FC- method) [46] that represents the colorimetric determination of products red /ox reactions of phenolic extracts of analyte molecules without differentiation between gallic acid, mono -, di -, oligo- and polymeric compounds. The optical density of the solution was measured at a wavelength of 765 nm against the reference solution.

Total amount of polyphenol compounds in % based on gallic acid was calculated according to the formula:

$$X = \frac{D \cdot m_0 \cdot 25 \cdot 1 \cdot 100 \cdot 100 \cdot 100}{D_0 \cdot m \cdot a \cdot 100 \cdot 100 \cdot (100 - w)}, \quad (1)$$

where D - optical density of test solution;

D_0 - optical density of standard solution of gallic acid;

m - mass of extracted cake, g;

m_0 - mass in grams of gallic acid;

and a - aliquot solution in ml;

w - loss on drying of the extract in percentage.

An aliquot was adjusted so that the optical density was within 0,2-0,6.

2.3.2. Determination of active acidity of extracts

Active acidity was determined in terms of the equivalent amount of tartaric acid. Determination of titratable acidity was

carried out by potentiometric titration performed with phenolphthalein as an indicator [47] and expressed in degrees of acidity.

The content of free organic in terms of the equivalent amount of acids tartaric acid in absolutely dry raw materials in percents (X) was calculated using the formula: [48].

$$X = \frac{V \cdot K \cdot 0,0075 \cdot V_{ext} \cdot 100}{m \cdot V_a} \cdot \frac{100}{(100 - W)} \quad (2)$$

where 0,0075 - the amount of tartaric acid corresponding to 1 ml of a solution of sodium hydroxide (0.1 mol / L), g;

V - volume of sodium hydroxide (0.1 mol / l), which had gone on titration, ml;

K - coefficient of bringing the solution concentration of alkali to exactly 0.1 mol / l;

V_{ext} - extract volume, ml;

V_a - volume of the sample of extract taken for titration, ml;

m - sample weight, g;

W - %. loss on drying of raw materials, %.

$\frac{100}{(100 - W)}$ - scaling factor of absolutely dry raw materials.

Antioxidant activity

Antioxidant activity of extracts and inhibition kinetics of free radicals was examined by using diphenyl picryl hydrazyl (DPPH) [49, 50], which is based on determining the absorbance of DPPH radical, in the presence of antioxidants. To determine the concentration of free radicals calibration curve was constructed within the limits of concentration 0.38-38 g / ml for the free radical DPPH and according to this

standard curve DPPH values at a particular time of the reaction were calculated.

Antioxidant activity of the extract of the tested extract was determined by the formula:

$$AA\% = \frac{[DPPH]_0 - [DPPH]_t}{[DPPH]_0} \cdot 100 \quad (3)$$

where $[DPPH]_0$ - concentration of DPPH radical at time $t = 0$ sec;

$[DPPH]_t$ - DPPH radical concentration measured with a spectrophotometer after 30 minutes.

2.5. Statistical analysis

Variance analysis of the results was carried out by least square method with application of coefficient Student. Differences were considered statistically significant if probability was greater than 95% (p -value < 0.05). Experimental results are expressed as average \pm SD (standard deviation).

Results of regression analysis of the obtained dependences with the use of correlation coefficient, coefficient of determination, the standard deviation and the Fisher criterion (with a confidence interval estimation of the model at the level of error $\alpha = 0,05$ (confidence level 95%) confirmed their adequacy.

III. Results and discussion

The yield of dry extract (YDE) on the working mass at hydro ratio of 1:5 is described by the regression equation (4) and at 1:10 hydro ratio by equation (5):

$$B\Theta = 14,649 + 0,103 \cdot t + 0,360 \cdot \tau - 0,0014 \cdot t \cdot \tau \quad (4)$$

$$B\Theta = 28,971 + 0,0745 \cdot t + 0,0270 \cdot \tau + 0,000 \quad (5)$$

where t – temperature of extraction, $^{\circ}\text{C}$;
 τ – exposure time, min.

Dependence of the YDE on the working masses on time, temperature and hydro ratio is presented in the form of the response surface in Figure 1.

High total yield of extractives was observed already at 100°C and 0.5 h (31,9% at hydro ratio of 1:5 and 39,4% at hydro ratio 1:10 and can be explained by the following factors:

- residual sugar content of not fermented pomace;
- partial hydrolysis of pectin substances, hexuronic acid acids and mucus.

During extraction at hydro ratio of 1:5, these factors also lead to lower yield of dry extract than with hydro ratio 1:10. This is especially noticeable when the exposure time is 0.5 h. With reduction of hydro ratio extract concentration increases and this leads to acceleration of the thermal destruction at high temperatures.

At 160°C there was considerable swelling of extractable mass. At this temperature, hydro ratio of 1:5 and the exposure time of 1.5 hours in the mass, after extraction, free water was not observed

visually, indicating insufficiency of hydro ratio 1: 5.

At high temperatures, the yield of YDE is defined by two processes: the formation and transition to extract of water-soluble compounds and their decomposition under the influence of temperature and acidity. The main contribution to the increase in the yield of the extract makes the hydrolysis of polysaccharides with their transfer into soluble compounds (oligosaccharides, dextrans, monosaccharides). Pectin hydrolysis is followed by cleavage of acetic acid.

With increasing exposure time and the temperature to 140°C the yield of the extract increases. At 140°C the rate of hydrolysis of hemicelluloses and decomposition of monosaccharides increases. Thus strong organic acids - formic acid and acetic acid are formed, increase in concentration of which leads to acceleration of hydrolysis of

hemicelluloses and decomposition of monosaccharides. Decomposition of the sugars also leads to the formation of hydroxymethyl furfural, furfural, humin substances etc.

Yield of reducing substances (RS) at hydro ratio of 1:5 was described by the regression equation (6) and hydro ratio 1:10 – by equation (7):

$$PB = 9,189 + 0,1071 \cdot t + 0,3172 \cdot \tau - 0,0010 \quad (6)$$

$$PB = 23,04 + 0,078 \cdot t + 0,034 \cdot \tau + 0,00066 \cdot \dots \quad (7)$$

where t – temperature of extraction, °C;
 τ – exposure time, min.

Dependence of the yield of reducing substances on time, temperature and hydro ratio in the form of a surface of response is shown in Figure 2.

For each hydro ratio with the increase of temperature and exposure time the yield of RS increases. Yield for a hydro ratio 1:10 under appropriate temperatures and exposure time is considerably higher (20-30%) than for a hydro ratio 1:5. This is due to the high concentration of the solution in the second case. High concentration, in accordance with the laws of chemical kinetics, leads to a significant acceleration of decomposition reactions. The final products of decomposition of sugars are humic substances that do not demonstrate the reducing activity.

For hydro ratio 1:5 some increase in yield of the RS with increasing

temperature has been noticed. However, it is significantly lower than for the hydro ratio 1:10 and will stabilize at 120-130°C. This is due to the high speed of chemical transformations of forming various sugars in solutions with a relatively high concentration of extractives.

With increasing temperature at hydro ratio 1:10 to 120°C there is a slight increase in the yield of RS. At a temperature 120-150°C there is a significant increase in sugars, which can be explained by hydrolysis of easily hydrolyzable polysaccharides (hemicellulose, pectin, uronic acid, etc.). Above 150°C number of extracted RS stabilizes practically at the same level, so

the work in the conditions of static extraction is not feasible. Analysis of qualitative reactions that describe the yield of reducing substances showed that increase in the concentration of solutions and temperature leads to a greater decomposition of sugars. Rational parameters extracting RS depend on the purpose of further processing of extracts. D Fermentation of extracted sugars to alcohol is one of the first schemes, from the viewpoint of the market appeal of the obtained products. Yield of polyphenols (tannin and catechin complex) of GP is represented by phenolic acids, flavonoids, tannins, proanthocyanidins, stilbenes.

Yield of polyphenols (F) at hydro ratio of 1:5 was described by the regression

a)

equation (8) and hydro ratio of 1:10 – by equation (9):

$$F = -5,902 + 0,164 \cdot t + 0,019 \cdot \tau - 0,00019 \quad (8)$$

$$F = 7,086 - 0,021 \cdot t + 0,002 \cdot \tau, \quad (9)$$

where t – temperature of extraction, $^{\circ}\text{C}$;
 τ – exposure time, min.

Dependence of the F of GP on time, temperature and hydro ratio is presented in the form of the surface of response in Figure 3.

b)

Figure 3 – Surface of response of yield of F of GP:

a) at hydro ratio of 1:5, b) at hydro ratio 1:10

The obtained data we have considered as a result of the flow of two opposing processes: 1) the transition of polyphenolic compounds into solution; 2) the secondary transformation of polyphenolic compounds, leading to degradation or transition into insoluble state and precipitation.

A significant increase in yield F we can explain by the transition into a solution

of tannins (tannins) and their hydrolysis products under high temperatures and acidic environment.

The amount of tannin (enotannin) in grape pomace may reach 10% (for dry weight). It exceeds its content in oak (5-6,6%), which is traditionally used for obtaining tannins.

The value of titratable acidity (K) at hydro ratio of 1:5 was described by the

regression equation (10) and hydro ratio 1:10 – by equation (11):

$$K = 3,281 + 0,0053 \cdot t - 0,0771 \cdot \tau + 0,000660 \cdot t \cdot \tau \quad (10)$$

$$K = 0,281 + 0,0271 \cdot t - 0,0262 \cdot \tau + 0,000271 \cdot t \cdot \tau \quad (11)$$

where t – temperature of extraction, °C;
 τ – exposure time, min.

The high K of the obtained extracts has been noted.

Recalculation of K on tartaric acid, which is the main component of grapes acid complex, showed that at 100-120°C the extraction of acidity passes through a maximum in time. This is due to the degree of extraction ratio of tartaric acid from the solid phase and chemical changes at elevated temperature.

The dependence of K (ml 0,1 mol / l NaOH) on time, temperature and hydro ratio is represented in the form of a surface of response in Figure 4.

Figure 4.– Surface of response of titratable acidity:
 a) at hydro ratio of 1:5, b) at hydro ratio 1:10

For some of the experimental points acidity of extracts obtained at hydro ratio of 1:5 is somewhat higher. This is due to the hydrolysis of polysaccharides and sugars decomposition with the formation of strong organic acids - formic and acetic acid, as well as a number of weak – levulinic acid, glucose izosaccharinic acid, xylose izosaccharinic acid, lactic acid [51]. In conditions of the lower hydro ratio concentration of sugars in the solution is greater, and respectively, decomposition speed is higher. The titratable acidity of the extract increases.

According to the formation and transformation of organic acids, dry extract

composition obtained by evaporation of water varies. Tartaric and levulinic acids are nonvolatile. They almost totally remain in dry extract. Formic and acetic acids, on the contrary, are volatile. Therefore, the acidity of the dry extracts obtained by evaporation is lower than the acidity of not evaporated solutions.

Tartrate solutions together with free tartaric acid contain their salts, in particular the acidic potassium tartrate. Therefore, determination of yield of tartaric acid and its derivatives according to titratable acidity gives low results even with the presence of other acids (malic, citric, etc.).

Antioxidant activity

The results of the kinetics of inhibition of free radicals (percent of DPPH which remains in the stable condition) at

hydro ratio of 1:5 are shown in Figure 5, with the hydro ratio 1:10 - in Figure 6.

Figure 5 - Kinetic curves of interaction of GP extracts (at hydro ratio of 1:5) with a free radical DPPH

Figure 6 - Kinetic curves of interaction of GP extracts (at hydro ratio 1:10) with a free radical DPPH

Knowledge of the kinetics of atom transfer is important because the free radicals in the body are short-lived species, which means that the influence of the

substance as an antioxidant depends upon its rapid reactivity to the free radicals. More rapid decline in absorption means a more powerful anti-radical ability of the

compounds. The steeper the graph of fall, the better and the faster free radicals bind. When hydro ratio is 1:5 all the free radicals are quickly bound by GP extract obtained in the medium of SCW at the temperature of 120⁰C and exposure time of 30 minutes. At hydro ratio 1:10 high speed of binding of free radicals was observed at the reaction with extracts of GP extracted in SCW at the temperature of 100⁰C and exposure time of 60 min.

As a result of recovery of DPPH by antioxidant (by extracts of GP) purplish blue color of DPPH in methanol decreased to a yellow, the reaction was monitored by change in optical density at a wavelength of 514 nm.

The antioxidant activity of the extracts of GP at hydro ratio of 1:5 was described by regression equation (12) and hydro ratio 1:10 – by equation (13):

$$APA = 117,1 - 0,45 \cdot t + 0,08 \cdot \tau \quad (12)$$

$$APA = 120,64 - 0,36 \cdot t + 0,03 \cdot \tau \quad (13)$$

where t – temperature of extraction, ⁰C;
 τ – exposure time, min.

It was found out that GP extracts obtained in SCW have high APA from 33% to 94% in relation to the stable DPPH free radicals. The most rapidly bind free radicals BB extracts obtained from liquor ratio of 1:10 and a temperature of 100⁰C retention time 60 min. ARA values for these parameters - 94.01%.

The obtained results ARA of GP extracts in the environment of SCW are significantly higher or comparable at least with 24 plant objects, which were extracted by percolation with ethanol.

Thus, extracts obtained in the environment of SCW have properties of ARA comparable not only with extracts

obtained by other methods, but they are superior to them.

IV. Conclusions

The conducted research gives the possibility to make the following conclusions.

When washing sweet pomace by hot water the yield of dry extract is up to 15% of weight of absolutely dry pomace. The bulk of the extract is the carbohydrates (mainly free monosaccharides) and acidic compounds. Under the SCW extraction extract yield is at least two times greater. The increase in yield of the extract can be explained by the formation of water-soluble carbohydrates out of polysaccharides, a significant amount of polyphenolic compounds is also observed.

The maximum number of RS - 48.991% had a yield at $T=160^{\circ}\text{C}$, exposure time $\tau=90$ min, pressure $P = 12$ MPa, hydro ratio of 1:10. These parameters of the process are rational in the fermentation of the extracted sugars into alcohol.

The maximum number of total polyphenols - 5.534% had a yield at $T=100^{\circ}\text{C}$, exposure time $\tau=60$ min, pressure $P = 12$ MPa, hydro ratio of 1:10.

The yield of polyphenolic compounds under the extraction SCW exceeds the amount of polyphenols obtained under the extraction with organic solvents and water at temperatures up to 60⁰C.

It should be noted that during the extraction of polyphenols of SLW low selectivity towards specific groups of flavonoids occurs. In extraction with organic solvents the proportion of phenolic substances in the extract is significantly higher and they are presented primarily by nontanning substances. This fact complicates the selection, separation and purification of polyphenol compounds from the extracts of SCW. Selectivity according to polyphenolic substances for SCW is

lower than for the organic solvents, but there is a significant increase in their yield due to tannins, and hence it makes sense not to extract and utilize separate polyphenol fractions but whole tannin and catechin complex out of GP.

Yield of acids at low temperatures of extraction (100-120⁰C) SCW is comparable to the amount of acids in the source pomace obtained by washing sweet pomace with hot water. When washing with hot water extraction of tartaric acid compounds is 80% and more of their content in the raw materials. Thus, at 100-120⁰C it is possible to extract tartaric acid almost completely.

Extraction of GP SCW (at hydro ratio 1:10, temperature of a process 100⁰C, exposure time 60 min) allows to obtain an extract with high antioxidant activity - 94.01%.

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RENEWABLE RESOURCES AND SUSTAINABLE INTERVENTIONS FOR CONSERVATION OF VALUABLE BIODIVERSITY OF NATURAL FLORA OF GRASSLANDS AND MOUNTAIN MEADOWS AND TO AVOID GROUNDWATER POLLUTION. CONTRIBUTIONS FOR ANIMAL WELL-BEING AND MOUNTAIN FARMS PRODUCTION AND LANDSCAPE PRESERVATION

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Abstract: *Abandoning the use of natural fertilizers for an interval of 8 to 10 years causes the phenomenon of rewilding the meadows by allowing the invasion of plant species that seriously affects the high natural value, vitiating biodiversity. Defective construction of the traditional stables generates poor hygiene and excessive noxious gases (ammonia, hydrogen sulfide, carbon dioxide, etc.). Liquid manure (urine), especially from cattle, is not collected, penetrating the ground, having a polluter effect on groundwater. Urine is also a valuable organic fertilizer (biological nitrogen), which collected and used on scientific basis may offer threefold benefits: improving the health of animals and farmers; avoid pollution of groundwater; preservation and enhancement of biodiversity, especially on meadows. Solid organic fertilizer, manure, coming from cattle and sheep / goats - is another factor of utmost importance both by the contribution of humus, etc., and by the effect of amending the natural acidity of mountain soils, a guarantee for preservation of biodiversity with high natural value. Ensuring the avoidance of mold in polyfloral hay is another important factor for consumers' health by preventing the occurrence of aflatoxin in milk.*

Keywords: *high natural value, organic fertilizer, mountain product, biodiversity, mountain areas*

1. Introduction. Problem enunciation

Climate change and demographic trends towards 9 billion inhabitants until 2015 bring intense discussion both in the exponentially growing need for food, and stepping up efforts to conserve exhaustible resources, while managing better renewable resources. The increasing interest for cleaner environment and for good quality food brings special attention to mountain areas. The natural polyfloral mountain meadows underpinning valuable biodiversity is the result of secular human efforts, based on continuous

systematic use of organic fertilizers coming from ruminants.

2. Quality in Mountain Areas

A large specific segment forming the planetary assembly is represented by mountain areas, which still have not been paid comparable attention to the one given for plain and hilly areas. Also for the Romanian Carpathians there is a growing interest for adapted continuous policies, focusing on renewable resources with relevance to economy and the environment, with respect for the key

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factors that depend on a good balance between man and nature, among which can be mentioned:

- vegetable resources - with major relevance: mountain natural flora (grass) and forest vegetation;
- resources provided by animals - strictly correlated with the beneficial relationship between fodder plants and organic fertilizers;
- human resources - represented primarily by mountain farmers;
- water - as a fundamental renewable resource, supporting the perennality of a mountain-type ecosystem, balanced and nuanced, depending on regional or micro-regional geo-climatic factors.

In this complex assembly reference shall be the QUALITY - in all its segments:

- environmental quality - water and air, unpolluted;
- quality of the natural flora, the grasslands, ensure that functional biodiversity of the first social utility, characterized by floral polymorphism - as the basis for feeding ruminant animals (cattle, sheep, goats);
- the quality of animals - breeds and varieties of mountain type, in terms of production but also of the organic resistance against the mountain environment subject to temperature and humidity variations, steep slope, et al;
- the quality of organic fertilizers - with differences given especially by bovine and ovine species;
- workforce quality - the producers/mountain farmers who own physical and mental qualities and traditional skills, "best practices" - a centuries-old legacy.

3. Data Synthesis – Romanian Carpathians (2012)

- Total surface = 71341km² (~30% of the national territory)
- Counties with mountain area = 27 (not including the mountains of Dobrogea)
- Local administrative units LAU = 658, of which 577 communes; ~ 3520 mountain villages
- private agricultural exploitations = ~ 820,000
- ~ 20% of the total population (~ 3.37 million inhabitants of which ~ 2.1 million living in mountain households / small farms, of which ~ 1.3 million are active farmers.
- Approximately 2.9 million hectares of farmland, of which: - pastures = 1.283 million ha; 938.000 ha meadows; arable = 616,000 ha; 53,000 ha orchards;

- Farm animals [1], cattle: 588 (decreasing with more than 40%), sheep: ~ 1.9200.00 (decreasing with more than 20 percent overall, but in small and medium farms the reduction exceeded 80%. (2015)
- Average agricultural land per mountain farm / household = 3.9 ha
- About 4 million hectares of forests and forest vegetation.

3. Structure of Mountain Grasslands

The qualitative polyfloral structure of grassland is the result of secular collaboration between man and nature, by using ruminant animals and organic fertilizers – an essential, irreplaceable relationship. By pastures and meadows, with cattle / sheep / goats and the use of organic fertilizers, was possible to close the vital cycle "summer / winter" providing the possibility of permanent human habitation in mountain areas.

In the Romanian Carpathians with 2.7 mil ha of agricultural land (some of the least productive soil) and 820.000 mountain households – in 2016 it produces quality food for more than 3 million people. Organic fertilizers (manure, urine, purine) are irreplaceable factors for an agriculture that relies on grass and consume less conventional energy comparing to lowlands. The organic fertilizers brings to the mountain soils (generally acidic) an intake of organic substance (also coming from grass) - essential for a thin layer of productive soil of about 10 - 15 cm (which needs a century for the accumulation of only one cm of humus), and also an additional alkalinity - the result of aging (rotting) manure, either in arranged platforms, or basins for collecting urine - especially in the case of cattle. A high contribution is due to the capsular shape of manure from sheep / goat which generates intense anaerobic fermentation and short term rotting (6 to 7 days). Through simple measures of good organization can be ensured quality organic fertilizers and so can be preserved the valuable polyfloral structure of mountain meadows and thus a type of biodiversity with high social utility.

Relatively recent research[2] and multiple practical observations over the last 20 years have shown that in about 7-8 years without ensuring continuity in the use of organic fertilizers on mountain pastures, it occurs a 're-wilding' phenomenon on natural valuable fodder flora, that was created in centuries

of continuity of preserving the mountain farming "best practices" - "the Mountain Punishment".

Restoration of a valuable polymorphous floral structure, valuable, on a natural, biological way, through the interspecific struggle of plant species with the risk of dominance of some less productive plants (nardus, forest moss, weeds and even noxious plants) is dependent on the existence of an essential and irreplaceable food chain in mountain conditions: MAN (mountain farmers) – RUMINANT ANIMALS – ORGANIC FERTILIZERS - and MOUNTAIN NATURAL POLYFLORA. The absence of a single element from this ensemble inevitably lead to the destruction of a balanced ecosystem whose recovery becomes extremely expensive or impossible to achieve in terms of the 21st century, marked with multiple alternatives for the young generations of mountain farmers, with trends for "agricultural abandonment" and migration to urban national or European areas. Hence the absolute priority on ensuring continuity of a large and extremely valuable mountain economy, through intense and continuous motivation of the essential factor – Mountain Population – the mountain agricultural producer, and especially the younger generation.

4. Some features of the organic fertilizers in the mountain area by species of ruminant animals.

Ovine / goats animals have a major role in the formation and improvement of the high mountain pastures and a completing role where meadows, which are frequently close to the households (anaerobic fermentation, alkalinity, organic matter, spreading during grazing at no extra cost). Cattles have a major role for hayfields. Quality assurance technology and usage are different from sheep (manure + urine). Requirements: arranged manure platforms; Fermentation (rotting) takes about a year (25/35 tonnes / ha). Scattering on hayfields is recommended in early spring. On pastures, fresh manure being highly acidic burns existing vegetation with minimal positive effect.

Urine is a major and precious resource of biological nitrogen, but still less used in the mountains of Romania. 15 liters per day per adult cattle. Traditional stables are not equipped with pool collectors of urine, generating harmful effects: source of gases (ammonia, CO₂, hydrogen sulfide, etc.). The consequence is damage to animal health, to production and farmers. Hygiene in the stables

(and sheepfolds) from the mountain area is mostly poor and thus we confront weak productions and health problems for both animals and humans.

Urine and groundwater: The absence of collecting basins has negative effects on groundwater because leakage occurs concentrated in the barn. Different, by urine collection and proper use, multiple benefits can be provided: disappearance of the source of harmful gases from stables, animal health in protected, and increase yields shall be recorded. Spreading aged urine on meadows will bring an intake of biological nitrogen, will increase the grass production helping to conserve valuable diversity, and ultimately, bettering the health of mountain farmers and their income.

5. The Hay Quality

The polymorphic composition is valuable and can still be improved. But the traditional hay conservation during winter, in haystacks, uncovered and exposed to rain and snow, involves the risk of mold, which included in animal nutrition can produce aflatoxins, whose harmful effects and can be transmitted through milk and may harm the consumers. Cheap and available prevention can be achieved by building enclosed barns, using lower class wood, directly on hayfield. Eg: Austria, the northern counties of Romania - NT, SV, MM, and partly BN. Means of mechanization exists but are still expensive and are based on conventional sources of energy – oil/petrol - exhaustible resource.

6. Economic References. New Opportunities - "Mountain Product"

Ensuring quality of the polymorphic floristic composition of grasslands and mountain meadows, and improving the state of hygiene in traditional stables is an element of serious concern for the ministry of agriculture and rural development, with a particular role assigned to the new agency of mountain area. Consumers' interest for better and healthier nutrition is growing. There is a significant market segment for mountain food products, with high-quality biological value, obtained based on the floral polymorphism, in the absence of agro-chemical and other polluting factors. Obviously, on terms of quantity, the mountain agriculture cannot compete with the big farming from lowlands, based

mainly on intensive chemical processing, mechanization and intensive industrial livestock systems in an increasingly polluted environment, especially to the ground water level. In this tacit "competition" the only chance of mountain farming can be found in quality, though mountain products as guaranteed niche products that are obtained with human efforts, having lower return rates, but consuming much lower conventional energy, the entire mountain agricultural system being based on a solution of the future: renewable energy.

This explains the rationale behind the new EU regulation No 1151/2012 (EP + Council of Europe) and no. EC 665/2014, referring to quality schemes and mountain quality product, explicitly. The period following 2016 opens a new opportunity for both consumers and mountain farmers - a heading direction, a chance for better future which require specific organizational efforts, a strong role being held by the development of a mountain cooperative system that will ensure improvements of farmers' income and sustainable development.

4. Conclusions

The use of organic fertilizers on scientific basis, ensure biodiversity conservation of mountain meadows, quality "mountain product" and consequently the preservation of high value landscapes.

Upgrading traditional old stables, ensuring accurate collection and use of manure and urine, and fostering construction of new hygienic stables is a priority for the mountain agriculture in Romania.

By conserving and improving the floristic composition of the grasslands, also the landscape quality is maintained and amplified - highlight for mountain tourism economy.

Modern agriculture and animal husbandry technologies provide the vast majority of human food - but in terms of quality this is not comparable to food products coming from mountain areas.

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PREPATION OF ETHYL ALCOHOL FROM GRAPE POMACE EXTRACTED BY SUBCRITICAL WATER

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Abstract: *This article discusses the process of obtaining raw alcohol from grape pomace by subcritical water extraction. Extraction was performed under a temperature range of $T = 100\text{C} \div 160\text{C}$, pressure $P = 12\text{ MPa}$, exposure of 30 to 90 min and hydronic modules 1:5 and 1:10. Results obtained in studies showed that the highest yield of extractives (primarily due to sugars and their degradation products) was observed at high temperatures ($140\text{C} - 160\text{C}$). But there is pollution of sugar solution harmful to microorganism's substances. Purification was performed by steam stripping of volatile compounds (furfural, formic acid, etc.) and subsequent filtration. The thus obtained solution was further subjected to extraction with inversion for larger amounts of fermentable carbohydrates. The highest yield of crude alcohol takes place for purified extract obtained by following process parameters: $T = 160\text{C}$, $P = 12\text{MPa}$, $t = 90\text{ min}$, hydronic module 1:10. This yield was ~ 160 (liters of absolute alcohol) / (ton of oven-dry pomace).*

Key Words: *extraction, subcritical water, raw alcohol, grape pomace*

1. Introduce

Recently there has been growing concern about environmental conservation and sustainable development of resources. [1] Technology for processing fruits and berries in the food industry leads to large amounts of secondary byproducts. Grape (*Vitis vinifera* L.) is the largest fruit crop to world production of about 68 million tons in 2009. [2] But in winemaking is used only 75-80 % of the desired product of total grape production.

The main byproduct of winemaking is grape marc (GM) [3]. GM is a multicomponent feed. Chemical composition of grape pomace is valuable because they are rich with polysaccharide complex; contain significant amounts of phenolic compounds and lignin. Up to 60 % by weight of dry grape marc (GM) comprise polysaccharides [4]. Traditional way of processing is their sugars for ethanol fermentation. Yield of dry grape alcohol is 3.5-4.5 dal per 1 ton of marc [5]. Under it there were fermented only available monosaccharides (mainly glucose), available in the GM. Polysaccharides (pectins, hemicellulose, cellulose) that constitute the vast majority of the explosives carbohydrate complex, were not subjected to fermentation. The polysaccharides can be processed in ethyl alcohol after their hydrolysis to monosaccharides. Thus, processing of grapes (such as obtaining a low-quality alcohol- mixed gasoline) is lost annually rather

significant amount of polysaccharides in the form of unused grapes.

The main problem that occurs on full use of explosives is their high moisture content, and the need for early treatment to prevent development of molds and prevent spoilage. Grape pomace begin to deteriorate after 2-3 days, and at high humidity (85 - 90%) and elevated temperatures ($25-40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$), shelf life is 8-12 hours. [6] Causes of damage are varied. This is primarily influenced by many organisms - rot pathogens. Significant role in the destruction play enzymatic processes. In the formation of rot are involved primarily yeast and fungi.

When choosing a method of preservation grape marc should be guided by the following characteristics: maximum preservation of the nutritional value of bagasse, efficiency and minimum duration. Freezing allows you to retain maximum nutrients, but this method of storing is enough energy intensive [7]. There are also ways to inhibit the growth of microorganisms in gaseous media, such as, reduced content [8-10]. When using gas atmospheres losses of biologically active substances are not observed. However, the above mentioned methods of conservation products have an important shortcoming because require significant capital investments, which is not appropriate in terms of primary winemaking enterprises, and applied to grape pomace. We have chosen the most common method of preserving raw materials and products in order to slow biochemical and microbiological processes - drying [11-12]. Received

conglomerates are well kept and require no additional energy supply in storage.

In order to maximally utilize all the fermentable sugars that are in the dried agglomerates, extraction was conducted with promising effective method - among subcritical water (superheated water under pressure at temperatures from 100 °C to 374 °C) [13-21]. Replacement of toxic organic solvents, and greenhouse liquefied gases with clean subcritical water will reduce the economic and environmental consequences of their use as an extractant.

When processing raw sugar - the most important is alcoholic fermentation. Depending on conditions (temperature, concentration, and type of raw materials, pH, and other types of microorganisms) following major products can be produced by fermenting: ethanol (alcohol fermentation); lactic acid, ethyl alcohol (lactic acid fermentation); acetone, butanol, ethanol (fermentation aceto - butyl); propionic acid, acetic acid (propionic fermentation), etc.

Of all sugar-containing materials used for preparing an alcohol extract grape marc is the closest one to the wood hydrolyzate. Getting ethanol from acid hydrolysates of vegetable raw materials is a well -studied process. Therefore, it is advisable to conduct extract fermentation similar to fermented sugar solution obtained by acid hydrolysis of wood [22].

II. Materials and methods

2.1. Plant material

Grapes of Moldova were acquired in late September in retail network of Donetsk (Ukraine) from the manufacturers - Republic of Moldova. Moldova - table grape. The average weight of bunches up to 350 grams. Berry large (2,5 x 1,9 cm), oval, dark purple, with a thick waxy coating. Peel thick, dense, durable. Pulp is fleshy, crunchy. Simple tastefully.

2.2. Preparation of raw materials

Crushing berries with crests was carried out on an industrial juicer to a moisture content of grape pomace - 55 % [23, 24]. Original drying was at 75 C \pm 2 ° C until constant weight was carried out in porcelain bowls placed in an oven TRTS02 TP- 1 with occasional stirring. Residual moisture of pomace after drying was 4-7 (% abs.). The resulting agglomerates are crushed to a fraction passing through the sieve with an aperture of 3 mm. Samples in powder form packaged in paper bags to protect them from light and polythene bags to protect them from

ambient moisture. Samples were stored at room temperature in a dark place in a laboratory of fluid technology of Donetsk National University of Economics and Trade named after M. Tugan - Baranovsky (DonNUET), Ukraine.

2.3. Extraction by for sub-critical water

The equipment used for extraction in subcritical water (SCW) has been designed and manufactured in a laboratory of fluid technology of DonNUET. Extraction was performed in a laboratory reactor under steady conditions. Usage ratio of raw material and extractant (water) is 1:5 and 1:10. The temperature was varied from 100 to 160 C in increments of 100C. The temperature was maintained by a controller with an accuracy of \pm 1 0C. Exposure time was 30 min, 60 min and 90 min. Report time started after reaching the desired temperature. At each point three parallel experiments were performed.

Level pressure $P = 12$ MPa. Such pressure provides subcritical conditions and high yield of extractables, as cell membranes are destroyed. Pressure was set and maintained, based on the thermodynamical properties of water. Differential equations of thermodynamics equations International 1997 , hereinafter referred to as Formulation IF - 97, which were calculated , designed for industry [25].

Calculated error values calculated by the equations Formulation IF - 97, in the fluid at temperatures of 25 ... 200 ° C and pressures of from 5 MPa to 100 MPa is \pm 0,005%.

2.4. Fermentation methodology of grape pomace extracts

We conducted fermentation at 10-35 C, pH 3.0-6.0. Alcoholic fermentation was carried out at expense of cultural, and due to wild yeast. Exposure time of extracts was from several hours up to 1.5 weeks.

Before fermentation extracts were subjected to inversion by boiling sulfuric acid in an open flask. This, together with water vapor purged volatiles, i.e. cleans the extract. After inversion excess acid was neutralized with lime. The resulting precipitate was filtered off on a Buchner funnel. The crude alcohol was distilled off together with water vapor.

For analysis of results amount of carbohydrates of various groups in original press cake was determined. Free carbohydrates, water-soluble polysaccharides, pectins, hemicellulose A and B were determined by the method of [26], based on a combination of carbohydrates separation schemes by Bailey, which is sequential extraction of material to different

solvents and spectrophotometric method by Dreywood. Cellulose was determined by alcoholic nitrogenous method (Kurshner) [27].

For the extracts concentration of active H⁺ ions was determined by titration with alkali [28]. Subcritical extraction at various acids is intermediate and final reaction products. In fact, extraction takes place under conditions of auto-catalysed hydrolysis of polysaccharides which act as acid catalysts. Therefore, acid is an important factor characterizing the extraction process, including in terms of formation of simple sugars from polysaccharides.

Moreover, since the alcohol formed during fermentation of simple carbohydrates, we

Table 1– Group of starting material

Groups of substances	Content on a dry weight pomace, %
Monosaccharides	7,5
Hemicellulose B	4,5
Hemicellulose A	0,5
Pectin	5,7
Water-soluble polysaccharides	6,5
Cellulose	23,5

As can be seen, starting material contains a significant amount of carbohydrates. Also it is high in sugars that can be fermented directly into alcohol.

The feedstock contains significant amounts of carbohydrates. But most of them represented by polysaccharides which cannot be directly fermented to ethanol.

During subcritical water extraction of these polysaccharides, they are hydrolyzed to form of monosaccharides. In this case a substantial part of starting polysaccharide BB - is hydrolyzable substances (hemicelluloses, water-soluble polysaccharides, pectins). In hydrolysis of polysaccharides derived sugars weight is further increased by addition of water. Hydrolysis catalysts include organic acids, such as contained in feed and generated in extraction process. In terms of technology index active acidity is important not only to the catalytic

evaluated amount of simple carbohydrates passing into solution by reducing the ability of extracts.

In connection with the above, the choice of extracts that ferment into alcohol, was taken into account experimental data obtained by the authors to determine the active acidity and reducing ability of these extracts.

III. Results and discussion

The results of determination of carbohydrate group of starting material are shown in Table 1.

point of view. It defines the pH of the extract, and hence the number and sequence of operations to prepare a fermented extract.

It is known that in the industrial hydrolysis with dilute sulfuric acid timber by percolation amount of acid is 0.3-0.7 wt% [22]. In addition, during hydrolysis in the decay of wood sugars produced organic acid in an amount of 0.3-0.5 wt. % from hydrolyzate calculated as sulfuric acid. Amount of H⁺ ions of the catalyst (sulfuric acid) and organic acids corresponds to the pH at the outlet of hydrolyser - 1.0-1.2. For the subcritical extraction of GM titrated amount (active) ions H⁺ under different conditions in terms of pH are shown in Table 2.

Most of acidity in extracts prepared at liquor ratio of 1:5. This is due to hydrolysis of polysaccharides and sugar decomposition with formation of strong organic acids.

Table 2 – Quantity of H⁺ ions in extracts

Temperature, °C	Extraction time, min	pH for hydronic module	
		1:5	1:10
140	30	1,06	1,36
140	60	0,99	1,32
140	90	0,99	1,33
150	30	1,03	1,31
150	60	0,92	1,27

150	90	0,90	1,21
160	30	1,00	1,28
160	60	0,90	1,26
160	90	0,88	1,21

When concentration of sugars lower liquor ratio in the solution is greater, respectively, and is above the decomposition rate. Titratable acidity of the extract increases.

Despite the fact that the acidity at 1:10 hydronic ratio is less than 1:5, pH at 1:10 liquor ratio is comparable to the pH at catalyzed hydrolysis with dilute sulfuric acid timber [22], which leads to hydrolysis of active polysaccharides for GM catalysis.

As for the output of reducing substances, for each hydronic with increasing

temperature and exposure time is their increase. Moreover, hydronic module 1:10 to yield at appropriate temperatures and dwell time is significantly higher (20-30 %) than for hydronic module 1:5. This is due to the high speed of chemical reactions of various sugars formed in solutions with relatively high concentration of extractives.

Response surface generated output of reducing substances from time to time, temperature and liquor ratio are presented in Figure 1.

a) b)
Figure 1. - Surface of output response of reducing substances:
a) hydronic module 1:5, b) hydronic module 1:10

Fermentation was carried out on ethyl alcohol for extracts showed the greatest reducing ability. Thus ferment extracts obtained at 140 and 160 C and a hydronic module of 1:10.

Figure 3 shows the quantitative results of the fermentation extracts.

a)

b)

Figure 3. - Results of GM fermentation extract obtained at:
a) 140^oC; b) 160^oC

Fermentation extracts obtained according to the above procedure was carried out and showed the following results:

- At a pH of less than 3.9 develops mainly propionic fermentation. At 30 °C and below propionic bacteria fermentation of tartaric acid salt was decomposed by acetic acid, propionic acid and CO₂. It develops strongly in diluted fermentation extracts (~ 2 % of solids), even at a temperature of 10 C. Also was noted the development of fungi;

- At a pH of 4, 0-5, 2 to extracts obtained at low temperatures developing alcoholic fermentation. With a long standing

extracts was indicated development of fungi. Before we can take optimal parameters for temperature 27-33 C and pH 4.2-4.8;

- For all of extracts obtained at 160 C and extracts obtained at 140 C and cooling time of 1.0 h and 1.5 h, fermentation occurs under any pH. In these extracts is also developing fungi, but not as active as in the previous cases. This is explained by strong pollution extracts decay products of sugars. Decomposition products of sugars (furfural, hydroxymethylfurfural, formic acid, etc.) inhibit growth of microorganisms;

- The largest yield of extractives (primarily due to sugars and their degradation products) was observed at high temperatures. But there is pollution harmful to the sugar solution microorganism's substances. These experiments and the results and published data may include: 1) organic acid - acetic, formic acid, levulinic acid, propionic acid, uronic, resin and higher fatty acids, 2) decomposition products of sugars and hydrolysis byproducts: furfural, hydroxymethylfurfural, methyl alcohol, formaldehyde, acetone, etc, 3) colloidal substances - lignin and humic; being in extracts in the form of a fine colloidal substances, they can be adsorbed on surface of yeast cells, reducing its active surface and inhibiting process of metabolism. Composition comprises extracts of mineral substances.

As expected, the highest yield of alcohol production takes place for extract obtained at 160 C and extraction time 90 min. Under these conditions, the amount thereof is equal to ~ 160 (L of absolute alcohol) / (tons of oven-dry bagasse).

IV. Conclusions

The most valuable products obtained when processing complex grape marc and yeast sediments are tartaric acid and its salts, and ethyl alcohol. According to its physical properties, it is no different from ethyl alcohol derived from other food raw materials (grain, potatoes, sugar beet).

Fermentation extracts of grape marc for raw alcohol showed good results comparable to the processing of plant materials by high-temperature hydrolysis. For example, yield of 100 % ethyl alcohol in the hydrolysis of softwood dilute solution of sulfuric acid is 150-180 l/(t absolutely dry wood) [23].

Resulting raw alcohol for use in food needs to be further purified by distillation. Moreover, its output will decrease by 10.5 % [24]. But even with the loss of cleaning obtained amount of ethyl alcohol is high enough to plant materials processed by high-temperature hydrolysis without external addition of catalysts (acid - sulfuric, hydrochloric, etc.).

Descriptions should also consider the process organization. Our investigations were performed in stationary conditions. Wood hydrolysis with dilute acid is lead by percolation. When applying this method for the extraction of sugars yield grape pomace, and,

consequently, alcohol may be increased to 20 % (relative).

Thus grape pomace extracted by subcritical water is a valuable product for raw alcohol and ethyl alcohol food.

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MOUNTAIN AGRI-TOURISM EFFICIENCY BY THE CONTROL OF QS PROCEDURES CONCERNING CHEESE

R. GRUIA*, Gh. PUCHIANU, R. REY

Abstract: *Under the context of present requests, on ecological line and the one of the development of mountain agri-tourism, the study proposes to highlight certain scientific elements in order to achieve a system of unitary control of the quality of traditional Carpathian cheese. We are referring to several categories of cheese, but especially to the mutton, goat, cows and even buffalo ones, which are specific to the Carpathian Mountain zone. There are studied and described traditional characteristics, in function of their geographical origin, as well as there are characterized the methods and procedures of the quality system (QS) in the techniques of traditional fabrication of cheese at farm level.*

The applied methodology presupposes to collect information and systematize it on sorts of cheese and the chain of traditional fabrication process, using statistic methods, as well as a series of physico-chemical, microbiological and toxicological analyses. In the study there is made a comparative analyses between the sorts of Romanian cheese produced in the mountain zone: „burduf” (skin) cheese, cheese in fir tree rind, „burduf”cheese with vegetable and flavoring plant adding, „urda” (soft sheep cheese), „caş” (mountain smoked soft sheep cheese).

Keywords: *mountain agri-tourism, farm cheese, quality system, traditionalistic.*

1. INTRODUCTION

A relevant aspect in agritourism is represented by the obtaining of animal origin products in own farms, especially in mountain zone, where sheep, goats, buffaloes or cattle have a favorable area for a qualitative production. Among zootechnic products, milk and dairy products, and especially cheeses, constitute a reference element, with a high market demand, but that do not always fulfill the qualitative characteristics asked by consumers. More than that, in the context of mountain zone development, there become opportune the idea of the analyses of the quality of these types of alimentary products, with an efficiency index through high prices sustained by the idea linked to the „mountain products quality” (Rey, R. and col., 2015).

Therefore, as for the system of cheese quality, produced both through industrial technologies (where the quality system

presupposes clear regulations and procedures), but especially obtained through traditional techniques, the problem is important in the conditions of high production diversity in agritouristic farms or in Romanian mountain farms. For example, in case of sheep, respectively of „burduf”cheese in fir tree (or pine tree, respectively species of resinous trees, used for their specific aroma) bark, our research mention a series of aspects linked to the type and sort of used bark, to the manner to avoid the tree destruction and the impact of using certain extracts. We have also observed the fact that (in order to preserve a certain renown) processing imposes a quality system/QS which, being respected, avoids quality differences between make charges, structure defects, consistence and cheese aspect (Gruia, R., Gaceu, L., 2010; Gruia,R.,2014).

We mention that any trial to achieve a comprehensive qualitative system for cheese production will take into account the law

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qualitative management, in conformity with ISO 9001:2008, the management system of aliment security ISO 22000:2005 and certificatory QSCert, as well as certain existing regulations and standards.

Combining everything that has been mentioned, we observe that, as for the making of traditional cheeses, and not only that, actual knowledge imposes a series of elements that we take into consideration in this study (Gruia, R., 2013; Rey, R., Gruia, R., 2013; Gruia, R., Rey, R., Bogdan, A.T., Tobă, G.F., 2015): - unaltered preservation of blooming pastures of the zone, maybe the largest blooming pastures that have remained in Europe depressions, the vegetal carpet being the big secret of the mountain zone milk and cheese quality; the reference techniques concerning grazing, milk conservation, milking, mamma hygiene, ablactation; - the traditionalism of cheese making takes into account the technologic operations of principle so that they harmonize (i.e. to take into account: the preparation and then the milk curdling, the cheese product formation, salting, maturation and preservation – where necessary -); - the registration of these products as being traditional, so that they may benefit of the encouraging European legislation face to the preservation of each people traditions and customs; - as mountain traditional product, it will have to benefit of a very well trimmed marketing strategy.

The brand of mountain traditional cheeses imposes to introduce sheep, but also goat, buffalo or cow cheese in connection to the „medieval” meadows characterized by mountain zone flora biodiversity, as well as to certain stages from cheese processing, as traditional specificity and as demands linked to hygiene. The manner to obtain these craft cheeses under the conditions of a quality system / QS must be tuned up and then it is proposed to be recommended for expansion.

The concatenation of the mentioned products will lead to sustain the cheese quality on three directions:

- From the exterior (packing, design, sapida /sensorial elements and others),
- of a nutritive order (nutritional density / macro-, micro and non- nutrients; thermal density, satiety and nutrition quality; bio-disponibility etc.) and

- of health generating order (salubrious / hygienic, clean, healthy, antioxidant capacity, glycolic and iatrogenic index, biochemical and genetic profile and others).

From all these aspects, we consider salubrity to be of major interest for the quality of mountain cheeses. If this basic element is fulfilled, then we may pass to the other characteristics that build coherent and efficient QS for the mountain alimentary products.

Therefore, the objective of this paper is to analyze the mountain cheese hygiene, as an element of corresponding QS. In this context, it is known that cheeses are very complex from microbiologic point of view, which makes it very difficult or sometimes impossible to appreciate their microbiologic quality. The intervention of technologic micro flora used in the processing largely contributes at these things.

2. MATERIAL AND METHOD

Between 1.01.2014 and 30.06.2015, we have examined a number of 16 sorts of cheeses, products of pasteurized and non pasteurized milk, from approximately 250 samples, more precisely 194 samples based on non pasteurized milk and 55 samples of pasteurized milk. The origin area is from the mountain zone, maybe the most developed and known one from the Romanian Carpathians, from Vama Buzăului and Ciucaș Mountains, at the shepherds from Săcele (Brașov), from the Făgăraș Mountains.

The samples have mostly had, as origin, natural and juristic persons, being gathered within the Self-control Program.

The diagnosis has been achieved within the Sanitary Veterinary and for the Food Safety Laboratory Brașov, using accredited methods in conformity with SR ISO 17.025/2005 forecasts.

The used methods have been (Bârzoii D. and col. 1999; Bârzoii D., Apostu S., 2002, Turcu, D., 2004; Puchianu, Gh., 2012; Ordin ANSVSA 17/2011):

- Microbiological ones: detecting and number of positive- coagulate staphylococcus, detection and enumeration of positive Escherichia coli at β – glucuronidasis;
- Mico-toxicological ones: detecting staphylococcus entero-toxin ;

- Physic-chemical ones: determination of fat protein.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Microbiologic controls that are made on cheeses generally aim to declare certain pathogenic germs, to establish the causes of certain defects and the relation between lactic micro flora and the present microbial micro flora.

The defects of cheeses may be of hygienic nature (the use of non corresponding milk), technologic one (incorrectly led process) or microbiologic one (produced by microorganisms) (Savu, C., 2002; Reg.CE 2073/2005; Apostu, C., 2006). The main defects met at cheeses (Gruia, R., Gâdei, Georgiana, 2012; Ivana, Simona, 2007 a,b) may be grouped in: bark defects, format defects, color, drawing, consistence, taste and smell ones (table 1).

Table 1. Defects of cheeses, described in specialty literature, with repercussions on quality

No.	DEFECT TYPE	DESCRIPTION OF THE DEFECT
1	Bark defects	- the frequently met are: too thick bark, with flaws, bark cancer, bark infection with mould.
2	Format defects	- may be: non uniform size of pieces, cheese flattening or bloating; cheese bloated bark often presents flaws, and their consistence is rubbery.
3	Color defects	- grayish-black color, reddish one, black spots on the surface (produced by moulds or torules - <i>Monilia nigra</i> , <i>Torula nigra</i>); it is generally due to non specific micro flora.
4	Drawing defects (ex.: as texture aspect)	- they may consist in the lack of drawing or rich drawing of the paste; - lack of drawing in section may be due to a reduced activity of gas producing bacteria; rich drawing of the paste is due to maturation at too high temperature or high degree of milk infection.
5	Consistence defects	- they refer at paste, which may be: frail, rubbery, with flaws.
6	Taste and smell defects	- they are to be found by sensations of sour, bitter, rancid.

There is known that cheeses obtained from milk infected with pathogenic microorganisms may become transmission means of infectious disease (for example: *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, *Salmonella typhimurium* and others may transmit at man by consuming infected cheeses). That's why microbiologic controls of mountain cheeses are compulsory, no matter the geographic area or the product source, which is introduced in the present study through analyses and detection of certain bacteria.

3.1. Detecting and enumerating positive-coagulate staphylococcus

Bacteria of the *Staphylococcus* genre, with the largest implications in alimentary hygiene are represented by *Staphylococcus aureus*, as well as by other species, such as: *S. epidermidis*, *S. agalactiae*, *S. dysgalactiae*, *S. uberis*, *S. sciuri*, *S. xylosum*, and *S. lentus* (Ştirbu C., Turcu D., 1999; Puchianu, G., 2011).

Staphylococcus aureus is frequently carried by apparently healthy people (generally on the nasal mucous membrane – being ejected by cough or sneeze and on skin), who manipulate milk and dairy products, as well as by animals producing milk (animal udder and skin, *staphylococcus mastitis*, etc.). Carriers frequency is larger among people who present or have presented furuncles, whitlows and different wounds at skin level. It is skin and hair transit resident and all the times in the intestinal tract, aliment contamination being due to non hygienic manipulation and processing.

The main danger of cheese contamination with *staphylococcus* consists in the elaboration by certain stems (coagulator-positive) of an enterotoxin able to provoke acute gastro-enteritis. The *staphylococcus* enterotoxin is thermo stable that is why, after its elaboration, it is hard or even impossible to inactivate it. *S. Aureus* multiplication is achieved at temperatures higher than 5-6°C and the elaboration of *staphylococcus*

entero-toxin at temperatures higher than 18°C. The intoxication risk grows as, through the development of these bacteria in different aliments, there do not obligatorily appear. Detection and enumeration of positive-coagulate staphylococcus has been achieved in conformity with SR EN ISO 6888-1 /June 2002.

The method principle consists in the inoculation of the surface of a selective environment of solid culture (Mediu agar Baird – Parker), using slabs in double, with a precise quantity from the initial suspension in case of solid products, aerobia incubation of the slabs at 35° C or 37° C and their examination both after 24 hours and after 48 hours, the calculation of the number of positive-coagulate staphylococcus per sample gram from the number of typical and/or

modifications in taste and smell in the aliment, even if their number is of hundreds of millions per gram (Ivana, Simona, 2007).

atypical colonies obtained on slabs at the chosen dilution levels so that they may give a significant result and confirmed through the result of a positive-coagulate test.

The obtained colonies have presented the following morphologic characteristics: black colored shiny colonies, the presence of an opalescent zone round the formed colonies. In case of atypical colonies, present at the majority of the examined non congruous samples, (positive non-coagulate staphylococcus), the opalescent ring has been absent. (fig. 1 and 2).

Fig. 1 – Positive-coagulate staphylococcus

Fig. 2 – Positive-non coagulate staphylococcus

Consequently to the made analyses there have been obtained the following results, present in table 2.

Table 2. Comparative results obtained consequently to the detection of bacteria of Staphylococcus genre, as congruous (C) or non congruous (N) samples

No.	Sorts of examined cheeses	Sample number			Non - pasteurized milk				Pasteurized milk			
		Total	Non-pasteurized milk	Pasteurized milk	C		N		C		N	
					No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
1	“Burduf” cheese	25	18	7	8	44,4	10	55,6	5	71,4	2	28,6
2	Soft cow cheese	3	1	2	1	100	-	-	1	50,0	1	50,0
3	Cow fresh cottage cheese	44	22	22	12	54,5	10	45,5	19	86,4	3	13,6
4	Cow matured cottage cheese	23	21	2	9	42,9	12	57,1	-	-	2	100
5	Ewe’s fresh cottage cheese	31	13	18	9	69,2	4	30,8	9	50,0	9	50,0
6	Ewe’s matured cottage cheese	37	36	1	33	91,7	3	8,3	1	100	-	-
7	Mixed fresh cottage cheese	6	1	5	-	-	1	100	2	40,0	3	60,0

8	Mixed matured cottage cheese	1	1	-	-		1	100	-	-	-	-
9	Goat's fresh cottage cheese	2	-	2	-	-	-	-	2	100	-	-
10	Cow whey cheese	35	30	5	12	40,0	18	60,0	3	60,0	2	40,0
11	Ewe's whey cheese	33	33	-	24	72,7	9	27,3	-	-	-	-
12	Mixed whey - cow/ewe	9	9	-	4	44,4	5	55,6	-	-	-	-
13	Cow Rumanian pressed cheese	6	5	1	3	60,0	2	40,0	1	100	-	-
14	Mixed Rumanian pressed cheese	2	2	-	2	100	-	-	-	-	-	-
15	Goat whey	1	1	-	-	-	1	100	-	-	-	-
16	Cow fat cheese	1	1	-	1	100	-	-	-	-	-	-
	TOTAL	259	194	65	118	60,8	76	39,2	43	66,2	22	33,8

It is observed that cheeses produced from non pasteurized milk have been non congruous (N) at the Staphylococcus parameter in a 39,2% percentage, whole cheeses produced from pasteurized milk have been non congruous (N) in a 33,8%. The difference is no significant, being of only 5,4%. The smaller percentage in case of cheeses obtained from pasteurized milk is due to the reduction from a numerical point of view of the bacterial micro flora consequently to the thermal treatment of the milk staple before processing. The enough high number of non congruous samples at cheeses obtained from pasteurized milk may be explained by deficient milk pasteurization or a contamination/recontamination after processing.

On sorts, it is observed that, in case of non pasteurized milk (except for cottage cheese, matured and non matured mixed fresh cottage cheese and goat whey, due to the non relevant number of examined samples), there exist significant percentages of non congruence (N) at cow matured cottage cheese– 57,1%, at “burduf” cheese – 55,6%, mixed whey – cow/ewe – 56,6%, cow fresh cottage cheese - 45,5% and cow Rumanian pressed cheese. It is to be remarked the non congruous (N) percentage of only 8,3% in case of ewe's matured cottage cheese.

In case of cheeses produced with pasteurized milk, high percentages of non congruence (N) have been observed at mixed fresh cottage cheese– 60%, ewe's fresh cottage cheese – 50%, soft cow cheese – 50% and cow whey – 40%. It must be remarked the reduced percentage of the non congruent samples of cow fresh cottage

cheese– 13,6% and a significantly smaller percentage of the non congruent samples of

“burduf”cheese – 28,6%, in comparison with the non congruent samples of the same sort from non pasteurized milk – 56,6%, the difference being of 28%.

3.2. Detection of staphylococcus entero-toxin

Out of the 98 non congruent samples, in which there have been detected bacteria of the Staphylococcus type, there have been isolated positive coagulate staphylococcus from a number of 25 samples. The 25 samples have been submitted to the examination of staphylococcus entero-toxin.

The examinations for staphylococcus entero-toxin detection have been made using the MiniVidas automatic analyzer, compact system of high performance in identifying highly pathogenic germs - Salmonella spp., Listeria .monocytogenes, Campylobacter jejuni, E.coli O 157, Enterotoxina Stafilococica. The MiniVidas automatic analyzer offers a large scale of applications, safety and simplicity in utilization, being an automatic, standardized and robust device which allows an objective reading and release of a rapid result in comparison to the classical work method (Mateescu C. and col, 2006).

The method has, as a principle, immunologic analyses in conformity with the European method of EU-RL and may obtain the results in 72 hours.

The matrixes submitted to expertise through laboratory examination have been cheeses from raw milk submitted to thermal treatment lower than pasteurization and from thermal treated milk

at which there have been identified positive coagulate staphylococcus. The samples from staphylococcus have not been examined in order to detect staphylococcus entero-toxin.

which have been isolated positive no coagulate

The obtained results consequently to sample examination have been synthesized in table 3.

Table 3. Number of examined samples and obtained results at staphylococcus entero-toxin detection.

No.	Sorts of examined cheeses	Sample numbers			Non-pasteurized milk				Pasteurized milk			
		Total	Non-pasteurized milk	Pasteurized milk	C		N		C		N	
					No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
1	Burduf „cheese”	8	5	3	3	60,0	2	40,0	2	66,7	1	33,3
2	Cow fresh cottage cheese	5	3	2	2	66,7	1	33,3	2	100	-	-
3	Ewe’s matured cottage cheese	3	3	-	2	66,7	1	33,3	-	-	-	-
4	Ewe’s fresh cottage cheese	5	1	4	1	100	-	-	3	75,0	1	25,0
5	Cow whey	2	2	-	2	100	-	-	-	-	-	-
6	Ewe’s whey	1	1	-	1	100	-	-	-	-	-	-
7	Mixed whey – cow/ewe	1	1	-	1	100	-	-	-	-	-	-
	TOTAL	25	16	9	12	75,0	4	25,0	6	66,7	3	33,3

There is observed that, from the total of 25 samples, in which there have been detected positive coagulate staphylococcus; at a number of 7 samples (representing a share of 28%) there have been detected staphylococcus entero-toxin. The highest percentage of non congruence has been registered at cheeses obtained from pasteurized milk – 33,3%, while at cheeses obtained from non pasteurized milk the entero-toxin has been present in 25,0% of the total of examined samples. This thing demonstrates that the entero-toxin has been produced by staphylococcus before having submitted the milk to the process of pasteurization, and applied temperature has not influenced its level. There is not excluded the milk contamination with positive-coagulate staphylococcus after pasteurization as a consequence of not having respected the hygiene conditions along the processing.

On sorts, there has been observed the fact that the highest percentage of non-congruence has been at “burduf” cheese obtained from non-pasteurized milk – 40,0%, followed, in descending order, by “burduf” cheese obtained from pasteurized milk, cow fresh cottage cheese, ewe’s matured cottage cheese - 33,3% and ewe’s fresh cottage cheese – 25,0%

The interpretation has been done in conformity with the stipulations of the 2073/2005 Regulation, in which there are stipulated microbiologic safety criteria that define the

acceptable character of processes, as well as certain microbiologic safety criteria of alimentary products that should establish a limit over which an alimentary product has to be considered unacceptable, as being contaminated.

3.3. Detection and enumeration of positive coli *Escherichia at β – glucuronidazis*

The usual Habitat of *Escherichia coli* is to be found in the digestive tract of man and animals with hot blood and of certain insects and represents the dominant micro flora of the colon. The bacterium is released in the outer environment at the same time with fecal matters, contaminating the soil, water and aliments (Palmer S.R. and col., 2005).

Escherichia coli may derive from the infested udder or, then, from manipulators ‘hands or during non hygienic milking, from the dirty animal with contaminated fecal. Milk may be mainly contaminated with *E.coli* through carrying persons (Order 17/2011).

Toxins produced by *E. coli* producing verocitotoxins (ECVT), among the most implied in human pathology are: VT1, VT2 and VT2c, which injure specific target cells (probable endothelial cells of the capillaries from kidney and other organs and tissues), their role in man's

Enterotoxins produced by *E. coli* are endotoxins firmly linked to cell wall, thermo labile proteins that inactivate at 60°C in 30 de minutes and completely destroy at pH = 3,5-5. They are resistant at tripsin action (Mateescu, C. and col.2006).

The following categories of aliments represent a risk for public health with *E. coli* verotoxigen (VTEC): cheeses obtained from milk or buttermilk that submitted to thermal treatment (Reg. 2073/2005; Reg.CE 1441/2007).

The diagnosis procedure is achieved in conformity with SR ISO 16649 – 2:2007, a horizontal method for enumerating positive *E. coli* at β – glucuronidasis from products

disease being taken into consideration since 1980.

Vero toxins are among the strongest known biologic substances, toxic for cells from pico to

nanomolar concentrations (Palmer S.R., Soulsby E.J.L., Simpson D.I.H., 2005).

designed for human consumption at 44 oC, using 5 – brome – 4 – Clorox – 3 indolil β – D – glucuronat (TBX), a solid environment that contains a chromogeneous ingredient to detect the β – glucuronidasis chromate. *E. coli* stems that do not develop at 44°C and especially the negative ones at β – glucuronidasis, *E. coli* O157, cannot be detected.

E. coli positive at β – glucuronidasis – bacteria which, at 44°C, form typically blue colonies on tripton – bile – glucuronat (TBX) environment (fig. 3).

a.

b.

Fig. 3 - *E. coli* positive at β – glucuronidasis

Consequently to the made analyses, there have been obtained the following results (table 4).

Table 4. Results obtained after detecting *Escherichia coli* positive at β – glucuronidasis

No.	Sorts of examined cheeses	Sample number			Non-pasteurized milk				Pasteurized milk			
		Total	Non-pasteurized milk	Pasteurized milk	C		N		C		N	
					No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
1	„Burduf” cheese	16	4	12	2	50,0	2	50,0	8	66,7	4	33,3
2	Soft cow cheese	3	1	2	1	100	-	-	1	50,0	1	50,0
3	Cow fresh cottage cheese	21	6	15	6	100	-	-	12	80,0	3	20,0
4	Cow matured cottage cheese	6	4	2	3	75,0	1	25,0	2	100	-	-
5	Ewe's fresh cottage cheese	19	6	13	6	100	-	-	9	69,2	4	30,8

6	Ewe's matured cottage cheese	8	7	1	7	100	-	-	1	100	-	-
7	Mixed fresh cottage cheese	3	1	3	1	100	-	-	3	100	-	-
8	Mixed matured cottage cheese	1	1	-	1	100	-	-	-	-	-	-
9	Goat fresh cottage cheese	2	-	2	-	-	-	-	1	50,0	1	50,0
10	Cow whey	12	7	5	5	71,4	2	28,6	4	80,0	1	20,0
11	Ewe's whey	7	7	-	7	100	-	-	-	-	-	-
12	Mixed whey – cow/ewe	4	4	-	4	100	-	-	-	-	-	-
	TOTAL	102	47	55	43	91,5	4	8,5	41	74,5	14	25,5

It is observed that cheeses produced from non-pasteurized milk have been non-congruous at the parameter *Escherichia coli* positive at β – glucuronidasis in a percentage of 8,5%, while cheeses produced from pasteurized milk have been non congruent in a percentage of 25,5%.

On sorts, there are observed significant percentages of non-congruence at “burduf”cheeses obtained from non-pasteurized milk, soft cow cheese obtained from pasteurized cheese, goat fresh cottage cheese obtained from pasteurized – 50% from the total of examined samples.

The presence of coli form bacteria denotes milk non corresponding pasteurization – raw matter, and conditions of non-satisfying hygiene.

4. CONCLUSIONS

1. Cheese contamination with bacteria of *Staphylococcus* type is largely a result of human contact. In agri-touristic farms and mountain households it must be minimized by implementing good processing and manipulation practice and microorganism development must be avoided through appropriate temperature control. There is imminently imposed the achievement of a quality unitary system / QS, which may give coherence to existing regulations together with the stipulated or to be stipulated traditional product standards.

2. From all the non-congruent samples, in which have been detected bacteria from the *Staphylococcus* type, there have been isolated positive coagulate staphylococcus 25,5%. Cheeses produced from non-pasteurized milk have been non-congruent at *Staphylococcus* parameter 39,2%, while cheeses produced from

pasteurized milk have been non-congruent 33,8%, which indicates milk deficient pasteurization or contamination / recontamination after processing at all sorts. Except for ewe's matured cottage cheese, with only 8,3% non-congruent samples from non-pasteurized milk. There must also be observed the non-congruence diminishing to half in case of “burduf”cheese

from pasteurized milk face to the one made of non-pasteurized milk.

3. *Staphylococcus enterotoxin* has been detected in 7,1% from the number of samples in which there have been detected bacteria of the *Staphylococcus* type and in 28% of the samples, in which have been detected positive coagulate staphylococcus. The highest non-congruence percentage has been registered at cheeses obtained from pasteurized milk – 33,3%, while, at cheeses obtained from non-pasteurized milk, the enterotoxin has been present in 25,0%, fact that demonstrates that enterotoxin has been produced by staphylococcus before submitting milk to the pasteurization process, and the applied temperature has not influenced its level. It is not excluded milk contamination with positive coagulate *Staphylococcus* after pasteurization, consequently to non respecting hygiene conditions over the processing. On sorts, there has been observed the fact that the highest non-congruence percentage has been at “burduf” cheese obtained from non-pasteurized milk (40,0%).

4. Cheeses produced from non-pasteurized milk have been non-congruent at *Escherichia coli* positive at β – glucuronidasis parameter in a share of 8,5%, while cheeses produced by

pasteurized milk have been non-congruent 25,5%. On sorts, there are observed significant non-congruous percentages at "burudf"cheese obtained from non-pasteurized milk, soft cow cheese obtained from pasteurized milk, goat fresh cottage cheese got from pasteurized milk (50% from the total of examined samples). The presence of coli form bacteria denotes milk non-corresponding pasteurization as raw material, as well as hygiene non-satisfactory conditions.

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HYGIENIC ENGINEERING AND DESIGN IN ROMANIA

Liviu GACEU¹

Abstract: *The aim of this study is to present the potential and the opportunities regarding EHEDG subsection in Romania. Starting from statistic data fo results of: 10 top food and drink sub-sectors in the region (by turnover); 10 top food and drink companies; Imports (in €m) and ranking of 10 top import/export countries (by %); Exports(in €m) and ranking of 10 top import/export countries (by %) it was emphasised the features and characteristics of EHEDG forum. Some of them are: identifying areas where knowledge of hygienic design is insufficient; filling the existing gaps and lack of know-how by practical guidelines and education; offering expertise, networking and further development in the fields of hygienic engineering & design and safe food production; preparing scientific and technical guidelines on all aspects of state-of-the-art hygienic design requirements in accordance to EU legislation; developing test methods in order to identify and reduce hazards of equipment used in food production; strengthening the participation in standardisation bodies like CEN, ISO, DIN, JIS, 3-A, NSF etc.; strengthening the cooperation with the EU (i.e. food contact material directive, BAT, traceability and other EU-Projects) as well as with other organisations; encouraging research and development in the field of hygienic design; promoting and disseminating hygienic design know-how by all kinds of digital and print media, congresses, seminars and other events on an international and local level. The conclusions shows that the formation of an EHEDG Regional Section for the Romania would provide a much needed platform to disseminate knowledge on Hygienic Engineering to a wide variety of food and equipment manufacturers with bases in different countries*

Keywords: *hygienic engineering and design in Romania.*

1. Introduction

Following rapid economic growth in the 2000s, Romania has an economy predominantly based on services, and is a producer and net exporter of machines and electric energy.

Agriculture is an important factor in the national economy, with a contribution of 7% of the GDP (compared to 2% EU average).

The number of people employed in agriculture represents 29% of Romania's population, one of the highest rates of employment in this sector in Europe.

The main agricultural crops are cereals, oilseeds, sugar beet, potatoes, vegetables, fruit and grapes. Livestock consists of swine, cattle, sheep and goats.

The food industry is the largest manufacturing in Romania. It is a market of 10 billion euros with almost 200,000 employees. Contribution to GDP is 8%.

There are more than 10,000 Romanian producers who process organic vegetables agricultural products.

Organic growth farms or animals have developed, especially in the sheep and goats sector, while the number of meat processing units in organic base has doubled to more than 70 in the last years.

Most companies in the food industry are foreign owned, top 10 companies have a market share of 18.8% and they have different fields: beverage processing, meat processing, refined oil and sugar processing.

There are: Coca Cola HBC Romania, Ursus Breweries, Bunge Romania, Expur Sa, Heineken Romania, Agrana Romania, Smithfield Prod, Prutul SA, Unicarm SRL, Nestle Romania.

Romanian exports of agricultural products increased their share in total exports from less than 5% in 2007 to nearly 9% in 2011. Over those five years, the agro food exports have increased more than 3 times, surpassing 3.9

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billion euros in 2011, while imports of food grain were up 30%.

Organic agricultural exports have reached over 100 million euros annually, which places Romania in the top 20 of world exporters of such products. The main markets for organic agricultural products originating in Romania are: Austria, Germany, France, Italy, Denmark and Switzerland.

Exports of agricultural commodities (almost 60% of total Romanian exports of agricultural products and foodstuffs) are represented, mainly cereals (wheat and maize), oilseeds (sunflower seed and rapeseed), tobacco and fats and oils. Food and agriculture exports are diversified, covering a wide range - from live animals, meat and meat or tobacco products, to cheese and dairy products, sugar and sugary foods or drinks.

The biggest markets for agricultural and food products exported by Romania in 2011 and the main categories of products delivered in these markets were Italy (cigarettes, wheat and corn, sunflowers, sheep and cattle, mushrooms) - 13.3% of the total export, Hungary and Bulgaria (refined sugar, poultry, sunflower oil and margarine) - 10.4% and 9.4%, Netherlands (sunflower and rapeseed, corn and wheat, oil sunflower, cigarettes, poultry) - 7.6% and Germany (cigarettes, rape, maize and wheat, various food preparations, sunflower oil) - 7.2%.

Romanian exports of agricultural commodities accounted for almost 32% of total imports of agricultural and food products in 2011, the rest being covered by imports of processed food and agriculture.

The product categories with the highest imports were: pork and poultry, raw sugar and refined grains (wheat and maize), fodder and food for pets, fruits (citrus, bananas, apples and pears),

vegetables (tomatoes and peppers) and frozen vegetables, oilseeds, various food preparations, cheese

Top five foreign suppliers of agricultural and food products on the Romanian market in 2011 and the main categories of products delivered were: Hungary (cereals, pork and turkey, sunflower oil, feed and fodder, dairy products) - 16.1% of total imports, Germany (pork and chicken, cheese, cigarettes, bakery and bakery, food preparations for babies - 12.1%, Bulgaria (oilseeds, cereals, refined sugar, poultry, chocolate and cheese) - 10.9%, Brazil (meat, coffee, raw sugar and refined feed and forage, tobacco and tobacco products) - 7.4% and the Netherlands (pork and poultry, ornamental plants and cut flowers miscellaneous food preparations, fruits and vegetables) - 6.6%.

Sanitary and Veterinary National Authority and for Food safety (ANSVSA) <http://www.ansvsa.ro/> ANSVSA is responsible for food safety and food hygiene across Romania. It works with local authorities to enforce food safety regulations and have staff who work in Romanian meat plants to check that the requirements of the regulations are being met. It also commissions research related to food safety.

The Framework Directive EC 1935/2004, the Machinery Directive EC 2006/42, Good Manufacturing Practice EC 2023/2006 and the Food Hygiene Regulations EC 852/2004 are all embodied in Romanian legislation.

There are over 10 EHEDG member companies which have bases in Romania; names such as ACO, Air Products, BASF, BP, Campden BRI, GEA, Heinz, Holchem, the Nickel Institute, MAFF, Mondelez etc

Table 1. Ranking of 10 top food and drink sub-sectors in the region (by turnover).

No.	Name	Turnover (Mil EUR)
1.	MILLING AND BAKERY	2.100
2.	JUICE	2.000
3.	BEER	1.500
4.	MILK	950
5.	MEAT	900
6	WINE	750

7.	MEAT PROCESSING & SAUGAGES	700
8.	FOOD GRADE OIL	200
9.	NATURAL JUICE	120
10.	SUGAR	80

2. Statistics regarding food and drink sectors

In order to evaluate the potential and opportunities in Romania regarding the the establishment of an EHEDG subsection, relevant data were collected. These are:

- 10 top food and drink sub-sectors in the region (by turnover);
- 10 top food and drink companies;

- Imports (in €m) and ranking of 10 top import/export countries (by %);
- Exports (in €m) and ranking of 10 top import/export countries (by %).

In this analysis, it shows the potential of agri-food development in Romania and, thus, the requirement of hygienic design in technology, equipments, curricula, legislation.

Table 2. Ranking of 10 top food and drink companies (by turnover).

No.	Name	Turnover [lei]	Turnover (EUR)
1.	COCA COLA HBC ROMANIA SRL	1.831.649.673	407.033.260.6
2.	URSUS BREWERIES SA	1.416.189.433	314.708.762.8
3.	BUNGE ROMANIA SRL	1.258.063.373	279.569.638.4
4.	EXPUR SA	1.098.758.653	244.168.589,6
5.	HEINEKEN ROMANIA SA	1.084.830.083	241.073.351.7
6.	AGRANA ROMANIA SA	955.742.303	212.387.178,4
7.	SMITHFIELD PROD SRL	800.726.267	177.939.170,4
8.	PRUTUL SA	745.775.493	165.727.887,3
9.	UNICARM SRL	662.386.755	147.197.056,7
10.	NESTLE ROMANIA SRL	644.948.823	143.321.960,7

Table 3. Imports (in €m) and ranking of 10 top import/export countries (by %).

No.	Import market 2014 Total=3.993,5 Mil Eur	Value (Mil Eur)	Percent (%)
1.	ITALY	531.4	13.3
2.	HUNGARY	414.5	10.4
3.	BULGARIA	375.7	9.4
4.	HOLLAND	304.4	7.6

5.	GERMANY	287.2	7.2
6.	SPAIN	205.1	5.1
7.	TURKEY	196.5	4.9
8.	GREECE	163.7	4.1
9.	FRANCE	159.4	4.0
10.	BELGIUM	135.6	3.4

Table 4. Exports (in €m) and ranking of 10 top import/export countries (by %).

No.	Export market 2014 Total=4.427,6 Mil Eur	Value (Mil Eur)	Percent (%)
1.	HUNGARY	713.9	16.1
2.	GERMANY	544.3	12.3
3.	BULGARIA	484.7	10.9
4.	BRASIL	329.7	7.4
5.	HOLLAND	291.5	6.6
6.	POLAND	290.0	6.5
7.	ITALY	272.2	6.1
8.	FRANCE	152.0	3.4
9.	AUSTRIA	136.4	3.1
10.	SPAIN	107.1	2.4

3. EHEDG features and guidelines

EHEDG provides a balanced forum for food processing equipment manufacturers, users and legislators to discuss issues concerning hygienic design and to stimulate food safety and quality by:

- identifying areas where knowledge of hygienic design is insufficient;
- filling the existing gaps and lack of know-how by practical guidelines and education;
- offering expertise, networking and further development in the fields of hygienic engineering & design and safe food production;
- preparing scientific and technical guidelines on all aspects of state-of-the-art hygienic design requirements in accordance to EU legislation;
- developing test methods in order to identify and reduce hazards of equipment used in food production;
- offering training courses, seminars and workshops;
- strengthening the participation in standardisation bodies like CEN, ISO, DIN, JIS, 3-A, NSF etc.;
- strengthening the cooperation with the EU (i.e. food contact material directive, BAT, traceability and other EU-Projects) as well as with other organisations;

- encouraging research and development in the field of hygienic design;
- promoting and disseminating hygienic design know-how by all kinds of digital and print media, congresses, seminars and other events on an international and local level;
- making sure that the use of the EHEDG name and logo is properly controlled.

Assurance of quality and safety is an essential need for the continued good reputation of foodstuffs. The correct hygienic design and maintenance of food production systems is considered as a prerequisite to fulfill these requirements.

In order to offer help to the industry in these questions, EHEDG has developed and published a variety of practical guidance documents on adequate hygienic design in different areas of food production equipment and machinery, as well as on the food manufacturing infrastructure. Titles available are listed below, while others are currently in progress to complement the EHEDG document series. The following list of guidelines is regularly updated and completed by new documents in various language versions:

<http://www.ehedg.org/vodii/>

1. Microbiologically safe continuous pasteurization of liquid food;
2. A method for assessing the in-place cleanability of food processing equipment;
3. Microbiologically safe aseptic packing of food products;
4. A method for the assessment of in-line pasteurisation of food processing equipment;
5. A method for the assessment of in-line sterilisability of food processing equipment;
6. The microbiologically safe continuous flow thermal sterilisation of liquid foods
7. A method for the assessment of bacteria-tightness of food processing equipment
8. Hygienic equipment design criteria
9. Welding stainless steel to meet hygienic requirements
10. Hygienic design of closed equipment for the processing of liquid food
11. Hygienic packing of food products
12. The continuous or semi-continuous flow thermal treatment of particulate foods
13. Hygienic design of equipment for open processing;
14. Hygienic design of valves for food processing;
15. A method for the assessment of in-place cleanability of moderately sized food processing equipment;
16. Hygienic pipe couplings;
17. Hygienic design of pumps, homogenizers and dampening devices;
18. Chemical Treatment of Stainless Steel Surfaces;
19. A method for assessing the bacterial impermeability of hydrophobic membrane filters;
20. Hygienic design and safe use of double-seat mixproof valves;
21. Challenge tests for the evaluation of the hygienic characteristics of packing machines for liquid and semi-liquid products;
22. General hygienic design criteria for the safe processing of dry particulate materials;
23. Production and use of food-grade lubricants, Part 1;
24. Production and use of food-grade lubricants, Part 2;
25. The prevention and control of Legionella spp. (incl legionnaires disease) in food factories;
26. Design of mechanical seals for hygienic and aseptic applications
27. Hygienic engineering of plants for the processing of dry particulate materials
28. Safe storage and distribution of water in food factories
29. Safe and hygienic water treatment in food factories
30. Hygienic design of packing systems for solid foodstuffs
31. Guidelines on air handling in the food industry
32. Hygienic engineering of fluid bed and spray dryer plants
33. Materials of construction for equipment in contact with food
34. Hygienic engineering of discharging systems for dry particulate materials
35. Integration of hygienic and aseptic systems
36. Hygienic welding of stainless steel tubing in the food processing industry
37. Hygienic Engineering of Transfer Systems for Dry Particulate Materials
38. Hygienic Design and Application of Sensors
39. Hygienic Engineering of Rotary Valves in Process Lines for Dry Particulate Materials
40. Design Principles for Equipment and Process Areas for Aseptic Food Manufacturing
41. Hygienic Engineering of Valves in Process Lines for Dry Particulate Materials
42. Hygienic Engineering of Diverter Valves in Process Lines for Dry Particulate Materials
43. Disc Stack Centrifuges - Design and Cleanability

44. Hygienic Design of Belt Conveyors for the Food Industry
45. Hygienic Design Principles for Food Factories
46. Cleaning Validation in the Food Industry - General Principles, Part 1
47. Guidelines on Air Handling Systems in the Food Industry - Air Quality Control for Building Ventilation

4. Results and discussion

The formation of an EHEDG Regional Section for the Romania would provide a much needed platform to disseminate knowledge on Hygienic Engineering to a wide variety of food and equipment manufacturers with bases in those countries. Compliance with legislation is also a high priority for all food businesses and the Regional Section would provide a focal point to provide up to date practical knowledge and expertise for the implementation of hygienic design principles to improve food safety. The absence of any formalised training courses or specific qualifications in Hygienic Engineering would also present an excellent opportunity for the Romanian Regional Section to provide ratified EHEDG training courses and liaise with Universities and Colleges to implement specific hygienic engineering design modules into Food Engineering course curricula. EHEDG provides a standard European platform for training and education in hygienic engineering and design, based on training modules which are summarizing the key knowledge of the EHEDG guidelines and other EHEDG publications. International EHEDG training courses in English language and national EHEDG courses in local language are offered several times a year at various locations in Europe and overseas.

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ROMANIAN ORGANIC FOOD – STUDY ON CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR

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Abstract: *The aim of this study is to present the results of the research conducted in order to establish the factors that influence the Romanian consumers' behaviour regarding organic food products. As a result, a behavioural model of the Romanian consumer was realised. It can serve as a base for marketing policy-making by organic food business operators. The method of investigation was the questionnaire-interview. The statistical analysis shows that three groups of organic food consumers can be delineated: non-consumers, every day consumers and occasional consumers of organic food products. Based on the results of the conducted study, a sequence of conclusions turned out to be helpful to the stakeholders on the Romanian organic food market.*

Keywords: *consumer, organic food, behaviour, marketing research*

1. Introduction

Organic farming is likely to receive a major boost in the European Union and most probably also worldwide since consumers have lost some trust in food derived from conventional production. The large increase in organic farming have increased due to a variety of factors: (i) to preserve the earning capability of farmers in a world that needs less producers to feed the well-fed part of the world's population; (ii) to preserve the rural countryside as it is; (iii) to use cultivation methods that will conserve the soil and contribute to sustainability (Siderer & al., 2005 [1]). The attitude of consumers towards organic food is in general positive with typically associated benefits such as superior taste, more environmental-friendliness, improved health, safer food products, and animal welfare (Rödiger & Hamm, 2015 [2]). A frequently reported reason for not buying organic food was price, since it was usually premium priced (Marian & al., 2014 [3]).

Organic food has thus gained a significant place in the public discourse as well as in political strategies for agricultural development. Consumption has a central role in this new quality food policy, and this is reflected in the political objectives on organic farming (Vittersø & Tangeland, 2015 [4]).

By definition, organic foods are not genetically modified and are produced specifically without the application of synthetic chemicals such as pesticides or fertilisers. Specifically, organic food include less harmful additives and more primary nutrients (vitamin C, dry matter, minerals) and secondary nutrients (such as phyto-nutrients) than traditional foods (Hsu & Chen, 2014 [5]). Numerous researchers (Grankvist & Biel, 2001 [6]; Lee & al., 2013 [7]) indicated that consumers perceive foods labelled as organic to be healthier than traditional foods. Between the sensory aspects of food (like taste, texture characteristics, odour) and the impact of non-food effects (like cognitive information, social factors, physical environment), human food choice is difficult. Although various models represent the complexity of food choice behaviour (Gifford & Bernard, 2006 [8]; Zander & Hamm, 2012 [9]), little research has investigated the impact of the regulatory fit effect, especially associated with organic food choice.

Consumers combine information about product attributes and consequences to evaluate a product and make their choices. They rely on their felt involvement which is influenced by their experience. The importance placed on each parameter is based on the consumers' priorities and values (Shafie & Rennie, 2012 [10]).

Demographic variables as well as lifestyle and environmental attitudes define the organic consumer profile. Regular consumers of organic food tend to be educated, affluent and of higher social class (Stobelaar & al., 2006 [11]). Awareness of food hazards and knowledge of food hazards were higher among females and individuals with more education and income (Shafie & Rennie, 2012 [10]). Lockie & al., 2002 [12] also found strong correlation between increasing consumption of organic food and levels of formal education. Regarding the price of organic food products, organic consumers are willing to pay approximately 10% premium for organic food with an average of 9.5% by women and 11.4% by men. Regular consumers would pay a slightly higher premium around 15%, an average of 12/6% by women and 18% by men (Urena & al., 2008 [13]).

The literature on organic products is poor in informations regarding Central Eastern Europe (Radman, 2005 [14]). In the same time, the literature concerning the organic food market in Romania is also limited with most studies focusing on food production (Gurau & Ranchhod, 2005 [15]), rather than consumer behaviour (Arvanitoyannis & Krystallis, 2006 [16]).

The present study focuses on Romania's case related to the organic food market potential. It is important to understand which factors contribute to the low demand levels of organic products on this market. What factors might motivate Romanian food shoppers to purchase organic food products rather than conventional food products, if any?

In order to investigate this market opportunity, the current situation in the Romanian organic food market is analysed. The focus is on consumer understanding, attitudes and perceptions regarding organic products, the perceived benefits, and finally consumer motivations to purchase organic rather than conventional food.

The purpose of this study was to identify what are food shoppers' perceptions on organic food products in Bucharest, Romania. In the analysis, both qualitative and quantitative techniques were employed.

2. Materials and methods

In this analysis, the population is comprised of food shoppers that live in Bucharest, the capital city of Romania. The criteria for this study are

drawn using age, family lifecycle, income and education level, as well as residency.. All the research participants are permanent residents of Bucharest. They were assured of both the anonymity and confidentiality of given data, and that the results would not be used for other purposes, according to the Market Research Society Code of Conduct.

The questionnaire based survey was conducted in Bucharest, on a representative sample of 1300 food shoppers. The target population comprised of all persons over 18 years old who are responsible for the shopping activities within their household (i.e. food shoppers) and who, at the time of the survey, were living anywhere in Bucharest.

The face-to-face interviews were conducted on high traffic streets in the city centre of Bucharest. The questionnaire was designed based on the reviewed literature and on the findings of the qualitative research. The sample size was of 1300 respondents with 1251 valid responses.

Quantitative surveys based on questionnaires are the most common way to assess the different factors affecting consumers' food choice (Steptoe & al., 1995 [17]). A set of relevant statements is presented to respondents based on literature and identified via the qualitative research. A five-point Likert (agree/ disagree) scale was used (Kotler, 1972 [18]; Honkanen & al., 2006 [19]).

The items in a scale should be strongly correlated with the latent variable (Hair & al., 1998 [20]). If this condition is true then the items within a scale should be strongly correlated with each other. Nevertheless, given the exploratory nature of this study, the scale proved to be unreliable.

The questionnaire comprises three sections: questions on consumption behaviour, a multidimensional scale on attitudes of organic food with five constructs and demographic questions (Steptoe & al., 1995 [17]; Lockie & al., 2002 [21]).

The data analysis was carried out using the SPSS 17.0 for Windows statistical program package.

Factor and cluster analyses were performed based on the responses given on the five-point Likert scale, at a significance level of 5 percent. The factor analysis is a technique whose objectives are to identify a smaller set of underlying dimensions which explain the inter-relationships among a large set of metric variables with a minimum loss of information. It achieves data reduction so that the original set of

variables is replaced by a smaller number of factors (Hair & al., 1998 [20]). The factors are used as variables for the subsequent analysis – the cluster analysis. This analysis is a multivariate technique for groups responses with similar profiles on a defined set of characteristics (Popa, 2008 [22]; Varga, 2009 [23]). The applications of cluster analysis are market segmentation, positioning and targeting, new product development, and test markets' selection (Hair & al., 1998 [20]).

3. Results and discussion

(a) Exploratory factor analysis using Varimax factors rotation method

The third section of the questionnaire (Annex 1) comprised of 30 affirmations regarding consumer behaviour on organic food market, which were submitted to statistical processing using factorial analysis, cluster analysis, Chi-square test of association and Chi-square test for the corresponding degree. The 30 affirmations are further referred as variables.

The factorial analysis was conducted by processing the obtained data and information from the questionnaire, third section, from the 1251 respondents, using the SPSS 17.0 software.

The statistical processing conducted with SPSS 17.0 software comprises two main parts:

- exploratory factor analysis by using Varimax factors rotation method;
- cluster analysis, using the following processing techniques: Chi and Chi-square tests.

The factor analysis uses two methods to determine the factors which are: primary component analysis method - Hotteling and common factors analysis method - Thurstone. In our case, we adopted the primary component analysis method - Hotteling, which looks for and extracts in successive stages the largest linear correlation between variables, every step meaning the identification of a factor. The values of the extracted factors are then used as variables for cluster analysis where the data needs to be organized in form of a matrix where "the cases" are on the line and "the variables" are on the columns.

The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett test of sphericity are two statistical tests that indicate the degree of association between the variables. High values, closed to 1 and significant, represent a favourable argument for the existence of some factors and so for the

legitimacy factor analysis on that data. 0.8 rounded value of KMO is suggesting one or more common factors, which justifies the application of a procedure of factor reduction (Varga, 2009 [23]).

One of the major problems of the analysis consists in obtaining a maximum variation at factor level, based on the combined variables. For obtaining that effect, the calculus program that was used permits a rotation of the variables variation space, i.e. a rotation of the graphical representation space so the original Ox axis could approximate itself the regression line. This type of rotation follows the maximization of the variation (variability) of the factor named "varimax". Its complementary aim is to reduce the variance of the values that are not part of the factor.

The primary components analysis implies the extraction of all the possible factors with the help of a numeric index, frequently used with this purpose, Eigenvalue index which can be calculated as a sum of the determination coefficients (r^2), between each factor and the variables that enter into its composition, eventually those factors which satisfy the condition that the Eigenvalue index value to be greater or equal to 1 being kept. In our case, the 30 variables designed to study the organic products consumer behaviour were cumulated based on the meanings and resulted the 8 factors, which together explain 51,021% from the variation of the analyzed values.

The degree of reduction of the obtained data is 74%. The percentage of the variation of a variable explained by reunited factors that indicates the indicator's safety represented by that variable was pretty low.

The data based on the Varimax method allows final conclusions regarding the factorial structure of the variables analyzed, such as:

- Factor 1 – The consistency of taste: it is mainly composed of variables related to satiety and taste;
- Factor 2 – Natural food products, uncertified: it explains the affirmations linked to consumer perception that the products produced and sold by farmers are organic products, uncertified ;
- Factor 3 – Ethical benefits: this lane? explains the affirmations that refers to the primary benefits of organic products, namely health and environment protection;
- Factor 4 – Snobbism: composed mainly of the variables linked to an eventual snobbism effect of organic food products consumption, in this case perceived as luxury products;

- Factor 5 – Accessibility : explains the affirmations that refer to the market disponibility for the organic food products and having a good good quality / price report;

- Factor 6 – Lack of familiarization: composed mainly of variables linked to the level of familiarization with organic food products category;

- Factor 7 – Ignorance: explains the affirmations that refer to the level of information and promotion of organic market;

- Factor 8 – Skepticism: composed of variables linked to lack of trust in organic food product concept.

Based on the data processing and as a result of the analysis of Varimax Table, a series of interesting and useful conclusions have emerged. First of all, it confirms the fact that the organic food products market is based on a group of loyal consumers, that acknowledges and appreciates the sensory and nutritional characteristics of organic food products and in the same time they are satisfied that organic products are more filling and even tastier than the conventional ones.

The group of loyal consumers have enough information and appreciate the diversity of organic food on the Romanian market with the price / quality ratio being fair.

According to the Varimax Table it appears that the group of non-buyers of organic products is based on the fact that they consider that natural products can be considered uncertified organic products and can be purchased from the local farmers or even produced in their own household (rural) at more affordable prices.

The data from Varimax table shows that the group of occasional users did not make a habit of consuming organic products for reasons of convenience or simply do not find their favorite products in organic version. They say that they don't believe that there really are organic products but instead recognize they do not have enough information about organic food products. They consider that the organic products were not aggressively promoted, but they are interested to know more issues which will determine them to consume organic food products in the future.

(b) Cluster Analysis

Cluster analysis was performed in order to identify the market segments. For this purpose the scores from factor analysis previously presented were used. Before presenting the results and conclusions of the cluster analysis, we will present some important outlines.

The cluster analysis is a multivariate technique that analyzes the possibility of grouping objects, then the analyst will choose not only the method of analysis but also the grouping solution that he considers appropriate. Cluster analysis is used in marketing for market segmentation, for positioning and orientation, new product development and testing selected markets (Hair & al., 1998 [20]).

The Chi-square test is used to highlight the degree of association between two categorical variables with the following conditions: categorical variables can be expressed either by numerical values or by string values (printable character); the two variables can not "intersect" (there must be no subjects included in more than one cell of the table); the expected frequency values not less than 5 (or at least in no more than 20% of the cells); there should be no cells with the expected frequency 0.

The Chi-square test is used for the degree of correlation when comparing the observed rates of a single categorical variable, with its expected frequencies, that are previously known.

Three significant groups of respondents were established by the k-means method, each one with 342 (27,3%), 381 (30,5%) and 528 (42,2%) respondents. The k-means method is an iterative group method, that starts from a fixed number of clusters established by the researcher to suit large amounts of data analysing.

The profiling of each consumer, from each of the three groups, was based on factor scores for each group and contingency tables with behavioural and demographic variables for which there were significant differences between groups based on chi-square test, at a level of significant variation of 5%.

From the analysis of the cluster centers and from the contingency tables we can observe the profiles of the three formed segments.

The occasional consumer represented 528 of persons from a total of 1251 interviewed persons, which present a low interest towards organic food products compared to the other two consumer groups. Anyway, the highest proportion of 34.5% (i.e. 182 people), preffer to go shopping once a week, while 34,1% (i.e. 180 people) go shopping 2-3 times a week.

Group 1 consist of non-buyers of organic products, who perceive certified foods as luxury products for snobs and believe that products bought from peasants or farmers, in general, are as natural and organic as certified organic products. This way we can explain why these

consumers do not purchase labeled organic food products: they are not willing to pay extra for certification, faith in rural production quality being very strong.

Group 2 represents the usual consumers of organic food products, who became loyal to these products due to product quality, especially at sensorial level.

Group 3 is represented by occasional buyers of organic food products who know the health and environmental benefits, but still retain a slight skepticism about the method of production, information on the label and certification schemes. They also buy such products that they feel are handy, in terms of quality - price ratio and the market availability of a variety of organic food products alternatives (at least at perception level).

Contingency tables with the 29 behavioural and demographic variables were performed to identify possible groups descriptors. From 29 variables, six of them proved to have statistical significance for the presented study.

Thus, these variables are: purchase frequency, initial source of information about organic food products, organic products consumption in general, organic milk consumption, consumer label use and age at time of study.

The non-buyers group (Group 1) represented by 342 people from a total of 1251 interviewed people, are very involved in household shopping, more than once per week, at a rate of 29.5%, which means 101 people. They also recorded the highest percentage (42.1% i.e. 144 persons) of weekly shopping. These results may show the inclination of Group 1 to visit the traditional trade more than other consumer groups.

The segment of the consumers of organic food products presents a more varied behaviour, exactly 23,4% of them are going shopping only 2-3 times a week, 37,8% are going shopping weekly, and 26,5% are going shopping even more than once a week.

For all three groups of consumers, the TV shows regarding organic food products consumption represented the primary source of information, followed by internet and point of sale advertising. Moreover, occasional users seem most receptive to promote organic products at the point of sale (15%) which may indicate that they buy organic products in momentum, as the decision is made on the shelves, out of curiosity.

It emerged the fact that milk and dairy products represents the most consumed organic food category, with a slight difference between segments: loyal consumers consume in proportion of 64.8% versus 53.4% for occasional users.

In general, consumers read the information on the packaging only partially (62%), but the consumers of organic foods group tend to give greater importance to this information, using the label every time, at a rate of 32%. In

general, consumers consume organic food less than once a month or never at a rate of nearly 50%. However, according to the segmentation above, there are some differences between the three groups: Group 1 has the highest rate of non-consumer (48%), Group 2 consumes most often (63%) and Group 3 consumes up to 2-3 times a month, in general (70%). On one hand young people aged 18-24 years are more curious and open to new things than other categories of consumers and on the other hand, they are the most financially constrained, this being the main reason they are found in a high percentage in the non-consumer group (42.7%). After analyzing the contingency tables, the group profiles can be resumed as presented in Table 1. It can be concluded that cluster analysis clearly revealed three groups of buyers: the first one - consumers that do not buy organic food products, the second one - the loyal buyers of organic food products and the third one - the occasional buyers of organic food products.

Table 1. Organic food market segmentation (consumer profile groups)

Profile variable	Number and group size		
	1 (27,3 %)	2 (30,5 %)	3 (42,2 %)
Group name →	<i>Non-buyers</i>	<i>Loyal buyers</i>	<i>Occasional buyers</i>
Factor scores (the level of a certain perception in the consumers mind)			
Consistency taste	neutral	strong perception	disagreement
Uncertified natural Foods	strong perception	neutral	disagreement
Ethical benefits	neutral	disagreement	strong perception
Snobbism	strong perception	neutral	disagreement

Accessibility	disagreement	neutral	strong perception
Lack of familiarization	strong perception	disagreement	neutral
Ignorance	disagreement	neutral	strong perception
Skepticism	disagreement	neutral	strong perception
Consumer Behaviour			
Frequency of purchase	more often	once a week	rarely
Frequency of consumption eco	almost never	weekly	occasional
Source of information	TV sows	media and Internet promotion	Internet promotion and point of sale promotion
Use of the label	partially	allways	partially
Demographic Profile			
Age	over 35 years	25-34 years	18-24 years

To make a comparison with other research results, we mention that in 2009 a similar study was conducted by the Centre for Rural Economy (CER) on consumer perception towards organic products in Romania and China. This study outlined the organic food consumer profile, being "informed, educated, who has knowledge about organic products, diets and their impact on health, has a monthly income above average, afford to pay a higher price and take their time to seek these products". In both countries, participants in the study, both consumers and non-consumers associate organic food products with health. They believe that organic products are expensive being considered luxury products that address to a narrow segment of the population, and the supply is insufficient, with a reduced and inaccessible variety of products. Contrary to the results obtained in our study, CER follows the fact that there is a lack of trust in the certification of products and in the veracity of their labels.

4. Conclusions

After studying the profiles of the interviewees we found that they fall into three representative groups: non-buyers group, the group of loyal consumers of organic products and occasional buyers of organic food products group, each of these groups being characterized by certain dominant traits;

The non-buyers group of organic products is made up of people who are involved in the household shopping, going once or more than once per week for shopping but have not yet determined the difference between natural and ecological product, preferring to buy products from farmers, being also cheaper than those that are certified as organic products, the latter being considered luxury products, that they believe to

have the same benefits essentially; the group of loyal consumers is composed of people who have enough information about organic products and have formed a true image about them, being aware of the cost-benefit ratio and became loyal consumers of such products; the group of occasional users go shopping once a week or less often but is still slightly more responsive and knows the benefits of eating organic foods, but sometimes is influenced by price, income, convenience, accessibility, factors that decrease the frequency of consumption of these products. Another feature of this group is its flexibility, making it easier to be influenced, a big impact being held by the promotion at the point of sale, which can influence them to buy such products out of curiosity; a very important category of consumers has proven to be represented by young people aged between 18-24 years, which although they are most receptive and flexible thanks to modern mentality and easy access to information constituting the biggest group of consumers of organic food products, both loyal and casual, they however are constrained by financial instability and also occupies much of the non-buyers group; as is well known in Romania the standard average living is low and the monthly average income is generally between 1001 and 5000 RON/household (section 2 - 3 of the questionnaire), which doesn't satisfy basic needs to a higher level of quality, and this fact reduces the consumption potential of organic food for the time. Summarising the results and conclusions following the marketing research that we conducted with the aim of shaping a behaviour model of the Romanian consumer of organic products, we can say that the organic products market dynamics in Romania is moderate and restrained by economic factors (significantly lower income per person than the

average income per person in the European Union), by social factors (traditionalist spirit and reserved towards new of the Romanian consumer) and even political factors (reduced stimulation of the state towards production of organic agricultural products) and reduced promotion of healthy food education with the addition of environmental protection.

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Annex 1.

The questionnaire developed and used for the research conducted in order to determine consumer perceptions of food products

Secțiunea 3: ATITUDINILE FAȚĂ DE ALIMENTELE ECOLOGICE						
Nr. crt.	Afirmații:	Dezacord	Dezacord	Indecis	Acord	Acord
		tot 1	2	N/A	4	total
		1	2	3	4	5
1	Consumul de produse agroalimentare ecologice contribuie la menținerea sănătății umane	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
2	Consumul de produse agroalimentare ecologice contribuie la protejarea mediului	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
3	Produsele agroalimentare ecologice sunt mai gustoase decât produsele convenționale	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
4	Aportul de substanțe nutritive este superior, în cazul produselor agroalimentare ecologice față de cele convenționale	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
5	Produsele naturale sunt produse ecologice	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
6	Există produse ecologice necertificate, comercializate în piețe, la țărani	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
7	Unele produse de la țară sunt ecologice	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
8	Pentru o dietă sănătoasă, consum produse ecologice	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
9	Alimentele ecologice și cele convenționale au	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
10	Produsele tradiționale sunt ecologice	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
1	Am văzut des alimente ecologice în magazine	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
12	Nu sunt informat(ă) adecvat în legătură cu	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
13	Am nevoie de mai multe informații despre metodele de producție ecologică	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
14	Prefer alimente ecologice produse de companii	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
15	Oferta de alimente ecologice din România este	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
16	Raportul calitate/preț al alimentelor ecologice este	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
17	Nu îmi permit să cumpăr alimente ecologice atât de des pe cât mi-aș dori	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
18	Cumpăr alimente ecologice pentru ca nu conțin organisme modificate genetic	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
19	Alimentele ecologice sunt indicate copiilor	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
20	Mă satur mai repede când consum alimente	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
21	Alimentele ecologice îmi aduc aminte de ce	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
22	Unii cumpără produse ecologice doar pentru că sunt	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
23	Am încercat produse ecologice din curiozitate	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
24	Produsele ecologice sunt produse de lux	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
25	Nu cred că există produse cu adevărat ecologice	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
26	Nu am găsit alimentele pe care le consum de obicei în varianta ecologică certificată	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
27	Nu caut în mod special produse ecologice	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
28	Nu am auzit de nici o campanie de promovare a alimentelor ecologice	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
29	Cei din mediul rural consumă alimente ecologice, din propria gospodărie	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
30	Cumpăr produse ecologice ca să mă răsfăț, la ocazii speciale	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]

EFFECTS ON THE COMPETITIVENESS OF FOOD BUSINESSES OF THE NEW NOVEL FOOD REGULATION

A.A. BAICU* M.E. POPA*

Abstract: From a theoretical point of view, the new novel food regulation is simplifying the authorization procedure, opening the market also for small and medium food businesses. This empiric research has shown that for the consumer the big companies are considered more trustworthy and have a bigger chance to rule the market. The small and medium sized companies will find it easier to enter the market with a novel food on the base of the new novel food regulation, but they will face the barrier set by the consumer behavior.

Keywords: novel food, consumers, competitiveness, innovation, food regulation.

1. Introduction

From the beginning of trade, when people used to exchange goods, they observed that having a vast variety of goods to exchange, made them more well-known in the market and to have more success with their business. They have also realized that having special products is an advantage, so they started to travel to other far places in order to obtain more and more unique and diversified goods. It is known that the commerce with corn, tomato seeds, potatoes, spices, tobacco and tea was developed in this way.

Nowadays, the discussions about innovation and competitiveness in the market are on the same attitude.

The food businesses follow the same idea of innovation as in the past, and even more because of new factors that are taken into consideration in the last century such as the growing of the population and the limited resources. Moreover, it was demonstrated that the innovative ideas not only make the food firms to survive, but also to prosper (Bremmers, H., 2014).

In the food industry, innovation is confronting not only with the suspiciousness of the consumer to new food, but also with the ideas of some countries and continents where the consumer doesn't have enough information and knowledge to be able to decide if the innovative food is good for him and the authorities should apply legislation that should protect the consumers. The acceptance of a technology depends on the consumer's perception of benefits and risks. These include the impact of the technology on taste, convenience, nutritional value, the perceived safety of the process or technology, the magnitude of the risk the technology reduces and the effect of the technology on the environment (Popa, M.E., 2012).

In the European Union, The General Food Law (Reg. (EC) 178/2002 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 28 January 2002 laying down the general principles and requirements of food law, establishing the European Food Safety Authority and laying down procedures in matters of food safety), in article 14(1) it is stated that 'food shall not be placed on the market if it is unsafe'. This article says that

there is need for evidence to prove that a food is unsafe in order to be taken out of the market and there is no need of pre-market approval for food.

Nonetheless, there are food categories that require pre-market authorizations in order to be proven as safe and to be placed on the market. The authorization process's main reasons are to prevent unsafe food to be placed on the market, to avoid misleading the consumer and to ensure that the food and ingredients which they are destined to substitute do not lead to any nutritional disadvantage for the consumer.

The scope of this study is to analyse the effect of the **new European novel food regulation** on the competitiveness of food businesses. This study will also compare the *novel food* legislation that exists in the USA, China and Africa, and the consequences of different or similar legislations on the competitiveness of the food industry.

In the second part of this study, the consumer's opinion and behaviour regarding *novel food* will be analysed. A research based on a survey will reflect the influence of consumer's opinion on food businesses competitiveness related to *novel food*. By checking the consumer's opinion, will be analysed whether the *new European novel food regulation* has beneficial consequences on the food business operators as well as on the shop flow.

2. What novel food is?

Over the years, the concept of *novel food* has known several approaches. If before 1997, the topic was not regulated by the European Parliament and the Council, it was highly discussed after 15th of May 1997, when the Reg. (EC) 258/97 of the European Parliament and Council of 27 January 1997 concerning *novel food and novel food ingredients* (hereinafter: 'novel food regulation') came into force. At that time, it regulated genetically modified organisms as well, but in 2003 an independent, updated EU legal framework on GMOs was released.

It is obvious that the subject became popular, especially after the incidence with the Bovine

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spongiform encephalopathy (the so called ‘mad cow disease’) and other food scandals, so the vigilance in assuring the food safety for the consumer has increased (Brossard, 2007).

After analyzing and implementing the actual regulation on *novel food*, it has been noticed that the entire procedure turns out to be difficult to follow so the business operators face difficulties in putting on the market a *novel food* (European Parliament, 2015).

The concept of *novel food* was a subject of discussions regarding its definitions, due to the broad and indefinite meaning that has in the present time. As a result, the EU Commission has made a Proposal for a new novel food regulation in 2008. According to the 2008’s Proposal, the definition of *novel food* becomes more specific. Nevertheless, the discussion held by the European Parliament and the Council on this proposal, did not cover the situation of the definition. The debate was finally channelled to the cloning issue and this made the proposal not to be approved (EU Food Law, 2014).

As the first proposal, published in January 2008 failed due to a disagreement among the European Commission, the European Parliament and the European Council regarding the specific provisions on food from cloned animals (Law360), a new proposal has been adopted by the European Commission in December 2013 and published in January 2014. This new draft updates the categories of food that can fall under the definition of *novel food*.

Finally, the second proposal’s text was subject of negotiations among stakeholders. The European Parliament and the Council agreed on releasing *Reg. (EC) 2015/2283 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 November 2015 on novel foods, amending Regulation (EU) No 1169/2011 of the European Parliament and of the Council and repealing Regulation (EC) No 258/97 of the European Parliament and of the Council and Commission Regulation (EC) No 1852/2001* (hereinafter: ‘the new novel food regulation’). It has been adopted on the 25th of November 2015 and it will enter into force on the 1st of January 2018.

The legislator keeps the definition still centred on the cut-off date 17 of May 1997, so *novel food is food that has not been used for human consumption to a significant degree within the Community before 15 May 1997*. The new definition of *novel food* aims to be clearer, nominating certain particulars that are included: substances containing or consisting of ‘engineered nanomaterials’ (as nanotechnologies are not yet regulated); vitamins, minerals that are produced with a new production process or consist of ‘engineered nanomaterials’. According to the new definition, *novel food* includes also food supplements that have not been used within the Community before 15 May 1997.

Compared to the 2008 proposal, the new regulation addresses more clearly the ‘food from a third country’

aspect as well as the meaning of ‘history of safe food use in a third country’.

3. Novel food legislation in other countries

China. In China, the *novel food* concept is addressed in the *Administrative Measures for Safety Review of New Food Materials* regulations (hereinafter “the new Chinese regulation”) that came into force in October 2013, after the abrogation of the prior regulation from 2007. In the 2007 regulation, the term that was used was ‘novel food’. In the new Chinese regulation, the term was changed to ‘new food material’ and it refers to food and materials that are not traditionally consumed in China, including plants, animal, micro-organisms and their derivate substances, as well as food substances whose original structure is changed. Other food ingredients that are newly developed are also included.

Under the new Chinese legislation, ‘new food materials’ have to possess the attributes of normal food, complying with their specific nutritional values and being ‘toxin-free and harmless, and shall not cause any acute, sub-acute, chronic or other latent health hazards’. (*Administrative Measures for Safety Review of New Food Materials 2013*, art. 3)

In order to put a ‘new food material’ on the market, a food business operator needs approval. The applicant has to submit a dossier that contains specific material, as listed in article 6 of the *Administrative Measures for Safety Review of Food Materials*.

The application is then published. Consumers, professionals and anyone else can give comments and scientific review. When the ‘new food material’ is approved, a public notice is made and the product can be placed on the market. If the ‘new food material’ becomes suspicious after the product was already placed on the market, the approval can be cancelled.

Africa. For this study, as a representative country for Africa, **Ghana** has been chosen.

In Ghana there are no specific laws or definitions for *novel food*, but there is a main regulation which is focused on foods, drugs, cosmetics, devices and chemical substances: *Food and Drugs Act, 1992 (P.N.D.C.L.305B)* (hereinafter: ‘the Ghanaian act’). In this general act the food segment has its own special section, addressing 10 different topics and starting with a prohibition against the sale of unwholesome food.

Another part of the Ghanaian act defines rules that food production should follow. According this act, food should be manufactured under proper supervision. The supervision has to be made by a person that has appropriate knowledge and qualification that will ensure the purity and wholesomeness of the food (*Food and Drugs, Ghana*).

USA. In the USA there are no regulations for food in general but only for ingredients. There is no definition of *novel food* in the USA and no legislation referring to it. The American authorities consider new

food ingredients to fall mainly into the following categories:

- a. food additives, or
- b. GRAS (generally recognized as safe) substances.

A GRAS substance does not require pre-market approval but an un-official notification to the FDA is recommended. A food ingredient is considered to be GRAS when there are evidences that it was used in the US before 1958 or in another country outside of the US. It can also be considered as GRAS passing a scientific procedure (made by the manufacturer, the FDA or by an expert panel), that will prove the safety of the ingredient (Sinopoli, D. 2015).

4. The relation between food businesses competitiveness and innovation and the new regulation on novel food

As the *new novel food regulation*'s aim is to centralize and simplify the procedure of authorisation on *novel food*, the consequences would be reflected on the time and costs that a company has to spend in order to deal with the pre-market approval requirements of a *novel food*.

If the costs with the authorisation procedure are lower, the small and medium companies will be able to enter the market with *novel food*. It is known that under the current regulation on *novel food* vast amounts of costs are needed to accomplish these procedures and it can take up to 12 years and still not be approved (*Case C-327/09, Stevia*). In his lecture about *Pre-market approval in the EU*, Mr. Martin Holle highlighted the costs of bringing a new product on the market, falling under the *actual novel food regulation*. The request for authorisation of the phytosterols was addressed, concluding that the final costs were between 19 to 24 million of euro (Holle, 2014).

By regulating the traditional food from a third country, the market can be easier opened for the small and medium firms to import from those countries. The authorisation procedure would be simplified in this case; the food business operators would need to bring evidence in the significant degree of consumption of a certain product in the last 25 years, and then to intercede for importing it.

As mentioned in the previous section, both China and USA pay more attention lately on *new ingredients* instead of on *novel food*, while African countries (Ghana) prefer to issue legislative acts that will ensure the safety of food in general. China and USA regulate new final food products but do not regulate the production process of it.

Therefore it can be observed that the EU zone is much stricter with *novel food* than Africa, China and USA. This makes food operators or food producers in China and USA more flexible to design *new food ingredients* or *novel food*.

At the same time, companies may have benefits if they import goods that include *new ingredients* from USA or China, because EU Regulation on *novel food* will cost them much more funds and will take longer time, which are two most important aspects for developing and market share.

EU market also owns less attraction for international food companies that design and produce *novel food*. The companies in Europe may also present a lack of international competitiveness, since they have less interest on trade of novel food.

However, *novel food* or *new ingredients* now have already led the development of food industry with innovation and improvement of modern science and technology.

5. The survey

This research aims to prove that with a *new novel food regulation* being approved, the competitiveness will be increased due to the legal text, but on the shop level the competitiveness will be less increased in the coming short period of time because of consumer mentalities and behaviour with regards to buying food in general and specially to buying *novel food*.

In order to measure the consumer's willingness to buy *novel food* from big/well-known/trusted companies or from small companies, a research has been realized.

The study has been carried out in two different environments: the *open market in the city centre of the city of Wageningen, Netherlands* and the *Forum Building – Wageningen University and Research Centre*. The reason for choosing these two places was to create a differentiation between a more educated and familiar with *novel food* ambience that could represent more informed consumers that could analyse the innovation in general and in this case the *novel food*, and a common ambience that could represent the big part of the consumers of today that doesn't have the information and the attitude to analyse the food innovations.

With this research we also wanted to find if a well-informed consumer could choose by himself to buy *novel food* or not and if the manufactures should be obliged by regulation to develop a wide public education program instead of strict pre-market regulations or even well informed consumers are not able to make a rational choice because of being afraid of unknown food and therefore there is need for the pre-market regulations as proposed in the law.

During the interviews, the interviewed persons were provided with detailed information related to the *difference* between '**new food**' and '**novel food**'.

The sampling was non-random and the choice criterion was to harvest data from two different ambiances: the academic one (Wageningen UR) and a common one (open market in city centre of Wageningen). From the Forum Building (Wageningen

UR) 30 students have been chosen, and from the open market, 30 random persons.

Within the limited framework in the questionnaire, we addressed 6 closed-questions.

The average duration of completing a questionnaire was 5-6 minutes and the field data collection was carried out from 21st of November to 26th of November 2014.

6. Findings

The charts in green colour represent the informed group and the charts in red colour represent the common group (Figures 1 to 6).

Question 1: When you buy food, do you check the labels in order to find information about the ingredients of the product?

This question was asked in order to define if the consumers from the Forum building are actually more heedful to the ingredients of the food in order to see the consumers' behaviour in buying food.

The results obtained by addressing the first question of the questionnaire reveal that in both groups of people, more than a half are conscious when they buy food and check the label for information in regards with the ingredients. However, it can be observed that the population from an academic ambience tend to pay more attention to this information than the common people in the open market. The difference is 10%.

Question 2: When you buy food, do you prefer it to be made by big/international companies or by small ones?

This question was asked to study the mentality of the consumers when buying regular food regarding the well-known producers and towards small, not well-known producers. For this question similar answers were given by both groups. 63% of the respondents prefer small food companies.

Question 3: Do you like to try new kinds of food?

This question was asked in order to see:

1. if additional information that could be given to consumers will affect their mentality regarding *new food*;
2. if the interviewed consumers are not open to any kind of *new food* at all.

When measuring the willingness of the respondents on trying new kinds of foods, it has been demonstrated that the population surveyed in the Open Market is more conservative than the one in the Forum Building.

Question 4: Did you ever hear about Novel food?

Despite of the different ambiances where the study has been carried out, from *Fig. 4* can be observed that almost three quarters of the surveyed group from the Forum Building declare that they never heard about *novel food*. Slightly more than a half of the analyzed

group from the Open Market affirmed they are familiar with the term of *novel food*.

There is a possibility that part of the interviewed consumers in the open market did not make a difference between *novel food* and *new food* despite the detailed explanations provided. However, from the comparison of the answers in question 6 to answers to question 2 it can be seen that there is a large difference so it reflects the difference the consumers did between *new food* and *novel food*.

Question 5: Would you buy novel food?

This question was asked in order to see if the consumers are more cautious in buying *novel food* rather than *new food*.

From the comparison of the answers to this question and answer to question 3 it can be seen that the both checked groups intend to buy *novel food* less than *new food*. These result reflects that the interviewed consumers distinguished between *novel food* and *new food* and it matched our expectation that consumers will be more cautious towards *novel food*.

Question 6: Would you prefer to buy this kind of food (novel food) from a big, well-known company or you would you buy it from a smaller company as well?

This question was asked in order to check if the producers could actually enter the market with *novel food* considering the approval of the *new novel food* regulation and the theoretically high chances in doing so, due to the simplicity of the new authorisation process.

Comparing the answer to this question with the answers to the second question, when it is about *novel food*, both groups have a higher interest in buying from bigger companies. It has been observed that even more conservative people who would not buy *novel food*, in case they would try it, they would prefer it to be from a big company rather than from a small one. This comparison also reflects the fact that consumers distinguished between *novel food* and *new food*.

7. Conclusions

From the findings of this study it can be concluded that about 70% of the consumers (from the both groups) are self-conscious with regards to the information provided on the food labels.

Almost 33% of the consumers in the research preferred to buy *novel food* from a big, well known company.

By this research it has been demonstrated that theoretically, small and medium sized food companies would have more opportunities to enter the market under the *new novel food regulation*, because the time and money invested on the authorisation procedure would decrease tremendously.

However, by an empirical analysis, the effect of the *new novel food regulation* is different on the consumer's opinion. Consumers would be suspicious on *novel food* and they would prefer to buy it from big, well-known companies that they consider to be trustworthy.

It is appropriate to highlight the willingness of the consumer on buying the traditional food products from smaller companies, boutique companies, or local ones, considering that aliments manufactured on a larger scale will not provide the same specific quality.

However, in regards of *novel food* particularly, the consumers are still cautious and deem that bigger companies will fit better standards.

To summarize, it seems reasonable to say that the *new novel food* regulation will increase the competitiveness in the food business but the small and

medium sized companies will still be confronted with barriers in entering the market. Presumably, the small and medium food businesses will have to wait one more stage, when the consumers will gather more information and confidence on *novel food* after buying it from the big companies.

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Fig. 1. Answers to Question 1: When you buy food, do you check the labels in order to find information about the ingredients of the product?

Fig. 2. Answers to Question 2: When you buy food, do you prefer it to be made by big/international companies or by small ones?

Fig. 3. Answers to Question 3: Do you like to try new kinds of food?

Fig. 4. Answers to Question 4: Did you ever hear about novel food?

Fig. 5. Answers to Question 5: Would you buy novel food?

Fig. 6. Answers to Question 6: Would you prefer to buy this kind of food (novel food) from a big, well-known company or you would you buy it from a smaller company as well?

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STUDY ON THE LEVEL OF GRAPE SEED FLOUR (%) ADDITION IN WHEAT FLOUR UPON THE CHARACTERISTICS OF BREAD DOUGH

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Abstract: *GSP (grape seed powder) were added at 5%, 10%, 15% flour substitution level for different bakery recipes. The final products after baking were analyzed taking in consideration: Size (Dough or batter piece weight; Product volume); Shape (Modeling, shaping, forming or depositing; Using pans, trays or processing as a free-standing item); External color (Ingredients and their qualities; Formulation, ingredient ratios; Baking and other processing technologies); Crust character (Baking temperatures, times and control of oven atmosphere, e.g. the use of steam or oven damper); Crumb cellular structure (Ingredient qualities; Formulation, ingredient ratios; Mixing and other processing technologies; Heat transfer during baking); Internal color (Ingredient qualities; Formulation, ingredient ratios; Crumb cellular structure); Crumb softness (Final product moisture content; Ingredient qualities; Formulation, ingredient ratios; Crumb cellular structure; Baking temperatures, times and control of oven atmosphere; Post-baking treatment, for example packaging and staling); Mouth-feel (Moisture; Crumb cellular structure; Formulation, ingredient ratios; Post-baking treatment); Taste (Specialist processing, such as prolonged fermentation of bread dough; Ingredient qualities; Formulation, ingredient ratios; Crumb cellular structure; Baking temperatures, times and control of oven atmosphere; Post-baking treatment); Aroma (Specialist processing; Ingredient qualities; Formulation, ingredient ratios; Crumb cellular structure; Baking temperatures and times; Post-baking treatment.)*

The results show that the addition of GSP at the level between 5...10% as flour substitution in bakery recipes has a big potential in functional food designing, taken in consideration many parameters, from technological to sensorial ones.

Key words: *Grape seed flour, quality parameters, bread.*

1. Introduction

Due to the antioxidant properties of grape seeds from the oligomeric proanthocyanidins complex (OPC), the grape seed extract is recommended for many diseases. Research has shown efficacy of OPC from grape seed for damaged blood vessels or weak blood vessels, for the treatment of diabetic retinopathy, edema (fluid accumulation) in the arms and legs and high cholesterol and could prevent cognitive decline. [16]. Due to the proanthocyanidins component from grape seeds, they have an important role as a neuro-protectant in the hippocampus and in preventing cognitive loss that can occur with age.

The study was to determine the effects of grape seed (GS) on the characteristic of and bread-dough properties.

2. Materials and Method

A common commercial wheat flour, ground (T 512) (moisture content (MC) = 13.50 %, ash = 0.55 %, gluten (GC) = 34.10 %, Falling number (FN) = 296s) provided by Carrefour Romania was used for the evaluation. Grape seeds were dried up to 2 to 4 % moisture and defatted by cold pressing to produce virgin grape seed oil as a main product.

The defatted seeds were ground to a grape seed flour of particle size 100 to 150 µm required for dough preparation. GSP (grape seed powder) were added at 5%, 10%, 15% flour substitution level for different bakery recipes [6], [7].

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Table 1. Recipe used for bakery products with grape seed flour substitution

Ingredients	Bread control (0% flour substitution)	Bread 5% flour substitution	Bread 10% flour substitution	Bread 15% flour substitution
Flour type 650	375.5 g	356.5 g	337.5 g	319.5
Yeast	8 g	8 g	8 g	8 g
Salt	6 g	6 g	6 g	6 g
Oil	2 g	2 g	2 g	2 g
Grape seed flour	-	19 g	38 g	56 g
Water	190 ml	190 ml	190 ml	190 ml

After baking, the final products were analyzed taking into account the following criteria: Volume score, Average volume, Specific volume, Uniformity of shape, Crust characteristic, Break and shred, Cell structure, Crumb colour, Crumb strength, Texture, Flavour and Aroma. Next (Table 1), are presented the exact quantities that were used for obtaining bread, through the direct method [10], [12].

Using the standard program of the bread baking machine that lasts about 3 hours, are presented the technological processes: 1st kneading (5 min), rest (5 min), 2nd kneading (20 min), first leavening (39 min), 3rd kneading (10 seconds), second leavening (25 minutes and 50 seconds), 4th kneading (15 seconds), 3rd leavening (49 minutes and 45 seconds), and ripening (43 minutes).

Assessing baked-product quality starts with a consideration of the external features

and moves to the internal features. The main features that are likely to be considered are listed in Table 2.

As will be discussed in later chapters, there are many factors contributing to variation in baked-product qualities. Some of the main ones may be summarized as follows:

- **Size**

- Dough or batter piece weight;
- Product volume;

- **Shape**

- Modeling, shaping, forming or depositing;
- Using pans, trays or processing as a free-standing item;

- **External color**

- Ingredients and their qualities;

- Formulation, ingredient ratios;
- Baking and other processing technologies;

- **Crust character**

- Baking temperatures, times and control of oven atmosphere, e.g. the use of steam or oven damper;

- **Crumb cellular structure**

- Ingredient qualities;
- Formulation, ingredient ratios;
- Mixing and other processing technologies;
- Heat transfer during baking;

- **Internal color**

- Ingredient qualities;
- Formulation, ingredient ratios;
- Crumb cellular structure;

- **Crumb softness**

- Final product moisture content;
- Ingredient qualities;
- Formulation, ingredient ratios;
- Crumb cellular structure;
- Baking temperatures, times and control of oven atmosphere;
- Post-baking treatment, for example packaging and staling;

- **Mouth-feel**

- Moisture;
- Crumb cellular structure;
- Formulation, ingredient ratios;
- Post-baking treatment;

- **Taste**

- Specialist processing, such as prolonged fermentation of bread dough;
- Ingredient qualities;
- Formulation, ingredient ratios;
- Crumb cellular structure;
- Baking temperatures, times and control of oven atmosphere;
- Post-baking treatment;

- **Aroma**

- Specialist processing;
- Ingredient qualities;

- Formulation, ingredient ratios;
- Crumb cellular structure;
- Baking temperatures and times;
- Post-baking treatment.

Table 2. *Main features considered in making an evaluation of baked-product qualities*

Features	External	Internal
Size	Y	N
Shape	Y	N
Crust character	Y	Y
Colour	Y	Y
Crumb cellular structure	N	Y
Softness	N	Y
Mouth-feel	Y	Y
Taste	Y	Y
Aroma	Y	Y

Subjective scoring sheets go beyond the simple recording of product attributes and tries to provide a framework for making more objective comparisons of baked-product qualities. Among the main problems with subjective evaluations are the inevitable variations in scoring between individuals and drift with time for any given individual. Thus, in order to make effective use of

scoring sheets it is necessary to have trained individuals making the assessment. It is also helpful to have some fixed reference points that any assessor may use. These usually comprise templates of size or shape, photographs (especially for internal appearance), color prints or 'chips' and standard descriptors. The scoring sheet for bread used is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. *Quality descriptors for bakery products*

External	Quality descriptors
Volume score (10)	A. Small B. Large
Average volume, cc	
Specific volume, cc/g	
Uniformity of shape (10)	A. Lack of boldness B. Uneven top C. Shrunken sides D. Low side E. Low middle F. Flat top G. Small end
Crust characteristic (10)	A. Light B. Dark C. Uneven D. Dull E. Thick F. Tough G. Brittle
Break and shred (10)	A. Wild B. None C. Shelled D. Insufficient
<i>Subtotal 40</i>	
Internal	
Cell structure (20)	A. Open coarse B. Thick cell walls C. Holes D. Non-uniform
Crumb color (10)	A. Dull grey B. Creamy
Crumb strength (10)	A. Tough B. Weak
Texture (10)	A. Rough B. Core C. Crumbly D. Firm E. Gummy
Flavour and aroma (10)	A. Satisfactory B. Unsatisfactory
<i>Subtotal 60</i>	
Total scor: 100	

3. Results and Discussion

According to the set methodology, the maximum recommended for replacement with grape seed flour is 5%, ensuring maximum functional compounds valuable in terms of minor technological changes and keeping quality conditions for the obtained products. Higher

additions of grape seed flour (80 to 100 g/kg) were unacceptable on the part of assessors and final quality of bread, too. The dark color of the bread produced is a positive aspect, too (according to preference of consumers today).

Table 4. Parameters checked for quality evaluation of bakery products

External	Quality descriptors				
	maximum	control	5%	10%	15%
Volume score (10)	10	9	8	7	6
Average volume, cc					
Specific volume, cc/g					
Uniformity of shape (10)	10	9	9	6	4
Crust characteristic (10)	10	10	8	6	5
Break and shred (10)	10	8	8	7	7
<i>Subtotal 40</i>	40	36	33	26	22
Internal					
Cell structure (20)	20	20	18	15	10
Crumb color (10)	10	10	10	10	10
Crumb strength (10)	10	8	6	6	5
Texture (10)	10	9	8	6	4
Flavour and aroma (10)	10	10	10	9	8
<i>Subtotal 60</i>	60	57	52	47	37
Total scor: 100	100	93	85	53	59

Conclusions

Different ingredients are included in bread formulations to improve nutritional and health benefits, organoleptic properties and shelf life. Grape seeds, a major component of grape pomace, are a waste product of the wine industry. Grape seed products (flour, oil, o/w emulsion etc.) belong to a group of additives with health benefits. A variety of nutraceutical and bioactive compounds, including procyanidins, phenolic compounds, tannins, dietary fibre, and resveratrol, a cancer chemopreventive agent, can be extracted from grape seeds. Antioxidants have also been found in cereals plant and seed oils, vegetables. Natural antioxidants including tocopherols and phenolic compounds may act to confer an effective defense system against free radical attack. Phenolic antioxidants have been viewed as an important class of food ingredients either as food additives or as novel ingredients to introduce extra health benefits to various food products.

The results will be applied on a large scale in a pilot production line in the bakery laboratory of Trasilvania University of Brasov.

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